

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D2.1 Initial Network Application blueprints and Open Repository design

Document Summary Information

Start Date	01/01/2021	Duration	36 months
Project URL	www.vital5g.eu		
Deliverable	D2.1 Initial Network Application blueprints and Open Repository design		
Related Work Package	WP2	Related Task	T2.1, T2.2
Contractual due date	31/12/2021	Actual submission date	V1.0 23/12/2021 V2.0 07/04/2023
Type	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Editor	Esteban Municio (IMEC), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC)		

Contributors and Peer Reviewers

Contributors
Giada Landi (NXW), Elian Kraja (NXW), Juan Brenes (NXW), Gino Carrozzo (NXW), Erin Seder (NXW), Esteban Municio (IMEC), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Ali Anwar (IMEC), Olivier Vasseur (IMEC), Jens Duym (IMEC), Valentin Carlan (DT), Aleksander Chernyavskiy (SF), Najmeh Masoudi Dionne (SF), Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS), Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Ilias Kotinas (WINGS), Nikos Tzagkarakis (WINGS), Konstantinos Kokkalis (WINGS), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS) George Guirlis (EBOS), Athina Ropodi (INCE), Chrysa Iliopoulou (INCE), Aristotelis Margaris (INCE), Kostas Tsagkaris (INCE), Alexandru Vulpe (BEIA), George Suciu (BEIA), George Iordache (BEIA)
Peer Reviewers
Christina Lessi (OTE), Lian Xiangyu (TEL)

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
v0.01	13/10/2021	2%	Initial Deliverable Structure	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.02	20/10/2021	2%	Revised version of the ToC	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.03	25/10/2021	5%	Revised version of the ToC	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.05	26/10/2021	5%	Revised version of the ToC	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.1	08/11/2021	10%	Input in 5.2.1, 5.2.5 and 5.2.6	Kostas Trichias (WINGS)
v0.15	08/11/2021	15%	Input in Section 2	Juan Brenes (NXW)
v0.2	10/11/2021	20%	Input in Section 3.1	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.25	15/11/2021	25%	Input in 3.2.13 and 4. Added blueprint example in Annex.	Giada Landi (NXW)
v0.3	17/11/2021	30%	Input in Section 8	Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS)
v0.35	22/11/2021	35%	Added section 3.1.4	Giada Landi (NXW)
v0.4	22/11/2021	40%	Added VS6, VA5 and VA5 blueprint	Jens Duym, Olivier Vasseur, Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.45	22/11/2021	45%	Updated section 2.2.1, added sections 2.2.2, 3.2.3, 5.2.2, 6.2	Giada Landi, Juan Brenes, Elian Kraja (NXW)
v0.5	22/11/2021	50%	Minor updates from WP2 meeting 22 Nov 2021	Esteban Municio (IMEC)

v0.55	24/11/2021	55%	Input and Blueprints of VS5, VS6, VS8 and VA5	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.6	26/11/2021	60%	Input for Section 5.3, Section 6.3, executive summary and Intro	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.65	29/11/2021	65%	Added input and blueprint for VS7	Valentin Carlan (DT)
V0.67	29/11/2021	67%	Added blueprints for VS3 and VS4 Updated Vertical Service and Network Application blueprint data models	Giada Landi, Juan Brenes (NXW)
v0.7	29/11/2021	70%	Added section 3.2.10, 5.4, 7.1, 7.3	Giada Landi, Juan Brenes (NXW)
v0.72	29/11/2021	72%	Added input for sections 3.1.2, 3.2.2, 3.2.6, 3.2.15; Added blueprints for VA2, VA6, VS9	Alexandru Vulpe, George Iordache, George Suciu, Lucian Necula, Ion Marghescu, Silviu Ciochina, Cornelia Alexandru (BEIA)
v0.73	29/11/2021	73%	Additional Input for VS1, VS2 and completing VA1	Ilias Kotinas (WINGS)
v0.76	29/11/2021	76%	Adjustments according to 29 th Nov WP2 weekly meeting and updates on Sections 5.3 and 6.3	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.78	29/11/2021	78%	Minor edits and Conclusions	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.8	30/11/2021	80%	Added vs1 and vs2 blueprints and updated Network Applications diagrams and descriptions	Ilias Kotinas (WINGS)
v0.82	30/11/2021	82%	Updating Web GUI Section	Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS)
V0.85	02/12/2021	85%	Added content for VA2, VA3	Athina Ropodi, Chrysa Iliopoulou, Aristotelis Margaritis (INCE)
v0.87	02/12/2021	87%	Updated sections 3.2.6, 3.2.15. Input to section 7.2	Alexandru Vulpe, George Suciu (BEIA)
v0.9	02/12/2021	90%	Closing first complete version of the document. Glossary and some references	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.92	03/12/2021	92%	Updating Access Control section	Ilias Kotinas (WINGS)
v0.93	03/12/2021	93%	Updates on VS5 input and blueprint	Aleksander Chernyavskiy (SF)

v0.95	03/12/2021	95%	Fixing references and finalising first D2.1 version	Esteban Municio (IMEC)
v0.96	13/12/2021	96%	Document reviewed by OTE, TEL, and NXT	Christina Lessi (OTE), Giada Landi (NXW), Lian Xiangyu (TEL)
v0.97	13/12/2021	97%	Comments assigned to partners, to be addressed by the end of the week	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC)
v0.98	17/12/2021	98%	Comments addressed by all partners	Juan Brenes (NXW), Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC), Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Valentin Carlan (DT), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS)
v0.99	17/12/2021	99%	All changes integrated	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC)
v1.0	23/12/2021	100%	Final Project Coordinator Review & approval	Kostas Trichias (WINGS)
V2.0	24/12/2022	95%	Comments for resubmission assigned to partners, to be addressed by 13/01/2023	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC)
V2.1	13/01/2023	98%	Comments addressed in supplementary documents	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC)
V2.2	31/01/2023	99%	All changes integrated, version prepared for the review	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC)
V2.3	23/03/2023	100%	Changes based on reviewers' comments provided	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac (IMEC)
V2.4	30/03/2023	100%	QA Review	Andreas Gavrielides (eBOS)
V2.5	04/04/2023	100%	Final Project Coordinator Review & approval	Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS)

Disclaimer

The content of this document reflects only the author's view. Neither the European Commission nor the INEA are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

While the information contained in the documents is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the VITAL-5G consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose.

Neither the VITAL-5G Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein.

Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the VITAL-5G Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Copyright message

© VITAL-5G Consortium. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	14
1 Introduction.....	16
1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs	16
1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	19
2 Network Applications Concepts and Modeling	20
2.1 Network Application definition and characterization.....	20
2.2 Data Models of Network Application packages and T&L services	21
2.2.1 Network Application Blueprint data model.....	22
2.2.2 Vertical Service Blueprint data model	32
3 VITAL-5G Network Applications	36
3.1 Network Applications mapping to Use cases and T&L Services	36
3.1.1 Assisted Vessel Transport.....	36
3.1.2 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras	38
3.1.3 Automation & remote operation of freight logistics.....	40
3.1.4 Remote technical monitoring and predictive maintenance.....	41
3.2 Definition of VITAL-5G Network Applications.....	44
3.2.1 VA1 Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & automation.....	44
3.2.2 VA2 Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & post-processing.....	46
3.2.3 VA3 Predictive Maintenance	49
3.2.4 VA4 IoT Management platform.....	51
3.2.5 VA5 Real time digital twin	53
3.2.6 VA6 Data stream organization.....	55
3.2.7 VS1 Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning.....	56
3.2.8 VS2 Human-robot collaboration.....	57
3.2.9 VS3 AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance	58
3.2.10 VS4 Technical Data Visualization	60
3.2.11 VS5 Remote Vessel Monitoring.....	62
3.2.12 VS6 Assisted vessel navigation	63
3.2.13 VS7 Navigation speed optimizer.....	65
3.2.14 VS8 Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II.....	67
3.2.15 VS9 Onboard data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel	69
4 The VITAL-5G platform	70
5 The VITAL-5G Portal Backend.....	76
5.1 Intent-Based interface	76
5.2 Service Lifecycle Manager (Service LCM).....	78
5.3 T&L Service Monitoring.....	84
5.3.1 Data Collection Manager	85
5.3.2 Data Collection Storage	87
5.4 Experiment Lifecycle Manager (Experiment LCM).....	89
5.5 Results Analytics.....	93
5.6 AI-based Performance Diagnostics	96
6 The VITAL-5G Management Backend.....	101
6.1 Access Control.....	101
6.2 Multi-site Inventory	102
6.3 Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory.....	103
7 The VITAL-5G Open Online Repository.....	106

7.1	Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue	106
7.2	Network Application Validator.....	111
7.3	License Manager	112
8	VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI.....	116
8.1	Design Experiment in VITAL-5G	116
8.2	Data Visualization.....	118
9	Conclusions.....	119
	References	120
	Annex I: Network Application Blueprints	121
9.1	VA1 blueprint: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation	121
9.2	VA2 blueprint: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing.....	124
9.3	VA3 blueprint: Predictive Maintenance.....	128
9.4	VA4 blueprint: IoT Management Platform	131
9.5	VA5 blueprint: Real Time Digital twin	135
9.6	VA6 blueprint: Data stream organization	140
9.7	VS1 blueprint: Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning	142
9.8	VS2 blueprint: Human-robot collaboration	144
9.9	VS3 blueprint: AI/ML based automated fault detection.....	146
9.10	VS4 blueprint: Technical Data Visualization.....	149
9.11	VS5 blueprint: Remote Vessel Monitoring	151
9.12	VS6 blueprint: Assisted vessel navigation.....	155
9.13	VS7 blueprint: Navigation Speed Optimizer	158
9.14	VS8 blueprint: Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II	161
9.15	VS9 blueprint: Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessels NAVROM.....	164

List of Figures

Figure 1:	High-level representation of a Network Application package	21
Figure 2:	Network Application Package structure.....	22
Figure 3:	Network Application blueprint data model.....	23
Figure 4:	5GEndpoint data model	24
Figure 5:	InfrastructureMetric data model	24
Figure 6:	InterfaceServiceSpec data model	24
Figure 7:	Vertical Service Blueprint data model.....	32
Figure 8:	Vertical Service “Remote Technical Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance”.....	44
Figure 9:	VA1 Network Application: Distribution Sensor ingestion and automation.....	45
Figure 10:	Network architecture of VA1.....	46
Figure 11:	VA2 Network Application: Workflow	47
Figure 12:	VA2 Network Application blueprint: Components & external endpoints.....	48
Figure 13:	VA3 Network Application: Workflow	49
Figure 14:	VA3 Network Application blueprint: Components & external endpoints.....	50
Figure 15:	Functional architecture of IoT Management Platform Network Application	52

Figure 16: Representation of IoT Management Platform Network Application blueprint – version with IoT supervisor installed as physical hardware on field..... 52

Figure 17: Representation of IoT Management Platform Network Application blueprint – version with IoT supervisor deployed as Network Application components in the virtual computing infrastructure 53

Figure 18: VA5 component model (Real time digital twin) 54

Figure 19: VA5 Network Application architecture 55

Figure 20: VA6 internal Network Application architecture..... 56

Figure 21: Representation of the AGV automation blueprint based on VS1 and VA1 combined operation..... 57

Figure 22: Representation of Human Robot collaboration using a combined VS2 and VA1 Network Application Blueprint..... 58

Figure 23: Functional architecture AI/ML-based fault detection & predictive maintenance Network Application 59

Figure 24: Deployment of VS3 Network Application for AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance in a 5G-enabled environment 60

Figure 25: Functional architecture of Technical Data Visualization Network Application and its cooperation with VA4 and VS3 61

Figure 26: Deployment of VS3 Network Application for AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance in a 5G-enabled environment 62

Figure 27: VS5 Network Application Architecture..... 63

Figure 28: VS6 component model 64

Figure 29: VS6 Network Application architecture 65

Figure 30: VS7 Network Application architecture 66

Figure 31: VS7 component model 67

Figure 32: VS8 component model 68

Figure 33: VS8 Network Application Architecture..... 68

Figure 34: VS9 Network Application Architecture..... 69

Figure 35: Software components of VITAL-5G platform 70

Figure 36: 5G EVE Intent based tool-Experiment blueprint and service parameters selection (13) 77

Figure 37: Vertical Service LCM Software Architecture 79

Figure 38: Vertical Service Instance Finite State Machine 83

Figure 39: T&L Service Monitoring architecture 85

Figure 40: Data Collection Manager architecture 86

Figure 41: DCS architecture..... 88

Figure 42: Dashboard Handler data model 89

Figure 43: High-level software architecture of the Experiment LCM..... 90

Figure 44: Finite State Machine for an experiment instance 92

Figure 45: VITAL-5G Results Analytics (RA) module – Block diagram	94
Figure 46: REST API for the VITAL-5G RA.....	95
Figure 47: Performance Diagnosis module workflow [20]	97
Figure 48: SOM Anomaly Detection Workflow	98
Figure 49: Root Cause Analysis process block diagram.....	100
Figure 50: Keycloak Core Concepts	101
Figure 51: Multi-site Inventory software architecture.....	103
Figure 52: Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory software architecture	105
Figure 53: Software architecture of VITAL-5G Network Application, Service and Experiment Catalogue	107
Figure 54: Conceptual architecture of the Network Application validator	112
Figure 55: Procedures for License Management.....	113
Figure 56: License Manager high-level software architecture	114
Figure 57: The home page of the 5G-EVE project [2].....	116
Figure 58: The instantiation of an experiment [2]	117
Figure 59: Experiment Blueprint Builder Wizard [2]	118
Figure 60: The Elastic Stack toolchain integrated with Beats and Kafka [2]	118

List of Tables

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....	16
Table 2: Network Application Package data model	21
Table 3: Network Application Blueprint element data model	25
Table 4: Component element data model	26
Table 5: InfrastructureMetric element data model	26
Table 6: ApplicationMetric element data model	27
Table 7: RequiredEquipment element data model	28
Table 8: ConnectivityService element data model.....	28
Table 9: SoftwareLicense element data model	28
Table 10: 5GServiceSpec element data model.....	29
Table 11: InterfaceServiceSpec element data model.....	29
Table 12: AttachedInterfaceSpec element data model.....	30
Table 13: Endpoint element data model.....	30
Table 14: SliceProfile data element model.....	30
Table 15: EMBBSliceServiceProfileParams data element model	31
Table 16: URLLCSliceServiceProfileParams data element model.....	31

Table 17: TestCaseSpec data element model.....	31
Table 18: VerticalServiceBlueprint data element model.....	32
Table 19: ServiceComponent data element model.....	34
Table 20: ServiceEndpoint data element model	34
Table 21: UC1 related Network Applications mapped to the two corresponding T&L services.....	36
Table 22: Detailed overview of Network Applications from the Assisted Vessel transport use case.....	37
Table 23: UC2 related Network Applications mapped to the three corresponding T&L services	38
Table 24: Detailed overview of Network Applications from the 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras use case.....	39
Table 25: UC3 related Network Applications mapped to the three corresponding T&L services	40
Table 26: Detailed overview of Network Applications from the Automation & remote operation of freight logistics use case	42
Table 27: Network Applications for Remote Technical Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance	43
Table 28: Detailed overview of Cross-Use Case Network Applications	43
Table 29: Functionalities differentiation	56
Table 30: List of VITAL-5G platform software components	71
Table 31: VITAL-5G platform components baseline and justification.....	73
Table 32: VMs for VITAL-5G platform deployment.....	75
Table 33: VITAL-5G Intent Based mechanism envisioned parameters	78
Table 34: T&L Service LCM supported actions	78
Table 35: Service LCM modules description and required extensions.....	80
Table 36: Service LCM Abstract Messages	83
Table 37: Data Collection Manager operations from its Open API specification.....	86
Table 38: T&L Service Testing abstract messages	92
Table 39: RA metric information object [19].....	95
Table 40: RA KPI information object [19]	95
Table 41: VITAL-5G Catalogue supported actions on NBI	108
Table 42: Abstract messages of VITAL-5G Catalogue NBI	110
Table 43: Abstract messages of License Manager NBI	115

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BMU	Best Matching Unit
CB	Context Blueprint
CNF	Cloud Network Function
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DCM	Data Collection Manager
DCS	Data Collection Storage
ELK	Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile BroadBand
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ExpB	Experiment Blueprint
ExpD	Experiment Descriptor
FSM	Finite State Machine
GB	Gigabyte
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HAL	Hardware Abstraction Layer
HD	High Definition
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol

I/O	Input Output
IB	Intent Based
IBN	Intent Based Networking
IWF	Interworking Function
IoT	Internet of Things
JPA	Java Persistence Architecture
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Life Cycle Management
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging of Laser Imaging Detection And Ranging
MANO	Management and Orchestration
ML	Machine Learning
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSNO	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator
NBI	North Bound Interface
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NFV SOL	NFV Solutions
NMS	Non-Maximum Suppression
NS	Network Service
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
NSO	Navigation Speed Optimizer
OSM	Open Source Mano
PD	Performance Diagnosis
RA	Results Analytics

RAM	Random Access Memory
RBAC	Role Based Access Control
RCA	Root-Cause Analysis
REST	Representational State Transfer
SBI	South Bound Interface
SNM	Service & Network Manager
SNPN	Stand-alone Non-Public Networks
SOM	Self-Organizing Maps
SQL	Structured Query Language
STEM	Service, Testing & Experiment Manager
T&L	Transport and Logistic
TCB	Test Case Blueprint
UC	Use Case
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication
VA	Vertical Agnostic
VDU	Virtual Deployment Units
VM	Virtual Machine
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VNFD	VNF Descriptor
VS	Vertical Specific
VSB	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
VSI	Vertical Service Instance
WebRTC	Web Real-Time Communication

Executive Summary

The deliverable D2.1 “Initial Network Applications blueprints and Open Repository design” is the first report of WP2 “VITAL-5G Platform Implementation”. It includes the initial outcomes of T2.1 “Network Applications development”. T2.1 mainly focuses on two tasks:

- The development of the vertical specific and agnostic Network Applications blueprints, that will be used in the VITAL-5G use cases, and some of them shared with the 3rd party experimenters
- The description of the software components and functionality of the VITAL-5G Platform (Portal Backend and Management Backend) and the Open Online Repository

This deliverable provides a first draft of both the VITAL-5G Network Applications blueprints and the internal details of the VITAL-5G Platform and Open Online Repository and their respective sub-components. In particular, Section 2.2 introduces the concept of Network Applications, as one of the key pillars of VITAL-5G since we envision them to be the building blocks of the T&L service chains on top of 5G-enabled infrastructures. The Network Applications are fundamental building blocks that abstract the complexity of 5G systems and are used for building complex T&L services that exploit 5G communications in the context of the three use cases defined in the project: (1) Assisted Vessel Transport, (2) 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras, and (3) Automation & remote operation of freight logistics. In this particular section, we explain the structure of the Network Application package, which consists of the main building blocks, such as: (1) VNF package (inheriting descriptor and image components from the Open Source MANO (OSM)-native VNF packaging structure), (2) Network Application blueprint that embeds all the details on Network Application features, structure, dependency on a particular hardware, monitoring capabilities, and 5G connectivity requirements. These building blocks are highly important for evaluating the overall network requirements of Network Applications and vertical services, mapping to the network and computing resources, as well as assigning them to particular 5G slices.

This deliverable presents the overall models, and strategies for design & development of Network Applications, and later on maps those well-established concepts to the three particular use cases defined in the scope of the VITAL-5G project. In particular, each use case is based on at least two vertical services, which are represented as chains of Network Applications that interact between each other and with end users (e.g., vessel or Automated Guided Vehicle) over the 5G network. For use case 1 Assisted Vessel Transport, this deliverable presents an overview of Network Applications that are chained into two vertical services delivering the functionality of this use case in the Antwerp trial site. These two vertical services are: (1) Vessel Navigation Assistance, which consists of the Assisted Vessel Navigation and Navigation Speed Optimizer Network Applications, and (2) Remote vessel monitoring, with On-board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II, Real-time Digital Twin, and Monitoring dashboard. In this deliverable, we provide an overview of vertical services and Network Applications that are enabling **5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras**. The three vertical services designed for this use case are (1) Data-enabled assisted navigation (Data stream organization & On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel Network Applications), (2) Accurate electronic navigation maps creation (Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing Network Application), and (3) Predictive maintenance and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship safety purposes (Remote inspection & risk assessment, and On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel, Network Applications).

Furthermore, the use case **Automation & remote operation of freight logistics** also consists of three vertical services: (1) Autonomous pallet transport within the warehouse (Network Applications: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation, and Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation), (2) Follow-me function for human-robot collaboration (Network Applications: Human-robot collaboration and Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation), and (3) Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation

(Network Applications: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation, and Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning). In addition, there are three Network Applications that do not belong to any of the three use cases, but used in a cross-use case manner, such as: (1) IoT Management platform for (i) unified collection, storage and basic processing of IoT data and (ii) control of actuators, interacting with multiple types of field buses (VA4), (2) AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance (VS3), and (3) Technical data visualization (VS4).

A subset of the presented Network Applications is open-source and as such fully available for the 3rd-party experimenters to reuse the source code when designing their own vertical services. On the other hand, most of the Network Applications designed for the three use cases provide a restricted access, which means that the vertical services and Network Applications from the 3rd-party experimenters can interface and interact with them (exchange data), but the source code is not publicly accessible. This deliverable provides the detailed overview of such an access per Network Application, including the justification on whether Network Application software has been reused from other projects and to what extent.

All Network Applications are classified as either Vertical-specific (VS) or Vertical-Agnostic (VA), which indicates their dependency to a particular vertical and use case scenario. Vertical agnostic Network Applications can be reused among different vertical services, and as such, can be suitable for building new vertical services and use cases with the 3rd-party experimenters.

This deliverable also focuses on the VITAL-5G platform and its constituting software components that deliver the platform functionalities, as derived from the functional architecture defined in D1.2 (1). All software components are grouped into three main categories depending on their role in the platform, i.e.,: (1) **core components** such as Service and Experiment Lifecycle Managers, Monitoring Platform, Blueprint Validation Tool, Network Application Catalogue, and Licence Manager, are in charge of the baseline functionalities that are enabling the experimental validation of vertical services composed of Network Applications in a 5G-enabled infrastructure, (2) **management services** such as Access Control, Slice inventory, and Multi-site inventory, support the core components with transversal functionalities related to the management of the user access to the VITAL-5G services, as well as the management of various aspects of the VITAL-5G testbeds, such as slice provisioning and configuration, and (3) **advanced functionalities** such as Result Analytics, AI-based diagnostic, and Intent-based requests manager, which are facilitating and improving the experiment execution, the management of the vertical services, thereby enhancing the analysis of the experiment results. As a subset of these components has been reused from the other related projects (e.g., 5G-EVE) an overview and justification per platform component are provided. Finally, in the Annex of this deliverable, we enclose the blueprints defined for all Network Applications, discribing the initial network requirements for each of the Network Applications (translated into slices info performance requirement on the 5G infrastructure), thereby including their dependency on a specific hardware, type of software image, among other parameters.

1 Introduction

The VITAL-5G project will design and implement a flexible platform that can host 5G-enabled Network Applications which will optimize the performance of the Transport & Logistics (T&L) vertical sector. In order to demonstrate how such Network Applications could help different T&L vertical sectors, VITAL-5G provides with an available repository of Network Applications that will be deployed and tested in three different Use Cases (see D1.1 [21]). The goal of these Network Applications is to address the T&L sector challenges, by offering extra functionalities, as described in Use case analysis in [21]. Additionally, the implemented Network Applications will inspire and help 3rd party experimenters (Network Application developers and vertical experimenters) to design and test their own Network Applications or vertical services, either by demonstrating certain functionalities or directly making them publicly available for their use and experimentation.

The goal of this Deliverable D2.1 document is two-folded:

- First, to describe the initial specifications of the Network Applications blueprints, giving details of their functionalities, internal architecture, and component model, and drafting a first version of the blueprints (given as JSON files in Annex I).
- Second, present the first details of the VITAL-5G Platform software architecture and each sub-component of the VITAL-5G Portal Backend, the VITAL-5G Management Backend, the Open Online Repository and the VITAL-5G Web GUI.

This document follows on the initial descriptions of the VITAL-5G Platform provided in D1.2 [1], and it is only focused on the software implementation of the components-

Additionally, since the software implementation of the VITAL-5G Platform is strongly based on the experimentation platform developed in the 5G EVE project [2], used as starting point for the development work, this document focuses in the main updates regarding 5G EVE software and the new VITAL-5G components. For the content that is still valid in each component and in order to avoid excessive redundancy, the reader is often referred to the specific deliverable and section of 5G EVE documentation where the information can be found.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T2.1 Network Applications development (Covered by D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)	The main goal of this task is the development of the vertical specific and agnostic Network Applications, that will be used in the VITAL-5G use cases and the respective relevant features	Section 2 and Section 3	Section 2 introduces the initial Network Application package and blueprint models. Section 3 lists each of the vertical specific and agnostic Network Applications, mapping them to the services and use cases they participate in,

			describing their main features and providing a first version of their blueprints (Annex I).
	The first phase of this task refers to the design and implementation of Network Applications in terms of number of VNFs in a service chain, and placement of VNFs on top of the vertical and cross-vertical infrastructure, based on the use case requirements that are recognized and defined in T1.1.	Section 3	In Section 3 Network Applications are grouped in T&L services and dependencies are established.
	In the second phase of the task, the developed Network Applications will be available at the Open online Network Application repository to be used by 3rd party experimenters, while the necessary functionality and tools will be developed to allow for the creation, onboarding and instantiation of additional Network Applications by other experimenters	Section 4, Section 5, Section 6, Section 7 and Section 8	A first version of the details of the VITAL-5G platform (Portal Backend and Management Backend), Open Online Repository and the VITAL-5G Web GUI is given in such sections
T2.2 VITAL-5G platform enhancement & Open repository development (Covered by D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)	The goal of this task is to implement the two main blocks of the VITAL-5G's Open platform, i.e., VITAL-5G portal and Open Online repository	Section 4, Section 5, Section 6, Section 7 and Section 8	In these sections, the high-level design of the VITAL-5G platform is presented, as well as different software modules (VITAL-5G Portal Backend, VITAL-5G Management Backend, VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, and VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI). In particular, section 7 details on the software modules of the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, which allows to publish and browse Network Applications, vertical services and experiments.
T2.3 Network Application	This task deals with verification and validation tools, methodologies and	Section 5, Section 7	Section 5 provides insights into advanced results analytics module, which will assist the evaluation

<p>verification tools (Covered by D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)</p>	<p>benchmarking procedures. The validation tools will be developed and used to pre-validate the Network Applications (in the lab) and to fully validate Network Applications using the VITAL-5G platform (in the field).</p>		<p>process of the experimentation results, as this module will be responsible for collecting all the metrics during an experiment, calculating KPIs, and validating them. In Section 7, more details on the Network Application validator are provided, as this validator tool will be used for both static validation before Network Application runtime, and for dynamic validation during onboarding/runtime, together with KPI monitoring and validation tool.</p>
<p>T2.4 Application & intelligence development (Covered by D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)</p>	<p>The main activities of this task are: i) definition and implementation of intelligent applications for the project use cases, ii) definition and implementation of distributed data ingestion, fusion and post-processing techniques for the experimentation data, iii) development of the Intent Based and Diagnostics mechanisms, and iv) (self) optimization of use cases based on intelligence inferred from steps ii) and iii).</p>	<p>Section 3, Section 5</p>	<p>Section 3 introduces the remote technical monitoring and predictive maintenance, a vertical service that integrates a custom processing logic enabled by AI/ML techniques for (early) faults detection and predictive maintenance. This section also introduces the vertical agnostic services for distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & automation, as well as distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & post-processing.</p> <p>Section 5 introduces the Intent Based Networking, which simplifies the creation, management and policy enforcement to the network layer with the use of AI/ML, and network orchestration.</p>
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D2.1 Initial Network Applications blueprints and Open Repository design</p> <p>Document describing the initial specifications of the Network Applications blueprints, the VITAL-5G platform and Open repository.</p>			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 gives a brief definition of Network Applications and a first version of the data models and blueprints for single Network Application and vertical services composed of multiple Network Applications.
- Section 3 presents the VITAL-5G Network Applications, first grouping them in T&L Services and Use Cases (Section 3.1) and later on, iterating through each of Network Application and presenting their functionalities and internal architecture. For each VITAL-5G Network Application an initial blueprint is provided in Annex I.
- Section 4 describes the VITAL-5G platform, giving an overview of its sub-components, and detailing a first version of its deployment requirements, as input for the integration and testing activities in WP3.
- Section 5 gives a more detailed overview of the VITAL-5G sub-components belonging to the VITAL-5G Portal Backend, i.e., the Intent-Based interface, the (T&L) Service LCM, the (T&L) Service Monitoring, the (T&L) Service Testing, the Results Analytics and the AI-based Performance Diagnostics.
- Section 6 gives details on the VITAL-5G sub-components belonging to the VITAL-5G Management Backend, i.e., the Access Control component, the Multi-site Inventory and the Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory.
- Section 7 provides the first description and the initial architecture for the Open Online Repository, as well as presenting each of its components.
- Section 8 presents the VITAL-5G Web GUI to be used to interact with the VITAL-5G Platform and the Open Online Repository.
- Finally, Section 9 concludes this document.

This work has been developed in parallel with D1.2 [1], ensuring its alignment with the work performed in that task to define the VITAL-5G Platform functional requirements analysis & specifications. Since D1.2 [1] provides the description of functionalities and requirements of the VITAL-5G Platform components, it is therefore highly recommended to read D1.2 [1] before D2.1.

Future WP2 deliverables, i.e., D2.2, D2.3 and D2.4 will iterate through the implementation and deployment details of the VITAL-5G Network Applications and the software components that form the VITAL-5G Platform and the Open Online Repository.

2 Network Applications Concepts and Modeling

The Network Application concept is one of the key pillars of VITAL-5G since we envision Network Applications as the building blocks of the T&L service chains on top of 5G-enabled infrastructures. As described in D1.2 [1], Network Applications extend the orchestration-oriented models proposed by European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI) Network Function Virtualization (NFV) (e.g., Virtual Network Function Descriptors (VNFDs), Network Service Descriptors (NSDs)), including information to better describe the service level information, and to simplify the composition of Network Applications into complex service chains. Furthermore, in order to realize the seamless integration of the vertical application into a 5G enabled infrastructure, Network Applications extend the current standards to enable the definition of their requirements in terms of 5G slices and 5G Core services. In fact, the information models defined in ETSI for VNFDs and NSDs [3] are focused on the internal structure of network functions and network services, respectively, defining the Virtual Machines or the containers composing them, the virtual links, forwarding graphs and paths interconnecting these elements, the size and multiplicity of each element, as well as the internal and external connection points. These models are fully generalized and service-agnostic, without describing information related to application logic, service interfaces or requirements related to the external context. These gaps are filled by the Network Application modelling, through the declaration of protocols and languages used at the application's service interfaces, dependencies on hardware and devices, requirements on 5G mobile connectivity or 5G core network services, etc.

The communication path between the Network Applications and the end users can be either established directly over the 5G network, or indirectly by allowing Network Applications to interact with each other. Thus, during the design of the Network Application concept, we also envisioned the latter type of Network Applications that are not directly using 5G network, but instead provide a part of a 5G-enabled service functionality. These Network Applications leverage the 5G connectivity provisioned for the overall vertical service and depend on the real-time data that is collected by other Network Applications over 5G. Such a fluid and dynamic design of vertical service can foster more effectively the participation of 3rd party experimenters, which may bring in their Network Applications to complement or differentiate the functionality implemented by the Network Applications developed in the project to deliver more complex 5G-enabled services.

2.1 Network Application definition and characterization

As described before, a Network Application is the fundamental building block we use in VITAL-5G to build complex T&L services that exploit 5G communications.

In D1.2 [1] we established the information model of a Network Application package (graphically represented in Figure 1), identifying the required information elements to be provided to complement the information contained in the standard VNF Packages:

- **VNF package:** This category groups the software images and deployment related descriptors of the VNF and CNFs. These descriptors determine the required resources to run the Virtual Deployment Units (VDUs), the network connectivity requirements and images in terms of virtual links and the monitoring metrics to be collected to optimize the service performance.
- **Network Application blueprint:** The Network Application blueprint embraces the additional vertical service level information required to enable the construction of the T&L service chains. This includes:
 - Vertical service definition, categorization and internal functional blocks' structure
 - Vertical service mapping to interface and protocol specifications
 - Required 5G slice profile and service capabilities
 - Specification of the application and infrastructure metrics to be monitored to evaluate the Network Application performance
 - Vertical service mapping to software licenses

- Specification of compatible T&L hardware (i.e., sensors, IoT gateways, actuators, etc.)
- **Software documentation:** This category embraces the software documentation, including interface specifications and overall details of the software packages to aid the usage of the Network Application and the construction of the T&L service chains. The files in this category are mapped to the vertical service in the Network Application Metadata.
- **Software license specifications:** This category includes all the licensing specification files, which define the licensing terms for the different functional blocks of the vertical service (as specified in the Network Application Metadata).
- **TestCase:** Test specifications to enable automated testing and validation per Network Application.

Figure 1: High-level representation of a Network Application package

The reader should refer to D1.2 [1] for further details regarding the information contained in each category. The following sections detail the format and structure of the Network Application packages and the data model used for the files in each category.

2.2 Data Models of Network Application packages and T&L services

In order to ease the management and packaging, in VITAL-5G Network Application packages are realized through ZIP compressed files containing the information for the categories mentioned in the previous section. This approach allows to group information in order to be easily distributed and made available through the VITAL-5G open online repository. In Table 2 we summarize the data models used for the different categories.

Table 2: Network Application Package data model

Information element	Data model
VNF Package	In VITAL-5G we use ETSI GS NFV-SOL 004 [3] and NFV-SOL 006 [4] based VNF packages. Moreover, the VNF Packages used shall be compliant with OpenSource MANO [5] NFV Orchestrator (NFVO). This enables compatibility with the orchestration platforms available on the three VITAL-5G testbeds. This file can be provided either as a compressed file or using an URL reference.
Network Application Blueprint	The data model for the Network Application Blueprint uses a JSON format using a specific structure as detailed in section 2.2.1.

Software Documentation	In VITAL-5G we will rely on the available formats and standards to provide the software documentation to ease the Network Application re-usage and composition. This includes, for example, support for OpenAPI specification for REST API, SQL schemas and plain text files describing the protocols and interfaces.
Software licenses specifications	These files provide the specific licensing details.
TestCase	These files document the procedures for testing and validating a Network Application. They use the format specified in D1.4 [6].

The internal structure of the Network Application package uses a specific organization in files and folders in order to ease the processing of the packages and the access to the information elements. The established structure is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Network Application Package structure

2.2.1 Network Application Blueprint data model

The Network Application blueprint provides the vertical service level information required in order to realize the VITAL-5G Network Application concept and at the same time acts as the entry point of the Network Application package, providing the mappings between the vertical service and the software documentation and software licenses. In terms of data model, the Network Application blueprint uses a JSON file following the structure depicted in Figure 3 and extended in Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 for specific information elements. The following tables describe the single attributes of the various information elements.

Figure 3: Network Application blueprint data model

The generic Endpoint definition is extended by the 5GEndpoint subclass, in order to include the additional information required for the particular type of external endpoints attached to the 5G network, i.e., interconnected to the data network on the N6 interface of an edge or core User Plane Function (UPF). As shown in Figure 4 this enables the specification of the required coverage area and specific mobile traffic parameters

related to the slice profile. The parameters of the Slice Profile, differentiated for eMBB and URLLC slices, are inspired by the network slice modelling defined in the 5G Network Resource Model (Stage 2 and 3) from 3GPP [7].

Figure 4: 5GEndpoint data model

The VITAL-5G platform will support the automated collection of certain types of infrastructural metrics, namely metrics related to the user plane network (associated to Network Application endpoints connected to the 5G network), and compute resource utilization related parameters (associated to the deployment units running the Network Application atomic components). In Figure 5 we list the supported infrastructure metric types.

Figure 5: InfrastructureMetric data model

Finally, the interface service specifications of the Network Application Blueprint may refer to files included in the Network Application package to support the interface specification, as represented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: InterfaceServiceSpec data model

The following 18 tables further elaborate on the data types and multiplicity of the parameters for each one of the information elements specified in the previous diagrams.

Table 3: Network Application Blueprint element data model

Network Application Blueprint			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
NetworkApplicationBlueprintId	String	1	An identifier for the Network Application package
specLevel	ENUM (VERTICAL_SPECIFIC, VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC)	1	Determines if the Network Application is vertical specific or vertical agnostic
configurableParameters	Map<String, String>	0..1	A Map containing the id of a configuration parameter and a name as the value. These parameters can be filled in by the Experimenter at the provisioning time to customize the service instance.
Description	String	0..1	A human readable description of the Network Application package
name	String	1	The Network Application package name
version	String	1	The version of the Network Application package specification
accessLevel	ENUM (PRIVATE, RESTRICTED, PUBLIC)	1	Determines how this Network Application is shared with other stakeholders. Private Network Applications are only visible to the account of the Network Application developer, RESTRICTED shall only be available to other certain accounts, while PUBLIC ones are available for everyone to see.
useCase	String	1	The use case to which this Network Application is mapped. Used to group monitoring information and reports.
testbed	ENUM (ANTWERP, DANUBE, ATHENS)	1	The targeted VITAL-5G testbed.
applicationMetrics	ApplicationMetric	0..N	The application metrics generated by the Network Application functions.
infrastructureMetrics	InfrastructureMetric	0..N	The infrastructure metrics to be monitoring for the Network Application optimized orchestration.
atomicComponents	Component	1..N	The internal functional blocks composing the Network Application.
endpoints	Endpoint	1..N	Endpoints represent the interfaces between the different functional blocks or towards external entities.

connectivityServices	ConnectivityService	0..N	The connectivity service models a logical link which establish the logical relationships between the components of the Network Application (including the attached endpoints).
softwareLicenses	SoftwareLicense	1..N	The license terms and attached file.
required5GCoreServices	5GServiceSpec	0..N	Determines the 5G core services that the Network Application may use.
requiredEquipments	RequiredEquipment	0..N	The IoT/T&L devices used by the Network Application to work.
providedInterfaceSpec	InterfaceServiceSpec	1..N	The interfaces provided by the Network Application.
requiredInterfaceSpec	InterfaceServiceSpec	0..N	The interfaces required from other Network Applications (i.e., the consumed interfaces).
vnfPackagePath	String	1	The internal pointer where the VNF package is available.
testCases	TestCaseSpec	0..N	The test case specifications associated with this Network Application.

Table 4: Component element data model

Component			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
componentId	String	1	An identifier for the component.
name	String	1	A human readable name for the component.
placement	ENUM (EDGE, CORE, FAR_EDGE)	1	The intended placement for the component with respect to the 5G network.
endpointIds	String []	1..N	The ids of the endpoints of the Network Application associated with this component.
minInstances	Int	1	The minimum number of instances of this component which will be used for the deployment. If “0” the component is not mandatory.
maxInstances	int	1	The maximum number of instances of this component which will be used for the deployment.

Table 5: InfrastructureMetric element data model

InfrastructureMetric			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
metricID	String	1	An identifier for the Infrastructure

			Metric.
name	String	1	The infrastructure metric name.
type	ENUM (USER_DATA_RATE_DOWNLINK, USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK, LATENCY_USERPLANE, LATENCY_CONTROLPLANE, LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT, RELIABILITY, AVAILABILITY, CPU_USAGE, MEMORY_USAGE, DISK_USAGE)	1	The type of infrastructure metric to be collected.
metricCollectionType	String	1	The type of collection type, e.g., gauge, cumulative or delta.
unit	String	1	The unit of the metric.
interval	String	1	The periodicity for the metric collection.
metricGraphType	String	1	The type of graph to be generated to report this metric.

Table 6: ApplicationMetric element data model

ApplicationMetric			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
metricID	String	1	An identifier for the Application Metric
name	String	1	The application metric name.
topic	String	1	The topic on which the monitoring information will be pushed within the VITAL-5G monitoring system.
metricCollectionType	String	1	The type of collection type, e.g., gauge, cumulative or delta.
unit	String	1	The unit of the metric.
interval	String	1	The periodicity for the metric collection.
metricGraphType	String	1	The type of graph to be generated to report this metric (e.g., Line graph, bar graph, etc.)

Table 7: RequiredEquipment element data model

RequiredEquipment			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
requiredEquipmentId	String	1	An identifier for the equipment required by the Network Application.
location	String	1	A geographical identifier of the place where the equipment should be placed.
type	Enum (IOT_GW, SENSOR, ACTUATOR, OTHER)	1	The type of IoT hardware device.
protocol	String	0..1	A description of the protocol to be used to interface with the hardware device.
mandatory	Boolean	1	Determines if the presence of the device is strictly required or not.
accessLevel	Enum (READ, WRITE, READ_WRITE)	1	The type of access required to the hardware device.

Table 8: ConnectivityService element data model

ConnectivityService			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
connectivityServiceId	String	1	The identifier of the connectivity service.
name	String	1	Name of the logical link.
external	Boolean	1	Determines if the logical link should be mapped to an external logical link in the NFVO.
endPointIds	String []	1..N	The ids of the endpoints attached to this connectivity service.

Table 9: SoftwareLicense element data model

SoftwareLicense			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
softwareLicenseId	String	1	Identifier of the license
version	String	1	The version of the licensing terms
componentIds	String []	0..N	The ids of the Network Application components associated to this license specification.
openLicense	Boolean	1	Determines if this is an open source based license or not.
type	ENUM (APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY,	1	Determines the general licensing terms of the license. We refer to D1.2 (1) for

	TIME_BASED, INSTANCE_BASED, FLAT)		further details.
validationURL	String	0..1	An external URL to be used while validating the license during the service instantiation (if required).
licenseFile	String	0..1	A reference to a file of the Network Application package defining the license specification.

Table 10: 5GServiceSpec element data model

5GServiceSpec			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
fiveGServiceSpecId	String	1	Identifier of the 5G service spec.
version	String	1	The version of the 5G service spec.
mandatory	Boolean	1	Determines if this 5G Core service is strictly required or not.
function	ENUM (NWDAF, LCS)	1	The 5G core service name (i.e., network data analytics or location service)

Table 11: InterfaceServiceSpec element data model

InterfaceServiceSpec			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
interfaceServiceSpecId	String	1	Identifier of the interface service spec.
version	String	1	The version of the interface service spec.
endPoint	String	1..N	The ids of the endpoints that provide or consume to this service interface.
name	String	1	The service interface name.
role	ENUM (PROVIDER, CONSUMER)	1	The role of the Network Application in the service interface.
commType	ENUM (REQUEST_RESPONSE, SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY)	1	The type of communication.
dataFormat	ENUM (JSON, YAML, PLAIN_TEXT, XML, OTHER)	1	The format used for the messages exchanged on this service interface.
protocol	ENUM (HTTP, MQTT, SQL, OTHER)	1	The application protocol used in the service interface.
attachedSpecifications	AttachedInterfaceSpec	0..N	List of attached file specifications.

Table 12: AttachedInterfaceSpec element data model

AttachedInterfaceSpec			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
file	String	1	Reference to a file of the Network Application package providing the interface documentation.
type	Enum (OPEN_API, SQL_SCHEMA, JSON_SCHEMA, DOCUMENTATION)	1	The type of documentation file.

Table 13: Endpoint element data model

Endpoint			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
Id	String	1	An identifier of the endpoint.
type	Enum (EXTERNAL, INTERNAL)	1	Determines if the endpoint is to be accessed externally or is just for internal communication between the components of the Network Application.
management	Boolean	1	If the endpoint is to be used for management purposes.
mobileConnection	Boolean	1	If the endpoint must be interconnected to the 5G network.
5GEndpoint			
coverageArea	String	1	Geographical id of the area to be covered by the 5G connectivity.
radioAccessTechnology	Enum (FIVE_G_NSA, FIVE_G_SA, NB_IoT, LTE_M)	1	The radio access technology to be used with this Network Application.
sliceProfile	SliceProfile	1..N	The slice profile specification.

Table 14: SliceProfile data element model

SliceProfile			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
type	ENUM (EMBB, URLLC, MMTc)	1	The type of slice profile.
profileParams	EMBBSliceServiceProfileParams/ URLLCSliceServiceProfileParams	1	The slice profile params specification (inspired by 3GPP standards (7))

Table 15: EMBBSliceServiceProfileParams data element model

EMBBSliceServiceProfileParams			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
expDataRateDL	int	0..1	The required downlink data rate in Mbps.
expDataRateUL	int	0..1	The required uplink data rate in Mbps.
areaTrafficCapDL	int	0..1	The required area capacity downlink data rate in Mbps/m2.
areaTrafficCapUL	int	0..1	The required area capacity uplink data rate in Mbps/m2.
userDensity	Int	0..1	The required user density in users/m2.
uESpeed	Int	0..1	The average user equipment speed in m/s.

Table 16: URLLCSliceServiceProfileParams data element model

URLLCSliceServiceProfileParams			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
latency	int	0..1	The required maximum latency in ms.
Jitter	int	0..1	The maximum supported jitter in ms.
availability	Float	0..1	The required minimum availability in uptime percentage.
expDataRate	int	0..1	The required data rate in Mbps.
mobility	ENUM (STATIONARY, NOMADIC, RESTRICTED_MOBILITY, FULL_MOBILITY)	0..1	The mobility level of the users in the coverage area.
userDensity	Int	0..1	The required user density in users/m2.

Table 17: TestCaseSpec data element model

TestCaseSpec			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
testCaseSpecId	String	1	The ID of the test case file.
name	String	0..1	Human readable name of the test case.
testCasePath	String	1	Test script file path in the Network Application package.

2.2.2 Vertical Service Blueprint data model

In order to compose Network Applications into T&L vertical services, in VITAL-5G we adopt the service-driven model of the Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB), relying on a similar approach already applied in other EU projects like 5G TRANSFORMER [8] and 5G EVE [2] to define a template that allows verticals to easily define the characteristics and requirements of their own services. In particular, this blueprint provides a representation of how various Network Applications can be combined together to deliver a more complex service, binding the different Network Applications' endpoints and connectivity services together, specifying the logical service sequence and providing mappings to the NFV Network Service Descriptors (NFV-NSDs). The specific data model for the VSB is depicted in Figure 7. Most of the data elements used in the VSB use the same definition described in the previous section.

Figure 7: Vertical Service Blueprint data model

The following 3 tables provide further details for the data elements which are specific for the Vertical Service Blueprint.

Table 18: VerticalServiceBlueprint data element model

VerticalServiceBlueprint			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
verticalServiceBlueprintId	String	1	An identifier for the VSB.
configurableParameters	Map<String, String>	0..1 (multiple values within the map)	A Map containing the id of a configuration parameter and a name as the value. These parameters can be filled in by the Experimenter at the provisioning time to customize the service instance.
serviceParameters	Map<String, String>	1 (multiple values)	A Map containing the id of a service parameter and a name as the value.

		within the map)	These parameters can be filled in by the Experimenter at the provisioning time to determine the amount of resources required by the vertical applications, in terms of NFV-NS deployment flavour and instantiation level.
description	String	0..1	A human readable description of the VSB.
name	String	1	The VSB name.
version	String	1	The version of the VSB.
accessLevel	ENUM (PRIVATE, RESTRICTED, PUBLIC)	1	Determines how this VSB is shared with other stakeholders. PRIVATE shall be visible only to the account that onboarded the VSB, RESTRICTED shall only be available to accounts related to the same use case, while PUBLIC ones are available for everyone to see.
useCase	String	1	The use case to which this VSB is mapped. Used to group monitoring information and reports, as well as regulate the VSB access in case of restricted VSB.
testbed	ENUM (ANTWERP, DANUBE, ATHENS)	1	The target VITAL-5G testbed.
applicationMetrics	ApplicationMetric	0..N	The application metrics exposed by the vertical service.
infrastructureMetrics	InfrastructureMetric	0..N	The infrastructure metrics to be used by the vertical service for optimized orchestration or monitoring purposes.
atomicComponents	ServiceComponent	1..N	The functional blocks of the Vertical Service. This are mapped to the Network Applications composing the service.
endpoints	ServiceEndpoint	1..N	Service Endpoints represent the interfaces exposed by the Vertical Service. They are mapped to the external endpoints of the Network Applications.
connectivityServices	ConnectivityService	0..N	The connectivity service models logical links which establish the logical relationships between the components of the vertical service (including the endpoints attached).
Required5GcoreServices	5GserviceSpec	0..N	Determines the 5G core services to be used (if present, overrides the ones declared in the single Network Applications).

requiredEquipments	RequiredEquipments	0..N	The required devices used by the service to work. It is a subset of the required equipment dependencies of the linked Network Applications and, if present, overrides the ones declared in the single Network Applications.
nsdPath	String	1	The internal pointer where the NSD is available.

The VSB also uses the concept of components representing the functional blocks of the service as in the Network Application Blueprint. The data model of the element in this case is extended to allow to specify the Network Application blueprint associated with the component, as detailed in Table 19.

Table 19: ServiceComponent data element model

ServiceComponent			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
serviceComponentId	String	1	An identifier for the component.
NetworkApplicationBlueprintId	String	1	The id of the linked Network Application blueprint.
serviceEndpointIds	String	1..N	The ids of the service endpoints associated with this component.
minInstances	Int	1	The minimum number of instances of this component which will be used for the deployment. If "0", the related Network Application is not mandatory in the service.
maxInstances	int	1	The maximum number of instances of this component which will be used for the deployment.

Similarly, the service endpoints allow to map to the vertical service endpoints to the endpoints of the Network Applications, as detailed in Table 20. Moreover, this definition allows to override the slice profile parameters associated to the Network Application to customize the 5G slice profile with values better fitted to the specific service.

Table 20: ServiceEndpoint data element model

ServiceEndpoint			
Attribute	Type	Multiplicity	Description
serviceEndpointId	String	1	An identifier for the service endpoint.
NetworkApplicationBlueprintId	String	1	The id of the linked Network Application blueprint.
endpointId	String	1	The id of the endpoint within the linked Network Application defined by the Network ApplicationBlueprintId.

sliceProfile	SliceProfile	0..N	The slice profiles to be associated with this service endpoint.
--------------	--------------	------	---

3 VITAL-5G Network Applications

In this section we further detail the Network Applications and their blueprints. First, we group the Network Applications in their respective Use Cases and T&L Services in Section 3.1. Secondly in Section 3.2, we iterate over the Network Applications to describe their internal structure, including its overall description, graphical representation, development road map, and a formal description of their blueprints. In addition, in Table 22, Table 24, and Table 26, we also provide a tabular overview of Network Application details such as the access for the 3rd-party experimenters and the type of data that can be collected from a specific Network Application, as well as the justification on whether a particular Network Application is new (developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project), or reused from the other projects (subcomponents reused and updated to fit the specific purpose in the VITAL-5G project).

3.1 Network Applications mapping to Use cases and T&L Services

The selected Network Applications to be developed within VITAL-5G are a representative set of Network Applications that address specific industry challenges existing in the T&L sector. Although they are tailor-made for the needs of the VITAL-5G selected use cases (UC1, UC2 and UC3), their goal is to demonstrate how VITAL-5G can address such challenges and serve as an example for further 3rd party Network Application developers.

Since the VITAL-5G Network Applications focus on their respective UCs, they are organized and grouped around them, and their corresponding T&L Services (UC1 Table 21, UC2 Table 23, and UC3 Table 25). Additionally, there are few Network Applications for an additional UC independent vertical service that are discussed as well (Table 27).

3.1.1 Assisted Vessel Transport

The UC1 applies 5G technology to a smart port context, and it will be performed using a vessel provided by Seafar at the Port of Antwerp. The main goal of UC1 is to showcase the automation of vessel-based logistics transport leveraging the 5G communications technology. For two types of vertical services that are designed in the scope of UC1 (Table 21), and described below, 5G connectivity is used for i) collecting high-bandwidth camera feeds, and real-time sensor data, from the vessels to the control center, and ii) real-time steering commands to the remote vessels.

Table 21: UC1 related Network Applications mapped to the two corresponding T&L services

Use Case 1		
Assisted Vessel Transport		
Vessel Navigation Assistance a. As part of this Network Application, IMEC will provide navigable waypoints (predicted path) to Seafar and ship captain b. The maneuvering of the vessel will be carried out by Seafar upon the acceptance of the predicted path	VS6	Assisted vessel navigation
	VS7	Navigation speed optimizer

Remote Vessel Monitoring	VS5	Monitoring dashboard
	VS8	Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II
	VA5	Real time digital twin

Vessel Navigation Assistance

This service provides the navigable path based on the VA5 and VS8, the path is shared with Seafar and vessel captain, who may accept it to further maneuver the vessel autonomously. It will be demonstrated in the full trial phase of the UC1 where the vessel (the Tercofin II) navigation will be shown. This service has the VS6 Network Application- developed by IMEC- for Assisted vessel navigation as its core Network Application. However, it also includes other Network Applications that VS6 depends on. VS5 – developed by Seafar - is required to assist the captain to monitor the vessel data. VS7 – developed by Digitrans - is used to calculate the optimal vessel speed in order to avoid wasting fuel and unnecessary waiting times before mooring. VS8 – developed by IMEC - is used to interface with the vessel and export public data. Finally, the VA5 – developed by IMEC - the Real time digital twin, a key component for the real-time assistance of the vessel for dealing with the live environment of the port (e.g., detecting obstacles).

Remote vessel monitoring

This service is demonstrated in the second phase of the UC1 where the vessels navigate into a narrower channel, heading to the docks. In the complex and busy area where there are safety risks, the captain onboard will take control of the vessel.

VS5 is used by the captain to assist him/her in navigating the vessel, as VS5 is the interface between the captain and the other Network Applications.

VS5 will visualize sensor data and nearby objects (coming from VA5). VS7 is used to provide information about the optimal speed to the captain, as mentioned before the output of VS7 will go to VS5 and the input to VS7 will come from 3rd-party services (e.g., Ports) and VS5 (e.g., Destination location). VS8 is used to export the public data. Finally, VA5 continues to assist and provide feedback to the captain, as redundant warnings in case of unexpected events.

Table 22: Detailed overview of Network Applications from the Assisted Vessel transport use case.

Network Application	Justification (New/Reused)	Access for the 3 rd -party experimenters (PRIVATE, PUBLIC, RESTRICTED)	Type of access for the 3 rd -party experimenters
Assisted vessel navigation (VS6)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	RESTRICTED	Access to global route map (output of global planning); Access to planned waypoints (output of the Network Application).

Navigation speed optimizer (VS7)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	PUBLIC	Open Source
Monitoring dashboard (VS5)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	RESTRICTED	Access to the python code and JavaScript for the front end
Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II (VS8)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	RESTRICTED	Access to GNSS data
Real time digital twin (VA5)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	RESTRICTED	Access to radar and/or LiDAR raw data (from sensors); Access to obstacle map (output of the Network Application).

3.1.2 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras

The UC2 leverages 5G technology to provide safer operation in the port, and to bring more security to navigation of ships in Galati port, with the help from assisted operation/navigation which uses IoT sensing system and video cameras installed in Galati port and on ships and cargos. Table 23 presents three types of vertical services that are in the scope of UC2, as well the corresponding Network Applications.

Table 23: UC2 related Network Applications mapped to the three corresponding T&L services

Use Case 2		
5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras		
Data-enabled assisted navigation	VA6	Data Stream Organization
	VS9	Onboard data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessels
Accurate electronic navigation maps creation	VA2	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing
Predictive maintenance and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship safety purposes	VA3	Remote inspection & risk assessment
	VS9	Onboard data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel

Data-enabled assisted navigation

The service uses the IoT sensing system and video cameras installed in Galati port and on the NAVROM vessel. It uses VS9 for specific collection of data from the NAVROM vessel. VA6 is used to categorize the data stream and allocate the relevant slice (URLLC or mMTC) according to the data that is sent from the vessel as well as provide interfaces for warning issuing and event classification. Each event will be rapidly, distinctly and granularly classified into dangerous/non-dangerous as well as the type of dangerous event. Warnings will be immediately issued leading to improved reaction time from the vessel crew.

Accurate electronic navigation maps creation

The service is based on estimating the correct safe distance for a ship. By using distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing offered by VA2, velocity, heading, water, wind speed data are fused with GNSS data leading to an increase in the accuracy of electronic navigation maps.

Predictive maintenance and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship safety purposes

The service uses VS9 On board data collection & interfacing for vessels for obtaining on-board diagnosis and monitoring data. The data is then used by VA3 for remote inspection and risk assessment, thereby limiting the impact of the human factor in risk assessment and taking potentially wrong decisions.

Table 24: Detailed overview of Network Applications from the 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras use case

Network Application	Justification (New/Reused)	Access for the 3rd-party experimenters (PRIVATE, PUBLIC, RESTRICTED)	Type of access for the 3rd-party experimenters
Data stream organization (VA6)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	PUBLIC	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
Onboard data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel (VS9)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	PUBLIC	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing (VA2)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project, based also on Intelligent proprietary work for ML components	RESTRICTED	Through the delivered UI and APIs to 3rd parties: access to ML results in Map view; allow for running various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training

			stage. UI not originally foreseen in D2.1.
Remote inspection & risk assessment (VA3)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project, based also on Incelligent proprietary work for ML components	RESTRICTED	Through the delivered UI and APIs to 3rd parties: access to ML results with relevant table/graph widgets; allow for running various ML-models, acquiring results as well as details on model type, hyperparameters and model performance during the training stage. UI not originally foreseen in D2.1.

3.1.3 Automation & remote operation of freight logistics

The UC3 applies 5G technology in an overall Logistics context, thereby optimizing warehousing operations through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs). Table 25 provides an overview of three vertical services that are defined for UC3, as well as the corresponding Network Applications for each of those services.

Table 25: UC3 related Network Applications mapped to the three corresponding T&L services

Use Case 3		
Automation & remote operation of freight logistics		
Autonomous pallet transport within the warehouse	VS1	Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning
	VA1	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation
Follow-me function for human-robot collaboration	VS2	Human-robot collaboration
	VA1	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation
Remote monitoring and control of AGVs	VA1	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation
	VS1	Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning

Autonomous pallet transport within the warehouse

This T&L service will aim to automate significant parts of the end-to-end process within a warehouse, as it covers key activities such as “from incoming products to storage”, “from picking to checking” and “from checking to shipping”. During these scenarios complex automation maneuvers will be demonstrated with the 5G enabled AGVs, including autonomous mobility within a complex warehouse environment and autonomous coordination

among AGVs and humans in the vicinity to avoid work-place accidents. These complex AGV functionalities will be enabled through the instantiation of a Cloud/Edge platform communicating with the AGVs, humans and warehouse sensors and cameras over 5G connectivity, collecting all relevant data and coordinating the AGVs' movement within the warehouse.

This T&L service will be realized by the combined operation of Network Applications "VS1: Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning" and "VA1: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation" which are described in the following sections.

Follow-me function for human-robot collaboration

In order to completely load a pallet with packages, a worker needs to go up and down the long storage corridors picking one order at a time and manually moving the picking pallet with their forklift. Therefore, the picking process is quite intensive. This T&L service will enable the AGV to follow the picking worker autonomously, saving them the effort and time required for the manual movement of the pallet. As the picking worker moves back and forth the storage corridor picking orders, the AGV will track them and follow them at a close but safe distance, based on onboard sensors and commands from a centralized server via 5G. The worker will be able to place every order they are picking directly onto the pallet of the following AGV, without worrying about moving the pallet. Once all the orders meant for this pallet are gathered and placed on the AGV by the worker, the AGV will autonomously navigate to the checking area, where it will deposit the pallet, so the items on it can be checked, before moving them to the shipping area. This will also allow the worker to continue right away to pick the next order. This T&L service will be realized by the combined operation of Network Applications "VS2: Human-robot collaboration" and "VA1: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation" which are described in the following sections.

Remote monitoring and control of AGVs

AGVs will share a constantly optimized and updated virtual map by monitoring the environment in real time. This map will assist in supervising the AGVs by providing their mark to the staff thus knowing their exact location. Remote control of the AGV will also be one of the included functionalities. Using the virtual map, workers will be able to set a specific location on the map directing the AGV to navigate to this location using an optimal route. This functionality will be available through an application or web interface running on the workers' smartphones so that they can monitor and interact with the AGV.

This T&L service will be realized by the combined operation of Network Applications "VS1: Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning" and "VA1: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation" which are described in the following sections.

3.1.4 Remote technical monitoring and predictive maintenance

The remote technical monitoring and predictive maintenance is an additional vertical service which is not specifically designed for a given testbed or use case, but it is applicable with minor customizations and configurations to different scenarios relevant for both warehouses and vessels. This service enables the remote collection and visualization of technical monitoring data, retrieved via 5G connectivity from various sensors and devices deployed on field, e.g., engines and onboard navigation systems in vessels or lifting equipment and environmental sensors in smart vessels/factories. On top of the collected data, the service integrates a custom processing logic enabled by AI/ML techniques for (early) faults detection and predictive maintenance, and configurable dashboards for visualizing alarms and notifications to help the technical operators in the management of the systems. This vertical service (see Table 27) is given by the composition of three Network Applications, i.e., (i) an IoT Management Platform (VA4) supporting multiple field bus protocols for a smooth integration with heterogeneous sensors and actuators, (ii) a service-specific AI/ML processing logic for automated fault detection and predictive maintenance (VS3), and (iii) a dashboard specialized for the

visualization of configurable technical data, alerts and alarms, as well as notifications for maintenance operations (VS4).

All the three Network Applications derive from the Symphony commercial product developed by Nextworks. Symphony is a service-oriented, generalized IoT platform capable of integrating thousands of interconnected devices in support of multiple vertical needs and applications. It embeds several functionalities, integrating various field bus protocols, data acquisition and actuators control, data storage and processing, rule-based engines, application logic and GUIs, into a unified fully decomposed and distributed IP-based platform. The domains of application of Symphony are quite heterogeneous, with specialized versions for smart building (Symphony Building Management System), smart factories (Symphony Factory Edition) and smart yachting.

The Symphony development roadmap for the near future is evolving towards fully virtualized and cloud-native models, with components installed in the cloud and features delivered following the as-a-Service paradigm. Moreover, some of the target environments where Symphony is usually deployed (smart factories and smart yachts) are currently starting to invest in 5G technologies, e.g., with 5G Stand-alone Non-Public Networks (SNPN) for big industrial factories and 5G antennas and routers starting to be installed in the bigger yachts. As consequence, it is becoming urgent to enhance, customize and tune the Symphony applications for 5G-enabled environments in order to develop a “5G-ready” product in line with the expected outcoming T&L market requests. The experimentation activities which will be performed using the VITAL-5G platform, starting from the Greek testbed to replicate the characteristics of a smart logistics warehouse environment, will help to evaluate the overall performance of multi-field bus data collection via 5G networks, to detect potential issues or incompatibilities and identify the optimal split and placement of the various components and functions in a virtualized infrastructure featuring 5G connectivity.

Table 26: Detailed overview of Network Applications from the Automation & remote operation of freight logistics use case

Network Application	Justification (New/Reused)	Access for the 3rd-party experimenters (PRIVATE, PUBLIC, RESTRICTED)	Type of access for the 3rd-party experimenters
Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning (VS1)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	RESTRICTED	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation (VA1)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	RESTRICTED	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed
Human-robot collaboration (VS2)	New Network Application, designed and developed in the scope of the VITAL-5G project	RESTRICTED	Access to sensor data; Access to video camera feed

Table 27: Network Applications for Remote Technical Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance

Cross-Use Case	
Remote Technical Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance	
VA4	IoT Management platform for (i) unified collection, storage and basic processing of IoT data and (ii) control of actuators, interacting with multiple types of field buses.
VS3	AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance.
VS4	Technical data visualization.

Table 28: Detailed overview of Cross-Use Case Network Applications

Network Application	Justification (New/Reused)	Access for the 3rd-party experimenters (PRIVATE, PUBLIC, RESTRICTED)	Type of access for the 3rd-party experimenters
IoT Management platform for (i) unified collection, storage and basic processing of IoT data and (ii) control of actuators, interacting with multiple types of field buses (VA4)	Network Application based on the re-packaging and adaptation of existing commercial solutions based on proprietary software	RESTRICTED	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3 rd parties after negotiation.
AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance (VS3)	Network Application based on the re-packaging and adaptation of existing commercial solutions based on proprietary software	RESTRICTED	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3 rd parties after negotiation.
Technical data visualization (VS4)	Network Application based on the re-packaging and adaptation of existing commercial solutions based on proprietary software	RESTRICTED	Usage of this Network Application may be granted to 3 rd parties after negotiation.

The graphical representation of the Remote Technical Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance vertical service is shown in Figure 8. The picture highlights the three Network Applications VA4, VS3 and VS4 (see the following section for the details of each of them) which interact together through their external endpoints. The interconnection of the IoT Management Platform Network Application (VA4) to the 5G network enables the collection of the sensors’ data from the field, making them available for the specialized processing performed at

the Fault Detection and Predictive Maintenance Network Application (VS3) and the configurable dashboards implemented by the Technical Data Visualization Network Application (VS4). During the experimentation activities and starting from this basic model, some variances of the deployment will be evaluated to identify the optimal solution and service tuning in a variety of scenarios (e.g., with users visualizing the data via 5G mobile connectivity, with functions of the IoT Management Platform partially running on field, etc.).

Figure 8: Vertical Service “Remote Technical Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance”

3.2 Definition of VITAL-5G Network Applications

In this section we describe in more detail both vertical-specific and vertical agnostic VITAL-5G Network Applications, and their internal structure. There are five vertical-agnostic (i.e., VA1-VA5), and nine vertical-specific (i.e., VS1-VS9) Network Applications.

3.2.1 VA1 Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & automation

This Network Application will be responsible for data ingestion and two-way communication with on-site equipment, decision support using rules and inference, monitoring and field assistance. VA1’s requirements will be fulfilled by functionalities organized in logical layers: the Network Application Communication, Network Application Core, Network Application Reasoning and Network Application Persistence layers (Figure 9).

- *The Network Application Communication layer* is responsible for enabling efficient and secure communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure. Raw data from on-site equipment and environmental sensors are collected in real time through the MQTT and REST API endpoints. Two-way communication is achieved by providing feedback and control commands to on-site equipment through the same protocols. The translation from raw data to domain-specific semantically

interpreted events and states is carried out using specific Sensor, AGV and Human-Machine Interface (HMI) APIs.

- *The Network Application Core layer* is the main application logic layer which combines data (events and states), and services to facilitate the two-way interaction with the monitored and controlled IoT devices. It couples together and synchronizes the whole Network Application infrastructure and services by means of a common event loop and state machine. It also facilitates the monitoring of the Network Application process through metrics collection and watchdogs for each critical component.
- *The Network Application Reasoning layer* contains the automation rules, transformation services, modeling and field assistance engines to provide Decision support. The transformations include filtering, consolidation, enrichment, aggregation, and supplementary operations regarding quality assurance. The transformed data are fed into the reasoning engines with the appropriate information for decision support. The reasoning engines include a Rule-based automation engine, a model-based Inference engine, and field assistance services such as online state estimation.
- *The Network Application Persistence layer* provides persistence and caching services to all other Network Application components. Relational databases, Object and File storage as well as time-series databases will be deployed to support the appropriate data model for different applications. Data caching services may also be deployed to support the efficient movement of data through the Network Application services.

Figure 9: VA1 Network Application: Distribution Sensor ingestion and automation

Figure 10 demonstrates the architecture of the VA1 Network Application in terms of the defined Blueprint.

Figure 10: Network architecture of VA1

The core controller platform handles the secure communication and interaction with the on-field systems (AGVs and other sensors) through a Virtual Network Gateway and Local IoT controller component. The 5G connectivity is used for the interaction between the Virtual Network Gateway and the other Network Application components.

The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

3.2.2 VA2 Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & post-processing

While VA2 shares similar functionalities with VA1, i.e., fusion of data, they differ in terms of the different ML-based mechanisms employed and the post-processing capabilities offered. More specifically, VA2 will support data ingestion, fusion and post-processing functionality from sensor data ingested from other Network Applications. It will output cloud-based decisions from resulting analytics that can be exploited for issuing warnings, notifications, reporting. Existing AI / Data analytics tools and inspection application are used as starting point, and they are to be enhanced with additional fusion, and analytics functionality, thereby supporting Vertical Specific Network Applications.

Figure 11 provides a high-level description of VA2 Network Application workflow regarding sensor data ingestion, fusion, and post processing. It is based on proprietary software modules for big data acquisition, ML modelling and de-facto standard, open-source technologies. More specifically VA2 Network Application is responsible for the following:

- Ingestion of data from other Network Application databases for the information that will allow for the deployment of ML models within the VA2 (e.g., time series predictions/ trajectory analytics), but also to be used by other Applications (for e.g., predictive maintenance/ risk assessment and so on).
- Transformation of datasets by means of both creating a fused (spatio-temporally correlated) data schema with basic data cleaning imputation functionalities.
- Data persistence for the data to be further utilized by other Network Applications or for further post-processing by the VA2 Network Application.

- d. Post processing of information, starting from simple functionalities like filtering, aggregating and ranging to applying selected ML models to allow for advanced analytics.
- e. Appropriate interfaces (APIs) for other VITAL-5G internal components, Network Applications and 3rd parties to utilize the enhanced information produced and stored.

Figure 11: VA2 Network Application: Workflow

Based on the above, the components comprising the VA2 Network Application are:

- **Data Collection:** This component is responsible for the collection of data through the southbound interfacing with other Network Applications databases, but can be expanded to collect data from external sources if necessary.
- **Data Fusion:** This component offers a number of capabilities depending on the needs presented. It performs the logical transformation of data to be further utilized by other VITAL-5G components or Network Applications. In more detail, it supports the basic imputation of missing values and allows for the time-space correlation of the received data for the logical fusion of data. Following these, the transformed/fused data are then sent to the ML module for post-processing (whether in the phase of model training or for the application of the ML-based transformation).

ML module: It is comprised of the Unsupervised and Supervised Modelling submodules, the Autotune Engine and the ML Registry. It incorporates mechanisms that ensure the optimal ML model approaches -supervised or unsupervised- will be used for advanced analytics depending on the Network Application and the testcase. In more detail, the Autotune Engine ensures the optimal hyper-parameter tuning for multiple modelling approaches and the best are stored in the ML registry. The results of these approaches can then be stored in a persistence layer. This component is also part of the VA3, however in VA2 the focus is in the application of supervised approaches and specifically time-series forecasting/prediction algorithms for selected variables, and also the prediction of trajectories. Depending on the complexity and availability of the data, we propose two types of forecasting models, namely SARIMAX, Prophet, but it can be easily extended to include more model implementations of the same type (including any data pre-processing needed as model input). Along with the ML-related functionalities, there are also backend subcomponents that are responsible for exposing data through

the appropriate APIs to the dashboard, other backend subcomponents, and 3rd party Network Applications.

- Data Persistence:** This component refers to a distributed data lake allowing for storage of both structured and unstructured data. It is where the raw data/KPIs as well as their transformations (e.g., imputed datasets, fused data) and the ML modelling results are persisted.

Figure 12 presents the aforementioned components and their external endpoints (all other endpoints are internal).

Figure 12: VA2 Network Application blueprint: Components & external endpoints

The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in VA1 blueprint: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation.

3.2.3 VA3 Predictive Maintenance

Figure 13: VA3 Network Application: Workflow

Figure 13 presents a high-level workflow for the VA3 Network Application for ML-based predictive maintenance. The VA3 Network Application may utilize the data ingested and exposed by other Network Applications, and specifically for UC2. It includes Incelligent’s proprietary software modules that perform supervised and unsupervised modelling techniques to achieve functions like automated labelling/outlier detection, trace back analysis, outlier predictions, that allow for graphical representations. This data can be used by other Apps for decision making in the near-future, therefore providing advanced diagnostics. This is done using the exposed information acquired through APIs for dashboards and other Network Applications. Also, the results of these techniques may be used for monitoring purposes. The aforementioned modules will be enhanced in terms of ML-modelling as well as adjusted to fit the specific needs of the T&L site and the type of information to be employed for the decision making. More specifically, it is expected to employ outlier detection mechanisms, specifically candidate modelling approaches are the unsupervised clustering methods of Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) [9] and/or Ordering Points To Identify the Clustering Structure (OPTICS) [10], as well as One-Class Support Vector Machine (SVM) [11], based on the Scikit-learn library¹.

Based on the above, the main components of VA3 are presented in Figure 14. To sum up, the incoming data -in this case engine sensor data- are exposed by another VA database are fed to the ML module that is responsible for the model development with respect to the predictive maintenance functionality. The ML module’s main functionalities are described also in the previous section. In short, through the automated model usage and calibration of multiple ML models by the Autotune Engine, the extraction of meaningful results is achieved. The models are trained and applied by the Unsupervised and Supervised Modelling subcomponents and saved in the

¹ Scikit-learn library, <https://scikit-learn.org/>

ML registry. Lastly, the results are then sent to the Data Persistence entity but are also exposed to other components/Network Applications and dashboards through the appropriate interfaces.

Figure 14: VA3 Network Application blueprint: Components & external endpoints

The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

3.2.4 VA4 IoT Management platform

The IoT Management Platform developed by NXW is a Network Application for the collection of technical monitoring data (e.g., environmental data, engines operational data, technical systems operational data) from heterogeneous systems available in the building (for warehouse) or on-board (for vessel). Due to its capability to retrieve data from different types of data sources, it can be considered as a Vertical-Agnostic Network Application and it can be easily customized to be adopted in various use cases and deployed in different testbeds. The first implementation of this Network Application for VITAL-5G will target the warehouse environment and it will be deployed in the Greek testbed.

The Network Application implementation is based on the proprietary Symphony product from NXW and the access to its functionalities will be limited to the VITAL-5G partners participating in the use case. Further potential usage from 3rd parties will be discussed on a per-partner basis.

The IoT Management Platform handles the interaction with various on-field systems through an “IoT Supervisor” that implements a Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL) integrating a number of plugins for specific protocols and information models (e.g., MQTT², Modbus³, etc.). The heterogeneous types of data collected from the field are unified in terms of information model and distributed to the upper layer functions of the Symphony platform in charge of storage, post-processing and visualization.

Depending on the target deployment environment, the IoT supervisor can be either installed in one or more instances as a physical component directly on the field and here interconnected to sensors and IoT gateways or instantiated as a virtual component in the computing infrastructure available in the testbed. The rest of the platform elements are designed to be deployed as virtual components in the edge or cloud computing infrastructure. In the former case the 5G connectivity is used for the interaction between the IoT supervisor and the other IoT Management platform components, while in the latter case the 5G connectivity can be used for the interaction between IoT supervisor and devices/IoT gateways on field. The selection of the particular deployment may be restricted by the capabilities of IoT devices and gateways (i.e., lack of native support of 5G connection) or it can be driven by performance and cost evaluations (e.g., number of required IoT supervisors, scalability of sensors’ amount, etc.). The experimental validation in a configurable 5G-enabled testbed will allow to evaluate and compare various deployment options, to obtain useful guidelines for the installation of the system in different types of real operational environments.

Figure 15 represents the high-level functional architecture of the IoT Management Platform Network Application. The various data are collected from field by the IoT Supervisor, properly unified and associated with meaningful metadata. Then, they are published on a message broker based on the MQTT protocol (“Message broker” component), which is instantiated in the network edge. The data on the broker are consumed by two other components, in particular the “Datastore and Dashboard” and the “IoT Event/Alarm Manager”. The “Datastore and Dashboard” is used to store the data on a timeseries database, so that can be accessed by further external application elements (e.g., to process historical data for ML model training), and provide basic visualization features. The “IoT Event/Alarm Manager” is used to recognize configurable patterns in the data exchanged on the broker and trigger pre-configured events or alarms, e.g., through notifications to the user or automated actions on actuators available on field. The actions on the actuators are mediated through the on-field IoT supervisor.

The graphical representation of the Network Application blueprints for the two deployment models mentioned above (IoT supervisor on-field or as virtual element at the network edge) are reported in Figure 16 and Figure 17, respectively.

² MQTT: <https://mqtt.org/>

³ Modbus: https://ctlsys.com/support/the_modbus_register_data_model/

Figure 15: Functional architecture of IoT Management Platform Network Application

Figure 16: Representation of IoT Management Platform Network Application blueprint – version with IoT supervisor installed as physical hardware on field

The version with IoT supervisor installed as physical hardware on field (Figure 16) is based on a Network Application with three atomic components, where the Message Broker exposes an external endpoint for 5G connectivity. This endpoint is the one used by the 5G-enabled IoT supervisor to push the data collected from field and it is modelled with a service profile that would require an ultra-reliable service. Depending on the specific type

of data, processing, and potential automatic reactions, additional latency constraints may also be required. The other external endpoints are exposed by the Datastore & dashboard component, to enable access for the users of the application, and by the IoT event & alarm manager, in support of notifications towards other external Network Applications. A potential alternative to be further investigated may involve access to the Network Application dashboard via 5G connection for mobile users. As shown in the picture, the IoT supervisor together with the IoT devices acting as data sources are represented in the Network Application blueprint as hardware dependencies. In terms of interfaces, the external endpoint of the message broker acts as provider of an MQTT-based interface (subscribe/notify pattern) with messages in JSON data format. The IoT event and alarm manager’s external endpoint also exposes an MQTT-based interface, but in consumer mode, and a REST-based interface in provider mode for configuration issues. Finally, the external endpoint of the datastore and dashboard component exposes two different interfaces, both of them in provider mode. The former is a web-based graphical interface to access the dashboard, the other is a REST-based interface (request/response pattern) to query the datastore, with messages in JSON data format. In terms of software licenses, the Network Application is associated to a closed license with a proprietary validation mechanism. The Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

The alternative version of the IoT Management Platform with the IoT supervisor deployed as a Network Application virtual component (Figure 17) has a slightly different Network Application blueprint, with four atomic component and the 5G-enabled external endpoint exposed by the IoT supervisor. In this case, this endpoint would be associated to interfaces modelled according to the protocol and capabilities supported by the devices on field. The other difference is related to the hardware dependencies, which would refer directly to the IoT gateways and sensors installed on field.

Figure 17: Representation of IoT Management Platform Network Application blueprint – version with IoT supervisor deployed as Network Application components in the virtual computing infrastructure

3.2.5 VA5 Real time digital twin

The responsibility of this Network Application is to create a real-time digital twin that constructs a local copy of a situational awareness model. It makes use of all available sensor data to build a real-time model of the environment. This model can afterwards be sent to VS6 for vessel assistance, and VS5 for remote monitoring purposes.

VA5 is a vertical-agnostic Network Application because it is a generalized application that can be easily adopted for different services (e.g., to create a digital twin for autonomous vehicles, robots in warehouses). Furthermore, it is a publicly accessible Network Application, meaning everyone can re-use it to build a new vertical service. VA5 will be developed by IMEC, but it does rely on the sensors of SF for the Antwerp testbed. It will be deployed in the Antwerp testbed area.

To create a digital twin of the environment, on-board sensor data is required. This data can be divided in visual sensor data and positional data. The former is received directly from the vessel via a 5G interface, whereas the positional data comes from VS8. The working of this Network Application can be divided into three parts (as can be seen in Figure 18):

- 3D bounding box estimation
- late sensor fusion
- occupancy grid map creation

First of all, every visual sensor data will be processed separately by a state-of-the-art 3D bounding box estimation algorithm. This algorithm detects all obstacles in the environment (e.g., other vessels) and estimates their position. Next, those overlapping bounding box estimations will be fused together using a non-maximum suppression (NMS) algorithm. Here, one 3D bounding box will be extracted out of the numerous overlapping ones. Finally, we will perform an affine transformation to transform the 3D bounding boxes onto a 2D occupancy grid map. For this purpose, the data from VS8 (Latitude, Longitude) will be used.

Figure 18: VA5 component model (Real time digital twin)

URLLC is required to receive real-time visual sensor data such that the occupancy grid map can be updated. The Network Application architecture is visualized in Figure 19. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

Figure 19: VA5 Network Application architecture

3.2.6 VA6 Data stream organization

VA6 supports, for UC2, the targeted improvement in navigation dangerous events occurrences related issues. It can be illustrated in a hierarchical manner, using a layer-based approach, but also some cross-layer components. The communication between all these layers is enabled by a data bus that crosses all the different domains.

- Physical layer represents the actual data coming from sensors as well as video streams. This layer is made of all the different sensors, devices and client agents that are in charge of collecting and transmitting data to the Network Application. Due to the different nature of the sensors as well as the different UC sites, this layer is likely to be very heterogeneous in terms of technologies, networks, protocols. In order to standardize the process of context data integration VA6 will adhere to a common data model.
- Network Application middleware layer offers relevant enablers for each UC needs, from device integration to complex event processing. The main component of the middleware is the data ingestion and integration block, which links the physical layer with the output layer using a data bus.
- Network Application core layer is in charge of transforming plain data into knowledge to enrich the higher-level decision support services with intelligence.
- Network Application exploitation/output layer is on top of the core layer and fed by it through the Decision support mediator. The mediator provides data and content to enable the VA5 outputs for UC stakeholders.
- VITAL-5G applications (not in scope of Network Application definition) will build on the Network Application outputs to enable users to interact with the VITAL-5G platform.
- Security components will span all layers and facilitate the efficient and secure communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure.

VA6 will have as inputs sensor data in JSON payload sent in a Publish/subscribe paradigm as well as video stream in WebRTC format.

VA6 will output the categorization of data streams. This will enable the proper 5G Network slice to be used as well as support the Vertical Specific Services for being used in UC2, and not only: decision support, collision avoidance assisted navigation, diagnosis etc. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I. .

Figure 20: VA6 internal Network Application architecture.

3.2.7 VS1 Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning

Using the VS1 Network Application, AGVs will be able to detect objects or humans, avoid them and will share a virtual map which is constantly optimized and updated by monitoring the environment in real time. This map will also assist in supervising the AGVs by providing their mark to the staff, thus knowing their exact location. All available data will be processed by the AGV controller in real time aiming at the efficient use of drive, steering and on-the-spot path planning. LiDAR sensors provide information about the distance of the objects with high accuracy and in this way a fast reaction time is provided to ensure the avoidance of accidents. For each pallet, the AGV will use the barcode scanner to acquire information regarding the area each of them must be placed. Using the lift controller and the virtual map, the AGV will carry the pallets in a safe way by optimizing the route based on the live data coming from its sensors, considering the people around and any other obstacles. Using data analytics, historical data, and real time information the AGV will be able to optimize the storing and picking process. The functionalities can be differentiated according to where they are hosted. They will be running either locally on the AGV or in our cloud/edge platform as shown in the following table.

Table 29: Functionalities differentiation

Running locally on the AGV	Running on the cloud/edge platform
Obstacle Avoidance (LiDAR sensors)	Computational offloading (Object recognition)
On-the-spot path planning	AGV monitoring
	Logistics LCM service

A Logistics Lifecycle Management (LCM) service will be part of the VS1 Network Application to collect pending warehouse transport tasks and make them available to the core automation controller of Network Application VA1.

The following figure demonstrates the architecture of the VS1 Network Application in terms of the defined Blueprint. The Blueprint JSON file can be found at Annex I.

Figure 21: Representation of the AGV automation blueprint based on VS1 and VA1 combined operation

The VS1 Network Application interacts with the VA1 Network Application via the Network Application Internal Connectivity Service bus. The core controller platform handles the secure communication and interaction with the on-field systems (AGVs and other sensors) through a Virtual Network Gateway and Local IoT controller component. The 5G connectivity is used for the interaction between the Virtual Network Gateway and the other Network Application components.

3.2.8 VS2 Human-robot collaboration

This Network Application will enable the interaction between robots and human workers in the warehouse for joint task execution. A Human Machine Interface (HMI) will be developed to allow the workers to set tasks and intervene in the operations of the AGV. Predefined commands such as ‘pick incoming products’, ‘pick checked orders’ or ‘follow me’ will give the worker the opportunity to assign tasks to the AGV. At the ‘follow me’ function the AGV must confirm that the worker has the rights to execute this command. This can be accomplished in two ways: either by using the barcode/RFID scanner assuming the worker is wearing a vest with a printed barcode/RFID tag or by using the camera and face recognition. The AGV will be following the worker at a predefined distance and each time it will detect the worker’s movements (adjusting its own movements respectively, e.g., stop and wait for loading, continue following the worker). After the loading procedure is completed, the AGV can be instructed by the worker to transfer the cargo to a designated area in the warehouse. The following figure depicts the follow-me functionality as instantiated by the combined operation of VS2 and VA1, along with their respective modular architectures.

Figure 22 demonstrates the architecture of the VS2 Network Application in terms of the defined Blueprint. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

Figure 22: Representation of Human Robot collaboration using a combined VS2 and VA1 Network Application Blueprint

The VS2 Network Application interacts with the VA1 Network Application via the Network Application Internal Connectivity Service bus. The core controller platform handles the secure communication and interaction with the on-field systems (AGVs and other sensors) through a Virtual Network Gateway and Local IoT controller component. The 5G connectivity is used for the interaction between the Virtual Network Gateway and the other Network Application components.

3.2.9 VS3 AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance

The AI/ML-based Network Application for automated fault detection and predictive maintenance (VS3) developed by NXW provides additional functionalities to the IoT Management Platform (VA4) implementing specialized data processing algorithms for the detection of anomalous behaviors in the technical sensors and systems of the warehouse (or the vessel, depending on the target deployment). The alarms identified by the Network Application are published in the common datastore offered by the IoT Management Platform and they are further processed to predict failure trends for the various types of devices installed on field and build a more efficient and global maintenance plan that allows to reduce the outage time of the operational environment while limiting the total number of maintenance interventions and their related cost.

The VS3 Network Application is typically deployed in a vertical service that also includes the IoT Management Platform (VA4), since it consumes its interfaces to access the information available in its datastore, i.e., the technical monitoring data collected from field and the associated alerts and events. However, it may operate jointly with any other Network Application that exposes similar kinds of data through the same interface and following a common data model. Moreover, it should be noted that VA4 is a Vertical-Agnostic Network Application that can collect data from multiple field bus protocols and thus easy to apply to various use cases and testbeds. Instead, VS3 implements processing algorithms that must be designed and customized for specific types of technical sensors, systems and information. Consequently, it can be considered as a Vertical-Specific Network Application that must be developed according to the specific requirements and characteristics of the equipment installed in the target environment where it will operate. In particular, in VITAL-5G the implementation of this

Network Application will be customized for the warehouse environment and its IoT sensors available in the Greek testbed. As for VA4, the Network Application implementation will extend the proprietary Symphony product from NXW and the access to its functionalities will be limited to the VITAL-5G partners participating in the use case. Further potential usage from 3rd parties within the context of the project will be discussed on a per-partner basis, issuing the required licenses where needed.

Figure 23 provides the functional architecture of the Network Application, assuming it collects its input data from the datastore offered by the IoT Management Platform. These data include both the technical measurements collected from the field and the events/alarms produced by the IoT Events and Alarms Manager component of VA4 (e.g., on a simple threshold basis). They are exposed following a unified and protocol-independent information model which is common to the different kinds of sensors and devices installed on field. They constitute the input for the Anomaly Detector element, which automatically identifies potential abnormal values or anomalous trends in the processed time series. The detection is based on ML techniques (for example based on sequential Deep Neural Networks, but the selection of the specific techniques depends on the target analysis) using pre-trained data models that are onboarded in the application by the administrator of the Network Application. The usage of external and publicly available datasets will be adopted for the initial model building phase, while the historical data collected from field may be used to optimize the trained model at a later stage. The Fault Detector generates notifications for the detected faults, which are placed into the common datastore provided by the IoT Management Platform, reported to the technical operators through customizable alarm mechanisms and given as input to the Fault Predictor component. Here the faults data are used to build profiles related to degradation and lifetime of the various equipment, which are then elaborated by the Predictive Maintenance Planner component to schedule optimized maintenance interventions.

The internal VS3 software is organized in a single software component written in python that implements all the three functionalities mentioned above and exposes its services over a single virtual network interface. The Network Application is not supposed to interact directly with the 5G network, but it is expected to use the mediation of VA4 for the collection of IoT data from field. In this sense, the Network Application can use exactly the same network slice associated with VA4.

Figure 23: Functional architecture AI/ML-based fault detection & predictive maintenance Network Application

The related Network Application blueprint, shown in Figure 24, has a single atomic component with an external endpoint. The endpoint is not directly interconnected to the 5G network, but it is used to interact with the IoT Management Platform Network Application (represented with the grey box) that mediates the access to the field data. This endpoint is used to (i) interact with the datastore component for querying and storing data and (ii) to expose a number of service interfaces for management and configuration, fault notifications and retrieval, and queries for predictive maintenance scheduling.

Figure 24: Deployment of VS3 Network Application for AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance in a 5G-enabled environment

As consequence, the interfaces modelled in the Network Application blueprint and associated to its single endpoint include the following:

- a REST-based interface (request/response pattern with messages in JSON format) in consumer mode to access the VA4 datastore;
- a REST-based interface (request/response pattern with messages in JSON format) in provider mode to enable the configuration of the Network Application and the onboarding of new trained models;
- a REST-based interface (request/response pattern with messages in JSON format) in provider mode to enable queries of detected failures and suggested maintenance operations.

The Network Application license is a closed one with proprietary validation mechanisms handled at the application level. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

3.2.10 VS4 Technical Data Visualization

The Technical Data Visualization Network Application developed by NXW simplifies the day-by-day monitoring and operational activities of the technicians responsible for the management of technical areas, which can span from smart buildings and smart vessels, up to smart factories and smart cities. In fact, the Network Application provides a unified access to monitoring panels and dashboards showing all the data, alerts and alarms collected by the heterogeneous sensors and systems available on field and gathered or elaborated through the IoT Management Platform (VA4). Moreover, Technical Data Visualization can show additional technical metrics and KPIs potentially processed and computed by the other applications, like the VS3 “AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance”.

As for VS3, the Technical Data Visualization Network Application operates in combination with the IoT Management Platform (VA4), since it reads the data from the VA4 datastore using the REST interface exposed by that Network Application. Moreover, it can be used in a vertical service that combines the set of three Network Applications developed by NXW (VA4, VS3 and VS4) to provide the joint visualization of the raw data initially collected by IoT Management Platform combined with the output of the fault detection and predictive maintenance logic implemented in VS3. In VITAL-5G, the Technical Data Visualization Network Application is customized with dashboards specialized for the type of sensor data collected from the warehouse environment in the Greek testbed and, accordingly, it can be classified as a Vertical-Specific Network Application. All the test and experimental validation activities will be performed on the Greek testbed in combination with VA4. The internal software of the Network Application, however, is based on the widely used Grafana stack, an open-

source software that can operate with several data sources, data bases and monitoring platforms. As such, the Network Application can be easily re-used and adapted in the context of other services.

The Technical Data Visualization Network Application is part of the software suite of the proprietary Symphony product developed by NXW. When combined with the rest of the system, the access to its functionalities will be limited to the VITAL-5G partners participating in the use case. Further potential usage from 3rd parties within the context of the project will be discussed on a per-partner basis, issuing the required licenses where needed.

Figure 25 describes the functional architecture of the Technical Data Visualization Network Application, showing how it cooperates with VA4 and VS3 to provide a graphical visualization for their data and results. From a functional perspective, the Network Application includes visualization dashboards, with web pages to browse the various graphs, filter the data, zoom on particular ranges or information, etc. This interface allows the technical operators to visualize all the various data sets from a single and unified platform using a common web GUI. The dashboard configurator allows to re-configure dynamically the dashboards and it can be used, for example, to add a new metric or data source for the monitoring panel. The kind of configuration to be performed is application and environment specific and it is usually handled by the administrator of the system(s) to be monitored.

As mentioned previously, the visualization dashboards rely on the datastore functional block provided by the IoT Management Platform Network Application, to access the monitoring data produced by the IoT devices without any direct communication. In this sense, this Network Application does not impose any additional 5G communication constraints, and can therefore use the same 5G slice associated with VA4.

Figure 25: Functional architecture of Technical Data Visualization Network Application and its cooperation with VA4 and VS3

The Network Application blueprint is represented in Figure 26. As depicted in the figure, the Network Application is composed by a single atomic component and includes one external endpoint used to: (i) Query the IoT

monitoring information available on the datastore; (ii) provide the web GUI for the technical operator to visualize the information in the specialized dashboard and for the system administrator to configure new dashboards.

Figure 26: Deployment of VS3 Network Application for AI/ML-based automated fault detection and predictive maintenance in a 5G-enabled environment

In terms of interfaces, the Network Application blueprint therefore contains:

- A web GUI service interface (in provider mode) to access the monitoring panels and their configuration options.
- A service interface in consumer mode to access the monitoring data available in the IoT Management Platform datastore, using HTTP protocol and JSON based messages.
- A management service interface in provider mode, which allows to customize the Network Application, using a HTTP REST based API.

The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

3.2.11 VS5 Remote Vessel Monitoring

This Network Application assists the captain onboard or at the shore control center while navigating. The dashboard will contain a camera feed, a map with the vessel location, the actual vessel speed, the advised vessel speed received from VS7 and a map with the nearby objects received from VA5. Furthermore, it will be possible to send a goal location to VS6 and activate VS6 whenever needed.

5G connectivity is required for this Network Application because of the stringent bandwidth requirements on the uplink needed for a high amount of data that will be sent out in form of HD video, and the strict low latency requirements for the sensor data. The latency/data throughput will be added as KPI on the dashboard to visualize the performance of the sensor data transmission during testing and operation.

Figure 27: VS5 Network Application Architecture

This Network Application can be internally divided into multiple components (the Network Application architecture is presented in Figure 27):

- **Vessel Connector:** This component connects to the vessel through 5G to get the necessary network KPI's and camera feeds, for which low latency is required.
- **Network Application Connector:** The Network Application connector connects to different Network Applications to communicate the necessary information with them. The information flowing from this component will get visualized in different visualization components.
- **Vessel Location Visualization:** A component with a map to visualize the vessel that is being monitored. The location comes from VS8.
- **Optimal Speed Visualization:** A component that visualizes the optimal speed that is calculated in VS7.
- **Nearby Objects Visualization:** A component that visualizes nearby objects coming from VA5.
- **Action Visualization:** A component that visualizes the actions calculated in VS6.
- **User Input Fields:** Input fields that can be used by the monitoring operator to activate/modify VS7/VS6 by changing the destination location & time.

The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

3.2.12 VS6 Assisted vessel navigation

This Network Application is responsible for assisted navigation of a vessel, consisting in trajectory prediction and including real-time obstacle avoidance. It is a vertical-specific Network Application because it is specific to the assisted vessel transport use case. It will be deployed in the Antwerp testbed area but it could be deployed in other port-like locations, provided they have sufficient 5G facilities available.

VS6 is developed by IMEC and relies on hardware from SF and TEL. As the Network Application performs vessel navigation, it is subject to restrictions and its access is not public: it is meant for the ship management company

(SF) only. Further potential usage from other VITAL-5G partners or 3rd parties will be discussed on a per-partner basis.

Assisted navigation relies on real-time obstacle detection and tracking in the form of a dynamic occupancy grid map, on on-board sensor data (latitude, longitude, heading, speed) and on goal position data (latitude, longitude). The dynamic map is provided by the Real-Time Digital Twin (VA5) and allows the planning algorithm to localize the environment and obstacles. Sensor data, collected on the vessel via On-Board Data Collection and Interfacing for vessel Tercofin II (VS8), consist in the real-time position, heading and speed of the vessel. Finally, the goal position is provided by the Remote Navigation Monitoring (VS5) and consists in the global target position that the vessel is expected to reach. VS6 also implements communication with the vessel and the control center: the calculated trajectory waypoints (latitude, longitude) are sent to the vessel, and videos of navigation can be sent to the control center for monitoring. In addition, request messages can be sent to the vessel and/or the control center in case a takeover of the vessel control by the skipper/captain is necessary.

Therefore, VS6 has interfaces with the VA5, VS8 and VS5 Network Applications and with the vessel and control center. This Network Application can be deployed on the vessel, in the control center, or in the cloud, depending on the available hardware dedicated to computation. In fact, computations can be offloaded from the vessel by running the array processing and AI-based algorithms on remote servers. Always-on connectivity and URLLC of the 5G network are required for real-time data sending to the vessel and for data exchanges with computation servers in case such a choice is made. eMBB is also required in case HD video sending to the control center is enabled.

Figure 28: VS6 component model

Figure 28 represents the high-level functional architecture of the Assisted vessel navigation Network Application. Up-to-date sensor data is collected from on-board sensors, received from VS8 (position, speed, heading) and processed and received from VA5 (dynamic map). Along with the global goal position provided by VS5, they

constitute the input to the global path planner component. This atomic component is responsible for computing intermediate goal positions which are necessary for the optimal functioning of the trajectory (local) planner. A set of intermediate goal positions is sent to the local planner using the Network Application internal connectivity. The local planner then computes a set of predicted waypoints and visualization data (video) if enabled, which are sent to the vessel and control center respectively over the 5G connectivity.

Figure 29 shows the VS6 Network Application architecture. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

Figure 29: VS6 Network Application architecture

3.2.13 VS7 Navigation speed optimizer

This Network Application is developed to help vessel operators (human or computer-based) in their daily navigation tasks by providing them with an optimal navigation speed so that they arrive just in time, resulting in reduced waiting times and fuel consumption. To this end, real-time data is collected from various sources via the 5G network, processed and given to an algorithm to calculate the optimal navigation speed. The result of this calculation can then be integrated into a vessel’s navigation dashboard.

As shown in Figure 30, the VS7 retrieves data from Tercofin II VS8 and, after processing the optimal navigation speed, delivers this result to remote vessel monitoring (VS5). 5G is a prerequisite for low latency and very high reliability (given through the 5G network availability) of data transfer with regard to vessels position, speed, heading.

Figure 30: VS7 Network Application architecture

As shown in Figure 31, VS7 uses also external APIs to retrieve the real-time data needed to calculate the optimal navigation speed for a vessel. In the first phase, this data is being collected from three sources as follows:

the GPS coordinates of the vessel’s current location and the destination of the voyage, i.e., the destination terminal, are sent to the NSO API from the client application.

based on these coordinates the inland navigation routing API can retrieve the inland navigation route. Hence, it can calculate the distance to be sailed. VisuRIS offers this kind of inland navigation routing API. Alternative services are Searoutes and Seamatrix.

the terminal planning is needed to calculate how much time remains until the vessel can be operated at the earliest at the terminal. Through the NxtPort PortCall+ API one could retrieve information on the movement of vessels within the port. An alternative would be to set up a NSO management portal (database) that contains the various terminals and their possible operating time slots. Another alternative would be to calculate the available length at the terminal by reducing the length of the terminal by the length of the moored (and expected) vessels.

The data from these three sources is then being used as input to the NSO algorithm. The optimal navigation speed is, in the first phase, calculated as the division of the distance to the terminal on the time remaining to the available time window to be operated.

The client application can then call the NSO API to retrieve the optimal navigation speed and integrate it into the vessel navigation dashboard. From a security point of view, all API traffic gets encrypted with SSL certificates. For authentication, this Network Application uses Oauth v2.4. This is an open standard for access delegation. This

⁴ OAuth v2.0 Authorisation Framework: <https://auth0.com/docs/authorization/protocols/protocol-oauth2>

protocol allows the user to give access to another website or web application without giving away their username and password. A token will be used to give a certain website or web application access for a limited amount of time. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

Figure 31: VS7 component model

3.2.14 VS8 Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II

This Network Application is responsible for collecting public vessel data from on board sensors (e.g., location, vessel heading, speed, water depth, etc.) that will be eventually made publicly available for other VITAL-5G Network Applications and 3rd party Network Applications. It is a vertical-specific Network Application because it is specific to the sensors on-boarded in the Tercofin II vessel used in UC1. The Network Application itself will be deployed in the UC1 cloud (at IMEC premises), although it will rely on the sensors deployed in the vessel at the testbed area.

The internal component model is represented in Figure 32. The Network Application receives from the 5G network, using a URLLC slice, data from sensors such as speed, latitude, longitude, and vessel heading. This data will be processed by the Device Specific Interface element, which translates the specific formats of the sensor data to a common standard format used in the UC1 ecosystem. This data will be optionally stored in the Data Store and it will be made publicly available according to the rules and policies of the Data Manager. External Network Applications will be able to use this data through the Public Interface component.

Figure 32: VS8 component model

Figure 33 shows the overall architecture of VS8, consisting only of a single atomic component, the Data Proxy Server. Such component receives the on-boarded sensors data from the vessel (Tercofin II) through an external 5G endpoint and exports the data through a generic external Network Application endpoint. This endpoint will also be used to manage the policies and behavior of the Network Application. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

Figure 33: VS8 Network Application Architecture

3.2.15 VS9 Onboard data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel

VS9 collects data from on board sensors (water speed, water depth, outside/inside temperature, engine functional parameters, etc.) and from video cameras placed on board of the NAVROM vessel, as Figure 34 shows. All data is made available for the local on-board server and provides the interface to/from external edge nodes and the 5G network. This software application is to be deployed on a server that has specific interfaces for different types of devices installed on board and surveillance modules. The data is formatted in a way to be understood and treated by the next level Network Application. For UC2, it will support the targeted cost reduction.

VS9 has specific inputs from NAVROM vessel sensors (water speed, water depth, engine parameters etc.) and video streams. Its outputs are API endpoints towards edge nodes and 5G network and API endpoints towards other Network Applications. The overall Network Application blueprint in JSON format is reported in Annex I.

Figure 34: VS9 Network Application Architecture

4 The VITAL-5G platform

The high-level design of the VITAL-5G platform is shown in Figure 35, identifying the various software modules that will implement the platform functionalities as derived from the functional architecture defined in D1.2 [1]. This section provides the list of the software components and the roadmap for their implementation in the three releases of the VITAL-5G platform planned in WP2, i.e., D2.2, D2.3 and D2.4. The details of each software component are provided in the following Section 5 (Portal backend), Section 6 (Management backend services), Section 7 (Open Online Repository), and Section 8 (Portal Web GUI).

Figure 35: Software components of VITAL-5G platform

The software components depicted in Figure 35 can be classified in three main categories:

The core components of the VITAL-5G Platform, represented in grey, provide the baseline functionalities to enable the experimental validation of vertical services composed of Network Applications in a 5G-enabled infrastructure.

The management services, represented in blue, support the core components with transversal functionalities related to the management of the users and their access to the VITAL-5G services, as well as the management of various aspects of the VITAL-5G testbeds, required to properly interact with them.

The advanced functionalities, represented in red, provide added-value services to facilitate and improve the definition of the experiments, the management of the vertical services and the analysis of the experiment results.

The core components and the management services will be developed in the context of Task 2.2 (catalogues and service lifecycle management functions) and Task 2.3 (experimentation and validation functions), while the advanced functionalities will be developed in Task 2.4. The implementation of the various components has been scheduled and prioritized on the basis of the analysis of the requirements performed in D1.2. In particular, the AI-based placement and the Network Application validator at on-boarding time have been classified as optional components and they will be introduced in later releases of the VITAL-5G platform.

The design and implementation of the VITAL-5G platform will adopt the 5G EVE platform⁵ [2] as software baseline for most of its software components, with some modifications that impact all the software modules. For example, new catalogues will be introduced to support onboarding and management of Network Applications, additional features will be added to meet the new VITAL-5G requirements in terms of interaction with T&L and IoT devices, the experiment management procedures are re-designed to enable a more flexible provisioning of vertical services decoupled from the experiment execution, the slice management have been re-designed to match the capabilities of VITAL-5G testbeds, etc. The details of the updates for each software component will be provided in the following sections.

Table 30 provides a list of the VITAL-5G platform software components, with their software baseline and target releases, while Table 31 provides the justification per each of the components based on whether it has been developed as a new component in the VITAL-5G project, or reused from the other projects and updated to fit the purposes of the VITAL-5G platform.

Table 30: List of VITAL-5G platform software components

Software component	VITAL-5G Platform block	Planned Updates	Release
Portal web GUI Graphical interface providing unified access to VITAL-5G Platform.	VITAL-5G Portal	Extensions to support Network Applications and visualization of IoT & T&L devices in VITAL-5G testbeds.	From D2.2
Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue Catalogue and logic of VITAL-5G Open Online Repository	Open Online Repository	New Network Applications catalogue and onboarding, update of NSD and existing blueprint information models.	From D2.2
Service LCM Manager to coordinate the instantiation and lifecycle actions of vertical services.	VITAL-5G Portal Backend	Modification of lifecycle logic to decouple service provisioning from test execution and support of network slice selection or provisioning.	From D2.2
License Manager Component to store and validate Network Application licenses.	Open Online Repository	New component.	From D2.4
Access Control Entity to authorize users' access to VITAL-5G services.	VITAL-5G Management Backend	Definition of new user roles and groups.	From D2.3
Slice Inventory Component to retrieve and request network slices in	VITAL-5G Management Backend	New component.	From D2.3

⁵ <https://github.com/5GEVE>

VITAL-5G testbeds.			
Multi-site Inventory Centralized inventory with information on all testbeds.	VITAL-5G Management Backend	Extensions to model VITAL-5G testbed information, including IoT & T&L devices.	From D2.3
Monitoring Platform (Centralized) ELK-based platform to collect, store and visualize service and infrastructure KPIs.	VITAL-5G Portal Backend	Updates to enabled access control on a per-user and per-group basis.	From D2.3
Blueprint Validation Tool Tool to verify the blueprints' format during their onboarding.	Open Online Repository	Extensions to support Network Application blueprints.	From D2.2
Experiment LCM Manager to coordinate the service testing and experiment procedures.	VITAL-5G Portal Backend	Modification of lifecycle logic to decouple service provisioning from test execution and support default testing procedures.	From D2.2
Network Application Validator Tool to verify the correct deployment of a Network Application in the target testbed at onboarding time.	Open Online Repository	New component.	From D2.3
Intent-based requests manager Tool to simplify the request of services and experiments.	VITAL-5G Portal Backend	Support of Network Applications and integration with VITAL-5G platform.	From D2.4
Results analytics Component to analyze the collected KPIs and evaluate the service performance.	VITAL-5G Portal Backend	Support of Network Applications and integration with VITAL-5G platform.	From D2.3
AI-based diagnostics Component to produce performance insights on the basis of the collected KPIs.	VITAL-5G Portal Backend	Update of diagnostic logic.	From D2.3

The official releases of the platform, due in D2.2, D2.3 and D2.4, will be installed in a production environment hosted in the Romanian testbed, which will be made available for the trial execution. The deployment will be based on a set of Virtual Machines (VMs) running the various software components, as reported in Table 32. The integration and functional validation of the VITAL-5G platform software will be preliminarily performed in a testing environment, also hosted in the Romanian testbed, in the context of T3.2 and T3.3 activities.

Table 31: VITAL-5G platform components baseline and justification.

Software component	Justification (New/Reused)
Portal web GUI	Reused from 5G-EVE but revamped completely to fit the purpose of the project. More specifically, the VITAL-5G GUI, will provide access to users to all the backend functionalities and tools of the VITAL-5G platform to design their experiments. The goal is to provide an intent-based service where internal and 3 rd -party users can conveniently select experiments, the Network Applications that they would like to use from the Network Application catalogue or upload their own Network Application for testing and the required service blueprints. The main features that the VITAL-5G GUI offers are: Access Control using KeyCloak integration, an improved Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint filtering using a variety of parameters (testbed, use case or status) depending on the user's needs, advanced testcase blueprint management and updated experiment descriptors, implementation of the experiment Life Cycle Manager, improved monitoring capabilities as well as improved visualisation of the vertical service blueprints.
Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue	Uses 5G EVE Portal Catalogue as baseline. VITAL-5G contributions will target: (i) Introduction of the information elements and repositories to support the VITAL-5G Network Application concept; (ii) Update information elements to decouple experiments and vertical services to enable independent lifecycle management operations; (iii) Development of drivers to support Testbed NFVO catalogue management and synchronization; (iv) Update catalogue management workflows to leverage file storage backends (e.g. Minio); (v) Develop interfaces and update workflows to use other VITAL-5G platform modules (i.e. Multi-site inventory, Network Application Validation, etc.).
Service LCM	Uses 5G EVE Service LCM as baseline. VITAL-5G contributions will target: (i) Interface and workflow updated decouple experiments and vertical services to enable independent lifecycle management operations; (ii) Development of drivers to support Testbed NFVO LCM; (iii) Develop interfaces and update workflows to use other VITAL-5G platform modules (i.e. Multi-site inventory, Monitoring platform, Multi-site 5G slice inventory etc.).
License Manager	New component; designed and developed in the VITAL-5G project.
Access Control	Reused from 5G-EVE but revamped completely to fit the purpose of the project. The Access control system in the 5G-EVE project is based on a Dockerized Keycloak service, an open-source IAM solution. The GUI and backend services (i.e. experiment-lcm, multi-site-inventory, NetworkApplicationCatalog, NetworkApplicationValidator, service-lcm) interact with the Access control component and limit system access to authorized users through RBAC (Role-Based Access Control). Roles are defined at Keycloak's realm level, including Experimenter, Network Application Developer, Platform Admin, Platform Technician, Testbed Admin, T&L Site Infrastructure Manager, and Vertical Service Provider. Additional granularity is achieved by assigning extra attributes to the

	user's access token for each Use Case (UC1, UC2, UC3).
Slice Inventory	New component entirely developed within VITAL-5G.
Multi-site Inventory	New component; designed and developed in the VITAL-5G project.
Monitoring Platform (Centralized)	New component; designed and developed in the VITAL-5G project.
Blueprint Validation Tool	Reused from 5G-EVE, but revamped completely to fit the purpose of the project. The validator from 5G-EVE was a command-line tool (a jar file) with limited functionality: static validation of the syntax of a blueprint. The blueprint validation tool is re-packaged as a web application to be part of the Network Application Validator. Besides validation of blueprint syntax, it also performs basic validation of IoT data used by the Network Application.
Experiment LCM	Uses 5G EVE Experiment LCM as baseline. VITAL-5G contributions will target: (i) Interface and workflow updated to decouple experiments and vertical services to enable independent lifecycle management operations; (ii) Development of drivers to support enhanced test execution mechanisms; ((iii) Develop interfaces and update workflows to use other VITAL-5G platform modules (i.e. Multi-site inventory, monitoring platform,); (iv) Updates to use new Testcase Blueprint and descriptor information elements.
Network Application Validator	New component, incorporates blueprint validation tool (See above). Functionalities include: OpenAPI-based REST interfaces for interaction with other components; validation of sensor data in the testbed facilities (via interaction with multi-site inventory); dynamic KPI monitoring and validation from the 5G testbed.
Intent-based requests manager	This platform component is still under discussion and targeted for the last release of the platform. Thus, we expect the component to be completely new, designed and developed in the VITAL-5G project. The final identification of the contributions of the project to the software baseline will be therefore described in D2.4.
Results analytics	Component reused from 5G EVE. Updated with real-time operation and support for generating triggers for the LCM closed-loop control mechanism.
AI-based diagnostics	Component reused from 5G EVE. Updated with real-time operation and support for generating triggers for the LCM closed-loop control mechanism.

Table 32: VMs for VITAL-5G platform deployment

Virtual Machine	Software components	Resource requirements
VM #1	Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue Service LCM Experiment LCM License Manager Multi-site Inventory	CPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 50 GB
VM #2	Portal web GUI	CPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 50 GB
VM #3	Results Analytics AI-based Diagnostic Intent-based Requests Manager	CPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 40 GB
VM #4	Slice Inventory Monitoring Platform (Data Collection Manager)	CPU: 8 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 120 GB
VM #5	Monitoring Platform (Data Collection Storage)	CPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 50 GB
VM #6	Blueprint Validation Tool Network Application Validator	CPU: 4 RAM: 8 GB Disk: 30 GB
VM #7	Access Control	CPU: 4 RAM: 4 GB Disk: 30 GB

5 The VITAL-5G Portal Backend

This Section describes the components that compose the VITAL-5G Portal Backend. The portal backend manages the core and internal logic of the VITAL-5G portal, supporting the VITAL-5G GUI and interacting with the operational databases required in the VITAL-5G platform. It includes three main components: the (T&L) Service Lifecycle Manager (Section 5.2) to coordinate the instantiation and life-cycle actions of vertical services, the Monitoring Platform (Section 5.3), a centralized ELK-based platform to collect, store and visualize service and infrastructure KPIs and the (T&L) Experiment Lifecycle Manager (Section 5.4), to coordinate the service testing and experiment procedures. Additionally, there are advanced functionalities provided by the Intent-based requests manager (Section 5.1), a tool to simplify the request of services and experiments, the Results Analytics component (Section 5.5), to analyze the collected KPIs and evaluate the service performance and the AI-based Diagnostic component (Section 5.6), to produce performance insights on the basis of the collected KPIs.

5.1 Intent-Based interface

Intent Based Networking (IBN) provides a new approach to networking, where planning, design, implementation and changes to a network layer are automated to a significant degree in order to assist the end-user. IBN's main goal is to simplify the creation, management and policy enforcement to the network layer with the use of artificial intelligence (AI), network orchestration and machine learning (ML). IBN captures and translates higher-level user/business intents into network policies that can be automated and applied consistently across the network. The end goal is for the network to continuously monitor and adjust network performance to assure the desired business outcome [12]. Besides its application on network management, Intent-Based mechanisms have also been used to facilitate the service and experimentation creation over dynamic/re-configurable platforms and to assist end-users without the necessary expertise/know-how, to interact with advanced experimentation tools/platforms and to set-up, configure, execute and analyze the results of experiments.

Such an experimenter-oriented Intent-Based (IB) mechanism was created within the context of the ICT-17 5G-EVE project [2], to facilitate the experimenters' interaction with the experimentation platform, to offer them the possibility to interact with the platform in natural language and to facilitate the selection of the proper tools, descriptors, blueprints and setting for their individual experiments. As described in 5G-EVE D4.1 [13] and 5G-EVE D4.4 [14], an end-user may interact with the IB component of the experimentation platform closer to their natural language and provide some key information regarding the experiment they are interested in executing, such as, the testbed they would like to use, the use case they are interested in, the number of end-devices to be included in the experiment, the experiment execution date/time, and more. Based on this high-level information, the IB mechanism proposes the most relevant Service and Experiment blueprints that the experimenter should use in order to set-up their experiment, while some key values/fields of the Blueprints are already pre-filled based on the user's input (the rest can be manually completed), as depicted in Figure 36. At the end of the process, an experiment descriptor is created, with all the necessary information to execute an experiment over the platform and the user has the opportunity to verify that this is indeed the intended experiment, and subsequently execute it.

Since the use of such an IB interface practically lowers the barrier for the use of complex experimentation platforms from vertical non-expert end-users, as it facilitates the set-up, configuration and execution of complex experiments without the need for a deep-understanding of the underlying technology, this is an extremely interesting tool for VITAL-5G as well, as the project's mission is to bridge the knowledge/expertise gap between the T&L sector, telecommunication experts and application developers. To this end the IB interface/mechanism developed in 5G-EVE will be re-purposed within VITAL-5G and will be offered as an experimentation tool via the central VITAL-5G platform, after it has been upgraded/extended in order to address the specific needs of the VITAL-5G platform and to make it compatible with the overall platform architecture.

5G EVE

New Intent Guided Selection 5G-EVE project 5G-EVE use cases 5G-EVE Portal Help

Please fill in the missing parameters:

Site: ITALY_TURIN
 Service blueprint: ARES2T Tracker service
 Experiment blueprint: Ares2T tracking experiment

Retry Guided

[ARES2T Tracker service] - service parameters

Number of tracked devices

[Delay Generator] - context parameters

Incoming Traffic Load

[TCB Ares2T Tracking with delay] - test case parameters

delay

delay variance

consecutive delay dependency percentage

Experiment descriptor details

Name:

Experiment details

Date

Day: Month: Year:

Time

Hour: Minute:

Duration

Minutes:

Submit

1 field(s) left

Figure 36: 5G EVE Intent based tool-Experiment blueprint and service parameters selection (13)

The VITAL-5G Intent-Based mechanism will be exposed to the experimenters via the Graphic User Interface (GUI) (Front-end) of the VITAL-5G platform and will assist them, with the understanding of the platform layout, the explanation of the available options and of course with the set-up, configuration, execution and results collection of the experiment. The IB mechanism inherited from 5G-EVE will be updated to support the selected VITAL-5G platform architecture, see Deliverable D1.2 [1], while its catalogues will be updated to reflect the VITAL-5G available options, in terms of available trial sites, available services, available equipment/sensors, available vehicles, etc. more over an extension of the IB mechanism will be implemented in order to incorporate the notion of Network Applications and to assist the experimenter with the selection and configuration of the appropriate Network Applications, depending on their selected trial site and service.

Table 33 depicts the envisioned parameters to be supported by the VITAL-5G IB interface, their definition and some exemplary values. Based on the experimenter's high-level input in natural language, some or all of the fields of relevant experimentation templates (e.g., blueprints, test cases) will be populated by the IB mechanism. In this sense, the service offered by the IB mechanism, is that it consumes information from the experimenter in a natural language, and translates it to specific, settings and experimental configuration choices, without the need for the experimenter to possess expert knowledge. The more information the experimenter provides over the IB interface, the more accurate the suggested experiment descriptor will be, and the more information will be pre-filled on their behalf. The experimenter will have the opportunity to review all suggestions and agree or edit any of the fields of the experiment descriptor after being presented with a list of all available alternatives. At the end of the process, the experiment will be ready for execution and the administrator of the selected facility will be informed about the type of experiment that needs to be executed on their respective site. This IB functionality is expected to significantly assist the interaction with the 3rd party experimenters with the VITAL-

5G platform as well, and to reduce the time and effort required to onboard and execute their experiments, using the available VITAL-5G Network Applications, components and tools.

Table 33: VITAL-5G Intent Based mechanism envisioned parameters

VITAL-5G Intent parameters	Definition	Example values
Experiment T&L site	Selection of one of the three VITAL-5G trial sites.	Antwerp (Belgium), Athens (Greece), Galati (Romania)
Experiment T&L domain	Selection of the T&L domain of interest around which the experiment should be focused.	Seaport, Riverport, Road, Warehouse
Targeted T&L service	Selection of a specific targeted T&L service that the experiment should be focused on.	Remote ship navigation, Warehouse autonomous pallet transfer, heterogeneous data ingestion, etc.
Selected Network Application(s)	Selection of all relevant Network Applications that should be used for this experiment.	Any Network Application from the list of available Network Applications ⁶
Targeted 5G functionality	Selection of a specific 5G service or slice type and profile, which should be the focus of the experiment.	eMBB, uRLLC, mMTC
Selected end-devices	Selection of specific devices that should be included in the experiment.	Sensors, cameras, smartphones, AGVs, etc.
Experiment duration / repetitions	Definition of the parameters of the experiment.	e.g., Repeat 5 times or execute for 2 hours

5.2 Service Lifecycle Manager (Service LCM)

The Service LifeCycle Manager (Service LCM) is the component responsible for processing the lifecycle management requests to create, terminate, query and update vertical service instances. This module offers a REST-based north-bound interface (NBI) which can be accessed transparently through the VITAL-5G GUI or using external REST clients. The full list of supported actions is detailed in Table 34, with details about the users (human users or software entities) that can consume them. All the requests arriving to the NBI will be authenticated and authorized using the Access Control module described in Section 6.1.

Table 34: T&L Service LCM supported actions

Action	Users
Creation of a new service instance	Service Provider or Experimenter
Approval or refusal of service instance	Testbed Administrator
Instantiation of a service instance	Service Provider or Experimenter
Scaling of a service instance	Service Provider or Experimenter VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use Network Applications

⁶ The list of available Network Applications may differ depending on the experimenter, their selected profile and the level of Access that they have been granted by the platform administrator, i.e., some restricted Network Applications may not appear as options for 3rd party experimenters

Termination of a service instance	Service Provider or Experimenter
Query of a service instance information	Service Provider or Experimenter VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use Network Applications
Deletion of a service instance	Service Provider or Experimenter
Update of service instance status	VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use

The baseline implementation for this module is the Experiment Lifecycle Manager⁷ from 5G EVE described in [15]. The software is a Java based Spring-boot application that uses a number of external tools, such as PostgreSQL for the backend database, and RabbitMQ for the asynchronous message exchange between the internal components. Moreover, the module uses Apache Maven to ease the module building process. The updated software architecture for this module is depicted in Figure 37.

Figure 37: Vertical Service LCM Software Architecture

As depicted in Figure 37, the NBI of the Service LCM is implemented using a REST controller which receives the incoming requests and interacts with the Access Control module to authenticate and authorize the requested action. The requests are then forwarded to the VS LCM Engine, which is responsible for creating a specific VSI

⁷Implementation available in: <https://github.com/nextworks-it/experiment-portal/tree/master/ExperimentLifecycleManager>

(Vertical Service Instance) Manager for each instance in case of a VS Instance creation request, or to forward the message to the specific manager for other lifecycle management actions (using the RabbitMQ message bus). The instance managers use singleton services to mediate the interactions with the other modules of the VITAL-5G platform, with testbed platform components and external platforms. In VITAL-5G we use REST-based requests to communicate between the different modules, and therefore all these services rely on REST clients. In particular, the interactions with the following components are performed:

- **Open online repository:** Retrieval of Vertical Service and Network Application blueprints (including the licensing information), translation of vertical service request into NFV Network Services (NFV-NS) deployments.
- **Multi-site inventory:** Retrieval of testbed information and credentials.
- **Multi-site 5G Slice inventory:** Retrieval or instantiation of 5G slices in the selected testbed. Such slices will support the vertical service applications and they will be selected on the basis of the 5G slice profiles associated to the Network Applications and the T&L service.
- **Testbed NFVO:** Request of the NFV-NS lifecycle management actions (i.e., instantiate, scale and terminate) required by the specific vertical service lifecycle management action.
- **Vertical Service Monitoring:** To configure the collection of application and infrastructure metrics as defined in T&L service and Network Applications blueprints.
- **License Manager:** To interact with the License Manager in case of deployment of Network Applications with closed licenses, in order to validate the requested operation and update the licensing usage accordingly.

In Figure 37 the Testbed NFVOs are depicted in color since they are external to the VITAL-5G platform and deployed in the VITAL-5G testbeds. In the figure, we also highlight which are the submodules to be updated or added with respect to the baseline 5G EVE implementation. In Table 35 we detail the main functionalities of each submodule and the required updates from the baseline.

Table 35: Service LCM modules description and required extensions

Submodule	Description	Extensions/Modifications
REST Controller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide the REST-based NBI towards the GUI and external clients. • Authenticate and authorize the incoming request. • Perform initial request validation. • Forward requests to the VS LCM Engine. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In 5G EVE the management of the service instances was coupled with the management of the experiments. In VITAL-5G we aim to decouple this logic, removing the experiment related actions from the NBI and adding the API for the creation of vertical service instances. • Updated Access Control mechanisms. • Update LCM messages to include licensing keys during the instantiation. • Support of service scaling requests. • Update LCM messages to include 5G slice related information (e.g., IMSI ids of the terminals, etc.).
VS LCM Engine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate all incoming requests. • Create the specific VSI Managers upon the arrival of VS instantiation requests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated logic and data models to handled LCM of vertical services instead of experiments.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Process incoming request forwarding them to the correspondent VSI manager. 	
VSI Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Process incoming LCM requests for a single VSI. Upon receipt of an instantiation/scaling request: Trigger the 5G slice selection and instantiation workflow, Trigger Placement algorithms, Trigger vertical application NFV-NS instantiation/scaling, Trigger e-license validation, Trigger monitoring metric configuration. Upon receipt of a termination request: Trigger 5G slice de-commissioning, trigger vertical application NFV-NS termination, Trigger monitoring metric de-commissioning, trigger e-license usage update. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated logic and data models to be handled LCM of vertical services instead of experiments. Added Network Application License validation support, adding licensing validation workflows to the baseline implementation. Updated VSI record information models to support the new data models of the blueprints and to include licensing information. Added 5G slice selection and instantiation workflow. Added usage of Multi-site Inventory for site configuration and credential retrieval.
VSI Record Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Management of the Vertical Service Instance Records. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated VSI record information models to support the new data models of the blueprints and to include licensing information.
Open online repository service & client	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mediator for the retrieval of Network Application and Vertical Service blueprints from the Open Online Repository. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated data models and support for Network Applications.
Multi-site inventory service & client	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mediator for the retrieval of testbed configuration information and credentials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New module.
Multi-site 5G slice inventory service & client	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mediator for the retrieval of the available slices and the request for 5G slice instantiation and configuration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New module.
NFVO Service & client	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mediator for the interaction with the Testbed NFVO for the NFV-NS lifecycle management actions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated with drivers to interact with the NFVOs available in the three VITAL-5G testbeds.
VS Monitoring service & client	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mediator with the VS Monitoring module for the configuration of the monitoring metrics associated with services and Network Applications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated data model with enhanced list of supported metrics. Removal of actions related to experiment execution.
E-license mgmt Service & Client	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validation of the license keys and the requested lifecycle management action. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New module.

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mediator with the E-licensing validation component. | |
|--|---|--|

The Finite State Machine (FSM) representing the evolution of the lifecycle of a Vertical Service instance (VSI) is depicted in Figure 38. This FSM is created when the Service LCM receives a request to instantiate a new Vertical Service. The FSM is initialized in “Created” state, during which the Service LCM retrieves all the blueprints from the Open Online Repository. The VS instantiation request contains the timeslot proposed by the user to run the service instance. The Testbed Administrator can accept or reject the proposed timeslot, causing the FSM status to move to “Accepted” or “Rejected” respectively. After a VSI has been accepted, there might be manual operations required in order to prepare the infrastructure for the instantiation, and therefore the testbed administrator shall issue a notification which confirms the infrastructure is ready to deploy the VS instance. This notification causes the FSM to move to a “Ready” status. Optionally a configuration may be set in the Multi-site Inventory to automatically accept and set the VSIs to ready, to avoid manual interventions.

Once a VSI is in ready state the user is allowed to trigger the service deployment in the testbed, which causes the VSI Manager to deploy the service contacting: Multi-site inventory, Multi-site 5G slice inventory, Testbed NFVO and VS Monitoring. Moreover, during this phase the licensing information is verified using the licensing keys provided in the instantiation request. If something fails either during the licensing validation or during the NFV-NS instantiation the FSM will move to a “Failed” status.

When the NFV-NS of the VS has been instantiated and the monitoring metrics configured correctly, the FSM shall pass to the “Instantiated” status. At this stage the user can trigger the execution of an experiment interacting with the Experiment LCM component (with the mediation of the GUI). The Experiment LCM module will notify the initiation or termination of an experiment to prevent the termination of service instances which are in use. During this stage, scaling procedures may also be triggered by the user or other components of the VITAL-5G service backend, or even by the Network Applications belonging to the service. The FSM moves to the “Scaling” status accordingly. This will trigger the validation of the licenses and the correspondent NFV-NS scaling procedures. Upon finalization of the scaling workflow, the FSM will return to the “Instantiated” state.

Finally, the user may request the termination of the service instance. This request will move the status of the FSM to “Terminating”, which will subsequently pass to “Terminate” once the monitoring metrics have been cleared, the NFV-NS terminated, and the licensing information updated.

Figure 38: Vertical Service Instance Finite State Machine

The abstract messages of the interface exposed by the Service LCM are described in Table 36, including the message parameters and the returned results where relevant.

Table 36: Service LCM Abstract Messages

Message	Parameters	Notes
InstantiateVS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vertical Service Blueprint id (String) Proposed timeslot (start and end time references) IMSI ids (Strings) Licensing keys (to be determined) Configuration parameters (map with parameter id and value, where the id corresponds to the one declared in the blueprint) Service Parameters (map with parameter id and value, where the id corresponds to the one declared in the blueprint) 	Returns the Vertical Service Instance ID (VSI Id) generated by the Service LCM.

QueryVSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optional query parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ VSB Id ○ Tenant ○ VSI Id ○ Use case 	Returns the list of VSI records matching the query parameters.
ScaleVSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VSI Id • Service Parameters (map with parameter id and value, where the id corresponds to the one declared in the blueprint). 	
UseVSI/ReleaseVSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VSI Id • Experiment execution identifier 	To be used by internally by the VITAL-5G platform to signal the creation/termination of an experiment execution associated with a VSI.
TerminateVSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VSI Id 	The VSI is terminated, but the instance is maintained in the internal database.
DeleteVSI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VSI Id 	The VSI is completely removed from the internal database.

5.3 T&L Service Monitoring

In order to provide experiment and service monitoring and results collection functionalities through the T&L Service Monitoring component to the VITAL-5G platform, the VITAL-5G Service Monitoring component leverages two components previously developed in the 5G EVE project [2]: the 5G EVE Data Collection Manager (DCM) [16] and 5G EVE Data Collection Storage (DCS) [17].

- The DCM element is responsible of the collection and delivery of the vertical service performance metrics gathered during the execution of experiments, interacting with the local monitoring platforms located in each testbed. The DCM also exports metrics and KPIs to the Result Analytics component, the AI-based Diagnostics component, the Service LCM component and the Experiment LCM component.
- The DCS element oversees the storing, maintenance, and monitoring of the experiment data, providing also the means for exporting and visualizing it to the VITAL-5G Web GUI.

A simplified representation of the T&L Service Monitoring component architecture and its interactions is illustrated in Figure 39. Details of both DCM and DCS are described in detail in Sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2 respectively.

Figure 39: T&L Service Monitoring architecture

5.3.1 Data Collection Manager

The DCM gathers and distributes all the network and vertical performance metrics and KPI values, which are required to be gathered during the execution of the experiments. Its main objective is to monitor the experiment, both from the service and network perspective. It is based on the multi-broker architecture inherited from 5G EVE DCM [16]. It fully integrates the automatic configuration of all the site brokers, enabling the interconnection between the site brokers in the local monitoring platforms at the testbed sites and the main centralized broker placed in the VITAL-5G platform. Figure 40 presents such architecture, based on the 5G EVE DCM architecture, which has been adapted to the VITAL-5G platform architecture.

In this new VITAL-5G architecture, the main differences lay in the horizontal relationships with other VITAL-5G components and the simplification of the interaction with the testbed sites.

On one hand, now the Main Broker does not only interact with the Result Analysis Validation (RAV) but rather with the VITAL-5G equivalent, the Result Analytics (RA), and also interacts with the new AI-based Diagnostics component. In a similar manner, the DCM Handler does not interact with the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELM) but with the Experiment LCM and Service LCM components defined in VITAL-5G. On the other hand, in VITAL-5G there is no Interworking Layer as there was in 5G EVE. This removes the need to have multiple broker coordinators at both the DCM and testbed sites levels: the local monitoring system in each VITAL-5G testbed will directly publish their metrics into the Main Broker.

Figure 40: Data Collection Manager architecture

The rest of the internal architecture is expected to remain unchanged: a set of MirrorMaker instances, managed by the DCM Handler, will coordinate the life-cycle of the topics to be created in the DCM and in the testbed sites, and the delivery of all the monitoring data is done through the Main Broker, which offers this monitoring data to horizontal or upper layers (i.e., in VITAL-5G, the Results Analytics and AI-based Diagnostics components to analyze and process the KPIs associated, or the DCS to save the data and display them through dashboards in the VITAL-5G Web GUI).

The implementation of the VITAL-5G DCM will be start from the 5G EVE DCM as baseline⁸.

The OpenAPI specifications of VITAL-5G Service Monitoring will mostly remain the same for both the DCM Handler and the DCM Site Plugin, except for the DCM Site services. While the original OpenAPI specifications are available in the 5G EVE Github repository⁹, a preliminary list of the ones used in VITAL-5G is presented in the following Table 37.

Table 37: Data Collection Manager operations from its Open API specification

Service	Path	Method	Input	Output	Description
DCM Handler	/dcm/subscribe	POST	expld = internal topic = signalling topic name	201 – accepted 400 - error	Subscribe to the signalling topic provided as input in the body request.
DCM Handler	/dcm/unsubscribe	DELETE	expld = internal topic = signalling topic name	201 – accepted 400 - error	Unsubscribe to the signalling topic provided as input in the body request.

⁸ Deployment details of the 5G EVE DCM can be found here: <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp3-dcm-deployment> (tag v0.2).

⁹ <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp3-dcm-handler/tree/v0.1>

DCM Handler	/dcm/publish/<topic>	POST	topic = signalling topic Array of records containing values with the information related to the topics to be subscribed/unsubscribed.	201 – accepted 400 - error	Publish the information related to the topics that will be created during the experiment (and deleted afterwards) in the signalling topics, so that the DCM triggers all the mechanisms to create the topics in Kafka and to distribute them to the proper entities.
-------------	----------------------	------	--	-------------------------------	---

Most of the monitoring service workflows from 5G EVE [2] do also apply in VITAL-5G. 5G EVE Workflows for the three phases of the monitoring service (i.e., subscription, monitoring and collection, and withdrawal) can be found in [16]. They will be similar to the ones used in VITAL-5G, except for the replacing of the 5G EVE components for their VITAL 5G equivalents, and except for the operations related with the DCM Site Plugins and the 5G EVE Interworking Layer.

5.3.2 Data Collection Storage

The DCS consists of two main tools: a data collection tool and a data storage tool. The data collection tool collects, aggregates and pre-processes monitoring data to extract the experiment results, metrics and KPIs generated for a given experiment from a specific Publish-Subscriber DCM. The storage tool indexes and stores data, allowing searching and filtering among all the data gathered by the DCM to obtain the useful information to be displayed to the experimenters, according to what results they expect to visualize during and after the experiment execution. Logstash and Elasticsearch, from the Elastic (ELK) Stack¹⁰, are the two main tools which will implement these functions, respectively. On one hand, Logstash¹¹ will be used for data collection, aggregation, and pre-processing. It is a server-side data processing pipeline that collects data from multiple input sources simultaneously, executes different transformations and enhancements and then ships the data to various supported output destinations; in our case, Elasticsearch¹². On the other hand, the main indexing and storage element for monitoring data will be Elasticsearch, a NoSQL database that is based on the Lucene search engine. It is an open source, distributed, RESTful, full-text and JSON-based search and analysis engine, which is easy to use, scalable and flexible.

In VITAL-5G, the 5G EVE DCS architecture is mostly kept, only applying minor modifications (see Figure 41):

¹⁰ <https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack/>

¹¹ <https://www.elastic.co/logstash/>

¹² <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

Figure 41: DCS architecture

The DCS has four main interfaces that will be offered to other VITAL-5G components:

- The interface with the DCM to subscribe/withdraw signaling topics and receive the monitoring data, as detailed in the previous subsection.
- The interface with the VITAL-5G Web GUI that will be used to select what network service KPI collection will be exported to the dashboards. This interface is exposed through the Dashboards Handler and Kibana.
- The interface with the Access Control. In the same way it was implemented in 5G EVE, the authentication of users and the definition of roles and restrictions to only access the data that corresponds to each user, depending on the use case, is provided through the VITAL-5G Access Control component (RBAC component in 5G EVE). However, for VITAL-5G we will updates to enable access control on a per-user and per-group basis.
- The interface with the Experiment LCM and Service LCM to allow them to activate/deactivate signaling topics processes.

Additionally, a PostgreSQL database is also deployed in the DCS to support logic modules such as the DSC Handler and the Dashboard Handler. The DCS Handler uses the database for saving the IDs of the Logstash pipelines, just in case of failure in the system. Regarding the Dashboard Handler, the PostgreSQL database contains the data model used for managing the dashboards visualized in the VITAL-5G Web GUI. Such model is presented in Figure 41. As with the VITAL-5G DCM, the VITAL-5G DCS implementation will use the 5G EVE DCS as baseline¹³.

¹³Details of the deployment for 5GEVE can be found here <https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-dcs-dv-deployment> (v0.2 tag).

Figure 42: Dashboard Handler data model

5.4 Experiment Lifecycle Manager (Experiment LCM)

The Experiment Lifecycle Manager (Experiment LCM) is the VITAL-5G component responsible for the creation of experiments and the execution of test cases to experimentally evaluate the functionalities and performances of vertical services composed of Network Applications and running in the 5G-enabled testbeds. The Experiment LCM offers a REST-based API on its NBI to allow VITAL-5G users, and in particular experimenters, to request new experiments, configure and launch their execution, retrieve information on their status and results, and finally terminate them. All these procedures can be requested using a REST client or, more simply, through the mediation of the VITAL-5G Platform GUI. All the requests are authenticated and authorized, so that experiments can be launched only on vertical services managed in the context of the same user group. The authentication and authorization mechanisms are implemented with the support of the VITAL-5G Access Control component, which is queried by the Experiment LCM at the beginning of each request processing.

In general, an experiment is associated to a Vertical Service which is managed through the Service LCM component. The lifecycles of vertical services and experiments are decoupled, giving the possibility to operate the service during the execution of an experiment. The management of the 5G network resources or edge/cloud computing resources is associated to the lifecycle of the service, e.g., for scaling or migration purposes.

Requesting the modification of the vertical service during the execution of its experiment allows to evaluate how dynamic changes in resource allocation impact the service performance.

Some restrictions are defined in order to maintain the consistency between a vertical service and an experiment executed over the service, in particular:

- An experiment can be created and executed only over already instantiated vertical services.
- Only a single experiment can be active for each vertical service, i.e., concurrent experiments over a single vertical service are not permitted.
- Vertical services cannot be terminated when a related experiment is still active.
- After an experiment is created, multiple consecutive but not parallel executions of that experiment can be launched, each of them with their own configuration.
- An experiment must be terminated before terminating the related vertical service.

Figure 43: High-level software architecture of the Experiment LCM

The Experiment LCM software is a Java based Spring-boot application that uses PostgreSQL and RabbitMQ as backend SQL database for persistency and for the asynchronous exchange of internal messages, respectively. The software code extends the 5G EVE Experiment Execution Manager, a component of the 5G EVE platform described in [18] released as open-source software available on GitHub¹⁴. However, since the VITAL-5G Experiment LCM handles also the creation and LCM of the experiments and not only their execution (as previously in 5G EVE) all the internal modules, the experiment FSMs, the REST controllers at the NBI, new SBI plugins and the internal data models and databases schemas will need to be updated accordingly. The high-level software design of the Experiment LCM is depicted in Figure 43.

¹⁴ <https://github.com/5GEVE/experiment-execution-manager/>

The core component of the Experiment LCM is the Experiment Execution Coordinator, which receives and coordinates the process of the requests issued from the experimenter through the REST API. All the requests are initially elaborated at the REST Controller and the token received in the HTTP messages is validated through the Access Control component. The requests related to experiment lifecycle actions (e.g., creation, execution, termination) are forwarded to the Experiment Execution Coordinator. Here, when the creation of a new experiment is requested, a new entry is created in the SQL database for persistency issues and a new Experiment Instance Manager is instantiated in memory. This manager is responsible to coordinate the procedures for the lifecycle of an experiment instance following the experiment FSM (see Figure 44) and handling the interaction with the other components of the VITAL-5G Platform through a number of SBI services. Each of them, implemented as a singleton, includes its own client to implement the interface with external software components. In case of asynchronous interactions, the notifications related to the various experiment instances are dispatched through the internal message broker to the Experiment Execution Manager and, from here, dispatched to the associated Experiment Instance Manager. The status and the information related to the experiment instances and their executions are kept updated into the internal PostgreSQL database and retrieved from the REST controller (through the JPA repository wrappers) in case of experiment queries received on the NBI.

The FSM describing the lifecycle of an experiment and the associated actions to be coordinated by the Experiment Instance Manager is represented in Figure 44.

When the experimenter requests an experiment execution, a new experiment instance is created, with its own FSM set to the status “creating experiment”. During this phase, the Experiment LCM authorizes and validates the received request, locks the vertical service interacting with the Service LCM and creates a new entry in the internal record. If all the steps are successfully performed, the FSM moves to the “created experiment” state, otherwise the state changes in “rejected” and the experiment cannot further proceed.

Once the experiment is in “created state”, the experimenter can request its execution. The experiment FSM will change state to “configuring”. In this phase, the Experiment LCM will interact with different VITAL-5G Platform components to configure all the necessary data (i.e., monitoring platform for topic creation, Results Analytics to notify new executions). In case of failure, the FSM evolves in a “rolling-back” state and after executing all roll-back activities, evolves in “failed”. In this case the experimenter can only request the termination of the experiment.

When the configuration phase is performed successfully, the FSM evolves to the “running” state. This is the core part of the execution. During this phase the experimentation occurs. Optionally, preconfigured testing scripts can be launched by the Experiment LCM. The termination of this phase is determined by a human interaction, invoking a stop execution request through the VITAL-5G Portal GUI, or by a timer indicating the experiment execution expiration. In both cases the experiment FSM evolves to the “validating” state. Here, the Experiment LCM invokes the Results Analytics to notify the termination of the execution and triggering implicitly the validation procedure at the Result Analytics. Once the validation is performed, the FSM state changes to “cleaning”. During this phase, the Experiment LCM performs some clean-up activities (i.e., reset of Network Applications’ configuration). If the clean-up phase fails, the FSM evolves to the “failed” state and the experiment can only be terminated by the experimenter. In case the clean-up is successfully performed, the experiment FSM moves back to “created experiment” state, where the experimenter can either run a new experiment execution or request its termination.

Figure 44: Finite State Machine for an experiment instance

The abstract messages of the interface exposed by the Experiment LCM is described in Table 38, including the input and output parameters.

Table 38: T&L Service Testing abstract messages

Message	Input Parameters	Output Parameters
Create Experiment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vertical Service Instance ID (String) Experiment Descriptor ID (String) - Experiment Configuration Parameters (Map<String, String>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment Instance ID (String)
Query Experiment	Filtering parameters, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment Instance ID Testbed Vertical Service Instance ID User 	List of experiment matching the query filter. For each of them: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment Status List<Experiment Execution>, where an experiment execution

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use case 	includes its own ID, status, configuration parameters and results.
Terminate Experiment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment Instance ID 	N.A.
Launch Experiment Execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment Instance ID (String) • Experiment Configuration Parameters (Map<String, String>) [override the global experiment configuration provided at creation time] • Experiment execution duration in minutes (integer, optional) • Diagnostics activation (Boolean) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment Execution Instance ID (String)
Stop Experiment Execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment Instance ID (String) • Experiment Execution Instance ID (String) 	N.A.

5.5 Results Analytics

To assist with the evaluation of the respective experimentation results, the VITAL-5G portal will also offer an advanced Results Analytics (RA) module. The RA module will be responsible for collecting all the metrics generated during an experiment, calculating the KPIs selected by the experimenter and validating them using a set of acceptable parameters (also provided by the experimenter). It is the first step in the performance evaluation process followed by the performance diagnosis (see Section 5.6), if requested, after the experiment has concluded.

The RA to be implemented in the VITAL-5G portal will be based on the respective Results analysis module of the 5G-EVE platform, as described in [19]. The key characteristics of the 5G-EVE based RA, that will be reused in VITAL-5G, are briefly described below, while the RA will be extended/updated to enable interfacing with the three VITAL-5G trial sites and to operate with the novel components of the project such as the Network Applications. The RA will directly interact with other key entities of the platform, such as the T&L Monitoring Service and the Experiment LCM while it will also be compatible with the respective orchestrators used in the three VITAL-5G trial sites. The RA module will provide the following main functionalities/sub-modules:

- **Analysis and validation:** this sub-module performs the analysis and validation operations and it handles the communication with other components of the 5G EVE platform using appropriate interfaces.
- **Experiment information storage:** This sub-module handles the management of the experiment data, pertaining to the RA operations, such as experiment IDs, metrics monitored, KPIs that need calculation, formulas for those KPIs and validation conditions.
- **Reporting:** This sub-module handles the generation of the final report based on the produced metrics and KPIs during the execution of the experiment and the requested validation conditions set by the experimenter during the experiment creation.

Figure 45 depicts the block-diagram of the RA module as well as its interfaces to the other modules of the VITAL-5G platform. The interface with the Service, Testing & Experiment Manager (i.e., the Experiment LCM module) and the interface with the Performance Diagnosis (PD) module are used for configuration of the module and operational control in a chain-like way where the configuration and control commands from the Experiment LCM get passed to the RA and then to the PD module. The RA also communicates, with the respective site's orchestrator in order to retrieve information regarding the network service and the topology of the experiment.

Lastly, communication between RA and the Service & Network Monitoring module includes consuming and publishing metrics and KPIs generated during the experiment execution. Interfacing the RA module with the other components is accomplished using a REST API, as depicted in Figure 46, exposing all the necessary functionalities.

Figure 45: VITAL-5G Results Analytics (RA) module – Block diagram

The Service Testing & Experiment Manager is responsible for configuring the RA for each experiment execution, by setting the values for key fields such as the **Experiment ID**, the **Network Service instance ID**, the **relevant Test Case IDs** and whether or not Performance Diagnosis (see Section 5.6) is enabled. The RA is tightly coupled with the Test Cases to be executed in each trial site, as it obtains the information regarding the measurement framework and metrics and KPIs to be measured for each test case and is responsible for the proper configurations to enable these measurements and the corresponding collection of data. The VITAL-5G Test Case template is defined in Deliverable D1.4 [6]. Both the metrics and the KPIs are accompanied with the information pertaining to the broker that will be used for consuming/producing these metrics/KPIs. A set of validation conditions is provided to validate each testcase, which is in turn passed to RA through this configuration. The configuration field contains two sub-fields, topics and publish that are the lists of the metrics and KPIs that will be monitored and published during the experiment execution. For reference, the information for metric and KPI objects to be used for the configuration of the RA follow the format seen Table 39 and Table 40, respectively.

POST	<code>/configuration/{executeID}</code> adds configuration for an experiment	↑
GET	<code>/configuration/{executeID}</code> get the configuration for an experiment	↑
GET	<code>/queue</code> dump list of active RAV instances	↑
GET	<code>/queue/{executeID}</code> dump results for specific experiment	↑
GET	<code>/queue/{executeID}/{tcID}</code> dump results for specific testcase	↑
GET	<code>/messages</code> dump the consumed messages per experiment and topic	↑
GET	<code>/validationResults</code> dump the validation results per experiment-testcase combination	↑
GET	<code>/terminate/{executeID}</code> terminate the experiment	↑
GET	<code>/terminate/{executeID}/{tcID}</code> terminate current testcase of experiment	↑
GET	<code>/validate/{executeID}/{tcID}</code> start testcase validation	↑
GET	<code>/status/{executeID}/{tcID}</code> show validation status	↑
DELETE	<code>/remove/{executeID}</code> remove a finished experiment	↑

Figure 46: REST API for the VITAL-5G RA

Table 39: RA metric information object [19]

Name	Description
brokerAddr	Broker endpoint to reach the topic
Topic	Topic name to consume the metric messages from
metric	Metric name

Table 40: RA KPI information object [19]

Name	Description
brokerAddr	Broker endpoint to reach the topic
topic	Topic name to publish the KPI in
kpi	KPI name

input	List of metrics to be used as input for the KPI formula
formula	Formula string to be evaluated using the inputs
interval	Interval of the calculation and publishing of the KPI
unit	Unit of the KPI values
lowerBound	Lower acceptable value for the validation of the KPI
upperBound	Upper acceptable value for the validation of the KPI

Besides the data collection and analysis, the RA is also responsible for the control and configuration of the Performance Diagnosis (PD) module, since its operation happens in parallel to the analysis and validation. The configuration information of the PD module is similar to the one used by RA but is enriched with additional information regarding the Network Service which is tested during the experiment. The additional information includes topology information for the elements taking part in the experiment as well as information regarding the resources used to deploy each of these elements. This information will be used in the Root Cause Analysis and the generation of a service profile for the given resources, respectively [19].

The VITAL-5G RA will support all the same functionalities, while it will have to be updated to operate with the VITAL-5G platform functional blocks (e.g., the VITAL-5G Experiment LCM instead of the 5G-EVE Experiment Execution Manager and direct communication with the trial site orchestrators instead of the Multi-Site Network Orchestrator (MSNO) in 5G-EVE) as well as to support the results collection and performance analysis of new entities such as Network Applications. The functional block diagram of the VITAL-5G testing & validation procedures depicted in Figure 3 of Deliverable D1.4 [6] shows the role of the RA component in the overall VITAL-5G platform, as well as the way it interacts/interfaces with the various other modules and components (e.g., descriptors, blueprints, etc.) of the platform.

5.6 AI-based Performance Diagnostics

The Performance Diagnosis (PD) module is responsible for collecting information during an experiment, parsing that information, analyzing it, and producing insights on the performance of the various elements that comprise the experiment. It is also responsible for detecting anomalies in the behavior of the various elements as well as identifying the root cause of possible problems or performance degradations during the experiment.

PD functionality description

Information collection, related to the first stage of the performance diagnosis operations, is managed by the Service & Network Manager (SNM). For the task of collecting and publishing data to the local and central broker, probes and data shippers will be used, respectively. The next step is pre-processing, where all the ingested information, comprising of metrics and KPIs will be parsed and transformed into appropriate structures, retaining temporal information that can be fed to the analysis algorithms to establish a behavior timeline for the various elements. The selected algorithms (see next sub-sections) will be used to perform the necessary AI based analytics and Root-Cause Analysis (RCA) on the resulting data to detect any faults or degradation on the observed performance of the used infrastructure. An additional level of in-depth analysis of the results will also be possible through the chaining of different algorithms. In this case, the results of the anomaly detection module are sent to the RCA module to determine the root of the detected anomaly. The targeted workflow of the Performance Diagnosis operations, as well as the interaction with the portal, the monitoring and RA components can be seen in Figure 47.

Figure 47: Performance Diagnosis module workflow [20]

Configuration and operational control of the module is handled by the corresponding RA module instance, since their operation will be closely tied together regarding the experiment information, stages, and results generation. This is accomplished using interfaces between the RA and PD modules.

The PD component upon receiving a registration request for an experiment, from the RA module, will initialize a new PD instance, retrieving the experiment topology from RA, creating the necessary data structures, and preparing the consumers for the metrics and KPIs. For the efficient detection of the root cause of a possible performance degradation the PD algorithms will be provided with information to match the service topology retrieved from the service descriptor to the metrics and KPIs generated, via the VNF/Network Application properties. During the experiment execution, all the generated metrics and KPIs will be collected and organized to create a behavior timeline for all the elements of the experiment that generate them. This process results in a list of vectors that will include all the available information for each element for every monitored moment of the experiment execution. These vectors will be fed to the PD algorithms to perform the actual performance diagnosis. The basic mechanisms that will be used to provide this functionality are Self-Organizing Maps (see Section 0) and Root Cause Analysis using adjacency lists (see Section 0).

PD interfacing with RA

The interface between the RA and the PD is used to control and configure the state of the PD module, according to the instructions received from the Experiment LCM. A similar REST API structure will be used for this interface as the one used for the communication of the RA module with the rest of the platform modules (Figure 46). Separate configuration and execution requests will be supported over the interface for better synchronization of the various stages of an experiment between the components.

AI technique used for PD

The Machine Learning (ML) technique selected for the implementation of the PD module is based on Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), which have been developed to detect abnormal behavior of nodes in a network service. In the case of the VITAL-5G deployment these nodes are the VNFs that compose a network service, i.e., the Network Applications composing the service.

SOM utilizes the concept of neurons, each with their individual weight and the learning process is based on unsupervised learning techniques, meaning that the learning process is not guided by predefined labelled outcomes, but through the discovery of underlying hidden patterns in the data set. More specifically, the learning of the SOM involves three main processes: i) the Competition, ii) the Cooperation and iii) the Adaptation process. During the first process, a distance is calculated to compare the similarity between the input vector sample and the weight vector of each neuron. The neuron with the weight more similar to the input vector is declared as the winner, known as Best Matching Unit (BMU). In the second process, the BMU determines the spatial location of the cooperation neurons, which are its neighbors. These neurons share common features and activate each other to learn from the same input. Finally, through the Adaptation process, the activated neurons become more like the input samples resulting in an increased chance of these neurons to respond to similar input data in the future.

The SOM technique's workflow is configured as shown in Figure 49.

Figure 48: SOM Anomaly Detection Workflow

The procedure to be followed in order to identify abnormal behavior of the nodes, is similar to the one used in 5G-EVE and is described by the following steps [19]:

- **Step 1 - Data collection:** The input data, which are the VNFs' performance metrics, are collected and stored as vectors.
- **Step 2 - Initialization of the topological map:** The topological map is composed of M neurons. Each neuron is represented by a weight vector. The weight vectors are initialized by random selection from the training data set, which consists of the performance data in normal condition.
- **Step 3 - Competition learning process:** For each input vector, the Euclidean distance between the weight vectors of the neurons is examined. The winning weight vector that is most similar to the input vector is

selected as BMU. This step is repeated until all input vectors are examined and assigned to their winning neurons.

- *Step 4 - Cooperation learning process*: Through this step, all the weight vectors are updated. Steps 3 and 4 are repeated until several iterations have passed.
- *Step 5 - Detect faults*: After training, the quantization error e_{QE} for each input vector is calculated. The quantization error is the distance between the input vector and the weight vector of the BMU. If the condition (5) is met, the input vector instance is considered abnormal: $e_{QE}(x_i) \geq \varepsilon(5)$, where ε is a predetermined threshold.

SOM was chosen over other algorithms, as it is able to combine and analyze various performance metrics (such as CPU utilization, memory utilization, disk I/O, network interface I/O, request latency etc.), to learn their underlying patterns and ultimately make decisions about the health status of VNFs without prior knowledge of specific thresholds.

The data input inserted in the SOM component consists of all the metrics and KPIs collected from each service node, in a synchronized manner, bundled as vectors. For the data output, the anomaly detection outcome consists of a Boolean decision on whether an input vector is characterized as an outlier or not, thus determining its health status, a health state that is produced depending on the distance of the vector from the BMU and the state itself. The input vector is enriched with this output and then passed on to the Performance Diagnosis module.

Root Cause Analysis (RCA)

A low complexity Root Cause Analysis algorithm will be implemented to localize a problematic node that causes performance degradation to other nodes and the deployed service in general. The basic principle of the algorithm is to check the reachability between the nodes (in our case instances that belong to VNFs), using each node's health status that is determined by the fault detection performed in the SOM module, and the network topology. The RCA module can also enable fault localization by identifying connected nodes that affect each other's status, e.g., non-healthy node connected to a healthy node, and both being detected as non-healthy.

The selected algorithm uses the health status provided, to label the service nodes as "Up" or "Down". An extra label "Unknown" is applied for the "Down" nodes that may be affected by other respective nodes. This is performed using an adjacency list that is obtained from the network topology. Specifically, an n-node undirected graph represented as an adjacency list is created using the virtual links of the topology. The nodes are numbered from 1 to n. Next, each "Unknown" node is examined to identify the Down nodes that may cause the node's non-healthy state. The algorithm's output is one list per "Unknown" node that contains the "Down" node(s) identified as the root cause for the respective node's performance issues. The workflow described above is structured in two parts of the algorithm: Part A determines the status of individual elements in the network ("Up", "Down", "Unknown"), Part B creates the Root Cause lists for the "Unknown" nodes [19]. Figure 49 depicts the steps of the RCA procedure to be applied in a block diagram [19].

The algorithm to be implemented for VITAL-5G will be capable of providing additional analysis capabilities by exploiting the advantages of the SOM tool (unsupervised deployment, heterogeneous input) and utilizing information provided by the VITAL-5G platform to follow the PD module's basic concept: perform network diagnoses of a deployed service without extensive knowledge of the service's functionality, metrics, and overall usage. Thus, it will comprise a useful tool that will complement the final Performance Diagnosis report produced for a performed experiment over the VITAL-5G portal.

Figure 49: Root Cause Analysis process block diagram

6 The VITAL-5G Management Backend

The Section describes the components that compose the VITAL-5G Management Backend. The management backend controls the core and internal logic of the VITAL-5G portal backend and the Open Online Repository. It includes three main components: the Access Control (Section 6.1) to manage the access and actions permissions in a role-basis for users and groups, the Multi-site Inventory (Section 6.2), a component to store the available information related with the testbed infrastructure, and the Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory (Section 6.3), to retrieve information about the network slices available on the testbeds or trigger their dynamic creation where supported.

6.1 Access Control

One of the core components of the VITAL-5G management backend is the Role Based Access Control (RBAC) component which will enable the authentication and authorization of all requested actions. An RBAC approach allows to regulate the access to the different resources according to the role of the user. The access control component will also enable the creation, listing, updating, and deleting of users and their corresponding authentication tokens. The Web GUI will also provide login functionalities. The functionality will be implemented using an Identity and Access Management based on Keycloak¹⁵.

Figure 50: Keycloak Core Concepts

Most VITAL-5G platform components need to interact with the Access control component to request authorization:

- The monitoring platform of the Portal Backend
- The REST controller of the T&L Service Lifecycle Manager
- The Data Collection Storage (DCS) component
- The REST controller of the Experiment Lifecycle Manager
- The Network Application catalogue for access control to private Network Applications and for the onboarding of new Network Applications.
- The Service catalogue for onboarding new T&L services with restricted Network Applications.
- The Experiment catalogue for onboarding of Experiment descriptors and blueprints.

All services of the VITAL-5G platform will be clients of Keycloak while related services (e.g., Experiment LCM, Network Applications Validator, etc.) will be placed at the same realm.

¹⁵ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Part of the functionality will be reused from 5G EVE and adapted with new roles for compatibility with the VITAL-5G platform. Group-based and user-based access control will also be added to allow fine-grained granularity in the permissions model. The access control functionality will be made available to the backend components via a REST API. The interaction with the REST API will be accomplished by requesting a token which will authorize subsequent requests for a certain period time. The RBAC will take care of refreshing and expiring access tokens.

Further information about the overall architecture has been provided in Section 8.3.1 of deliverable D1.2 [1].

6.2 Multi-site Inventory

The Multi-Site Inventory is a management backend software component that stores the information related to the systems, platforms, infrastructure capabilities and devices installed into the three VITAL-5G testbeds and exposes these details to the other internal components of the VITAL-5G Platform. Such information is required to establish the interaction between the VITAL-5G Platform backend and the testbeds' systems in a secure manner (e.g., with the NFV Orchestrator or slice management systems) and to properly use and configure their services (e.g., for monitoring purposes). Moreover, the information related to the physical infrastructure, e.g., for the networking of the testbed, is needed to properly select the testbeds' networks to interconnect the vertical services and their Network Applications to the 5G network. Finally, the subset of information stored in the inventory and related to public or use case specific IoT and T&L devices installed in the various testbeds, depending on their disclosure policies, can be partially exposed through the Portal GUI to VITAL-5G Platform users, so that they can design and implement their Network Applications to interact with those devices.

The data stored in the Multi-Site Inventory are expected to be configured through management actions by the administrator of the VITAL-5G Platform using administration access rights. Once available in the inventory, data can be queried without restrictions by all the backend components of the VITAL-5G Platform, also using administration access rights. The access to the data will be in general forbidden for the VITAL-5G users, which are not supposed to have visibility on the internal details of the testbed infrastructure, platforms and tools. Only a subset of information, declared as public or restricted to some use cases, will be available for visualization on the Portal GUI, mostly related to high-level capabilities of 5G and computing infrastructures of the testbeds, as well as specialized hardware devices made available for (3rd-party) Network Applications' interaction. The system and testbed administrators, when onboarding the information for a given testbed, will be able to specify the level of disclosure associated to the specific information item. For example, a given sensor will be visible only for users in a specific group/use case, the general capabilities of the 5G network will be publicly visible for all the users, the URL to access the NFVO will be restricted and visible only with administration rights, etc.

The software architecture of the Multi-Site Inventory is shown in Figure 51. Internally, the software is developed as a java Spring-boot application with a REST controller to expose its API and an SQL database based on PostgreSQL to store the data. The application will make use of JPA (Java Persistence Architecture) to model the various repositories of the inventories and apply filters to their queries. The requests received at the REST controller will be initially authorized interacting with the Access Control component and, based on user profile and information embedded in the token, the required disclosure policies will be applied. The software derives from the IWF Repository developed in the 5G EVE project [16], which will be extended in terms of data model and interaction with the VITAL-5G Access Control component.

Figure 51: Multi-site Inventory software architecture

6.3 Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory

The Multi-Site Inventory is a management backend software component that stores the information related to the 5G slices available in each of the three VITAL-5G testbeds, and exposes it to other components in the VITAL-5G Portal Backend and the Open Online Repository.

The 5G Slice information per site is required to expose the 5G capabilities of each testbed to components such as the Network Application Validator or the Intent-based Request Manager. Such slice information will be made available to properly match the Network Application and T&L Service requirements with the available 5G infrastructure in a given moment. This inventory mainly consists of a database, a REST API and a simple inventory service to add the required logic. It has a similar architecture of the previously described Multi-site Inventory

(see

Figure 52: Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory software architecture

), however it will only manage a single inventory with the 5G slice information in the different testbeds. All 5G Slice information stored in the inventory will be exposed through the Portal GUI to VITAL-5G Platform users, so that they can design and implement their Network Applications to use the available 5G Slices in each testbed.

The data stored in the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory is expected to be configured through management actions by the administrator of the VITAL-5G Platform using administration access rights. Once available in the inventory, data can be queried without restrictions by all the backend components of the VITAL-5G Platform, also using administration access rights.

By default, the access to the data will be public for the VITAL-5G components and users, since they should be able to know what the availability of 5G resources in each of the testbeds is. However, the administrator can also hide resources that may not be used (e.g., for maintenance, testing, etc.).

Internally, the software is developed as python application linked to a REST controller to expose its API and an SQL database based on PostgreSQL to store the data. The requests received at the REST controller will be initially authorized by interacting with the VITAL-5G Access Control component and, based on user profile and information embedded in the token, the required disclosure policies will be applied (e.g., only admin token

requests can onboard new slice information). The authentication procedure will be adjusted in terms of data model and interaction with the VITAL-5G Access Control component. There will be an additional Slice Manager Client, a component used to communicate with the different local 5G Slice Managers located in each of the testbed to retrieve or update information about their 5G capabilities. Such communication will be performed through a REST interface.

Figure 52: Multi-site 5G Slice Inventory software architecture

7 The VITAL-5G Open Online Repository

The section describes the software modules of the VITAL-5G Open Online Repository, which allows to publish and browse Network Applications, vertical services and experiments. The repository includes the Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue (section 7.1) to collect blueprints and descriptors for all the service design and experimental validation activities in VITAL-5G. The catalogue is complemented by the Network Application Validator tool (section 7.2), for the validation of Network Application packages, and the License Manager component (section 7.3) used for the validation of licenses related to proprietary Network Applications offered in the VITAL-5G catalogue.

7.1 Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue

The Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue is the component responsible for storing Network Application packages and blueprints, Vertical Service Blueprints and Descriptors (VSB and VSD), Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (ExpB and ExpD). The Catalogue maintains the synchronization with the NFVO catalogues at the three VITAL-5G sites, to keep the map between Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprints and the corresponding VNF packages and Network Service Descriptors (NSD), respectively. The functionalities of the various catalogues, the criteria applied for the access control of the VITAL-5G internal and external users to the various items stored in the catalogues, the interactions with the other VITAL-5G Platform components and the workflow for the onboarding of Network Application packages have been already presented in deliverable D1.2 [1]. This deliverable, and this section in particular, focuses on the software implementation of the component.

The baseline of the VITAL-5G catalogues software is the Portal catalogue of the 5G EVE platform [17] for onboarding and storage of VSBs, VSDs, ExpBs and ExpDs, with the integration of functionalities from the 5G EVE IWL catalogue [16] to support the interaction and synchronization towards multiple NFVO catalogues. Both 5G EVE catalogues are open-source software released under Apache 2.0 license. However, in VITAL-5G new features and information models are required: the onboarding of Network Application packages in a file storage, the store of Network Application blueprints in the internal SQL database, the interaction with the three VITAL-5G testbeds without the mediation of an interworking framework and the Network Application validation to be integrated in the onboarding lifecycle. For this reason, a full restructuring of the software is required, with the software design depicted in Figure 53.

The software is based on a Spring-boot application which exposes its north-bound interface, implemented as HTTP-based REST APIs with messages in JSON format, through a *REST controller*. The requests can be received from a VITAL-5G user (usually through the GUI) or from an external component of the VITAL-5G Platform. All the requests are authenticated and authorized on the basis of a token and interacting through the Access Control component through a dedicated *Access Control Client*. The authorized requests are then forwarded to the *Catalogue Service*, a singleton which implements the internal catalogue logic and coordinates the procedures for the onboarding of Network Application packages, vertical service/experiment blueprints and descriptors.

The onboarding of vertical service/experiment blueprints and descriptors follows a similar approach as in the original 5G EVE software. Their information models are also aligned with the ones defined in 5G EVE and documented in [14]. When the onboarding request is received, experiment blueprints and descriptors, as well as vertical service descriptors, are deserialized and their elements are stored in the local SQL database (based on PostgreSQL) through the wrapping of JPA (Java Persistence API) repositories. Once onboarded, they can be directly retrieved by the REST controller through the filtering queries implemented in each repository.

The onboarding of the Vertical Service Blueprint, which implies also the associated NFV NSD or its reference identifier (ID), integrates an additional step to synchronize with the NFVO at the target VITAL-5G testbed. This action is handled through the new *NFVO Synch Manager* submodule that interacts with the target NFVO through the mediation of the *NFVO Catalogue Service*. If a new NSD is provided in the request, the NFVO Synch Manager

requests the onboarding to the remote NFVO and uses the returned ID to associate the NSD to the VSB. Otherwise, if the request provides the NSD ID, the NFVO Synch Manager verifies the presence of the NSD on the remote NFVO and, if successful, the VSB onboarding proceeds with the storing of the VSB elements in the SQL database. The data model of the VSB has been updated with respect to the 5G EVE one; the VITAL-5G VSB data model is specified in Section 2. Moreover, the NSD format adopted in VITAL-5G follows the NSD model used in OSM, which is aligned with the ETSI NFV SOL 006 specification, with minor updates for configuration purposes.

The interaction with the NFVO catalogue is handled through the NFVO Catalogue Service. The details required to interact with the NFVO available in the target testbed are retrieved interacting with the Multi-site Inventory using the REST client submodule. In particular, information like the NFVO type, the URL of the catalogue and the credentials to access it are initially collected at the initialization of the system and refreshed when required. The NFVO Catalogue Service integrates the OSM plugin, which implements the REST client to interact with OSM R10 (the type of NFVO installed in each VITAL-5G testbed) and the translation of the interface messages.

Figure 53: Software architecture of VITAL-5G Network Application, Service and Experiment Catalogue

The onboarding and retrieval of Network Application packages is a completely new functionality that will be developed in VITAL-5G and integrated in the Catalogue. When onboarding a Network Application package, the VITAL-5G user must provide the related file in zip format, following the structure defined in Section 2.2. During the processing of the request, the *Catalogue Service* unzip the file, extracts its components and validates the structure and the format. If all the files are well-formatted, the Network Application blueprint embedded in the Network Application package is parsed and elaborated. The included information is evaluated on the basis of the capabilities offered by the target testbed for the given use case, as retrieved from the Multi-site Inventory. For example, in case of dependencies from a given type of hardware device (e.g., an IoT gateway or an AGV), the catalogue verifies that the required hardware is available on the testbed and that it is accessible for the use case declared in the Network Application blueprint. Moreover, the presence of the VNF packages associated to the Network Application is verified interacting with the NFVO Catalogue using the *NFVO Synch Manager* and the

NFVO Catalogue Service. If explicitly requested in the onboarding command, the *Catalogue Service* interacts with the Network Application Validator, using its REST client, to trigger a test deployment and validate the provisioning of the Network Application in the testbed.

At the end of all the verification procedures, the *Catalogue Service* upload the Network Application package and all the included artifacts in the local Object Storage, based on the MINIO¹⁶ open-source software. The interaction is mediated through the File Storage Client, which integrates the open-source java library implementing the client side of the Amazon's S3 API, adopted by MINIO. The selection of this software as object storage allows a nearly transparent migration towards Amazon S3 for more scalable deployments in a post-project phase.

The information elements of the Network Application blueprint, instead, are stored in the SQL database using dedicated JPA repositories, so that more efficient filtering queries can be implemented to browse the Network Application catalogue. The data model of the Network Application blueprint is defined in Section 2.2.1. and the blueprints initially defined for the Network Applications to be developed in the project are available in appendix.

In terms of queries, the VITAL-5G user can simply retrieve the Network Application blueprint, to get information about the structure and the characteristics of the Network Application, or download the entire Network Application package or some specific files (e.g., the documentation, the OpenAPI spec, etc.) to access the software. All the requests are validated on the basis of the access rules declared for the given Network Application, in order to limit the access to proprietary software.

The list of actions supported for the various kind of catalogue services' consumers at the REST-based NBI is reported in Table 41. As for other entities of the VITAL-5G platform, the consumers can be other internal software components of the platform or different categories of VITAL-5G users. The platform components will access with administration rights, in order to have the full view of the catalogue. The VITAL-5G users, instead, will have a limited access that depends on the user role (i.e., Network Application developer, Service Provider, Experimenter, System or Testbed Administrator) and the user group (see deliverable D1.2, Section 6.2 [1] for further details on the mapping between VITAL-5G services and user categories). The same role-based rules are applicable to both internal and 3rd-party users. The System Administrator profile has access to all the actions, and it is omitted from the table.

Table 41: VITAL-5G Catalogue supported actions on NBI

Action	Users
Onboarding of Network Application package	Network Application developer or Experimenter.
Modification/Removal of Network Application package	Only Network Application owner, for Network Applications not in use.
Query of Network Application blueprint	All users for public Network Applications. All users associated to the Network Application use case for restricted Network Applications. VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use.
Download of Network Application package	All users for public Network Applications. All users associated to the Network Application use case for restricted Network Applications with public software. VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use.

¹⁶ <https://min.io/>

Download of Network Application artifact	All users for public Network Applications. All users associated to the Network Application use case for restricted Network Applications with public software. VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use.
Onboarding of VSB	Service Provider or Experimenter. In case of VSB including restricted Network Applications, the onboarding is enabled only for users associated to the Network Applications use case, which must correspond to the VSB use case.
Modification/Removal of VSB	Only VSB owner, for VSBs not in use.
Query of VSB	All Service Providers or Experimenters for public VSBs. All users associated to the VSB use case for restricted VSB. VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use.
Onboarding of ExpB and its elements	Experimenter.
Modification/Removal of ExpB	Only ExpB owner, for ExpBs not in use.
Query of ExpB	All Experimenters for public VSB. All users associated to the ExpB use case for restricted ExpB. VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use.
Onboarding of VSD	Service Provider or Experimenter. In case of VSD associated to a restricted VSB, the onboarding is enabled only for users associated to the VSB use case.
Modification/Removal of VSD	Only VSD owner, for VSD not in use.
Query of VSD	All Service Providers or Experimenters for public VSDs. All users associated to the VSD use case for restricted VSD. VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use.
Onboarding of ExpD	Experimenter. In case of ExpD associated to a restricted ExpB, the onboarding is enabled only for users associated to the ExpB use case.
Modification/Removal of ExpD	Only ExpD owner, for ExpD not in use.
Query of ExpD	All Experimenters for public ExpDs. All users associated to the ExpD use case for restricted ExpD. VITAL-5G Platform components for internal use.
Forced removal of Network Application packages, VSB, VSD, ExpB, ExpD	System administrator (for clean-up purposes)

The abstract messages of the NBI exposed by the VITAL-5G Catalogue are described in Table 42, including the input parameters and the returned results where relevant. The information for access control (e.g., the user token) is omitted for simplicity, but present in the input parameters of every message; similarly, the output always includes a result code (e.g., successful, not permitted, etc.) which is omitted in the table.

Table 42: Abstract messages of VITAL-5G Catalogue NBI

Message	Input Parameters	Output
Onboard Network Application package	Network Application package	Network Application package ID
Remove Network Application package	Network Application package ID Forced (Boolean)	--
Download Network Application package	Network Application package ID	Network Application package
Download Network Application package artifact	Network Application package ID Network Application package artifact name	Artifact
Download VNF package	ID of the Network Application package associated to the VNF	VNF package
Get Network Application blueprint	Network Application package ID	Network Application blueprint
Get VNFD	ID of the Network Application package associated to the VNF	VNFD
Get Network Application blueprints list	Filter (e.g., use case, testbed, public vs restricted, category, etc.)	List <Network Application blueprint ID>
Onboard VSB	VSB NSD or NSD ID List<Translation rules> (optional)	VSB ID
Remove VSB	VSB ID Forced (Boolean)	--
Update VSB	VSB ID New VSB (optional) New NSD or new NSD ID (optional) New List<Translation rules> (optional)	--
Get VSB	VSB ID	VSB
Get VSBs list	Filter (e.g., use case, testbed, public vs restricted, category, etc.)	List <VSB ID>
Get NSD	ID of the VSB associated to the NSD	NSD
Onboard VSD	VSB ID VSD	VSD ID
Remove VSD	VSD ID Forced (Boolean)	--

Update VSD	VSD ID New VSD	--
Get VSD	VSD ID	VSD
Get VSDs list	Filter (e.g., use case, testbed, public vs restricted, category, etc.)	List <VSD ID>
Onboard ExpB	ExpB List <Test Case Blueprint> (optional)	ExpB ID
Remove ExpB	ExpB ID Forced (Boolean)	--
Update ExpB	ExpB ID New ExpB (optional) New List <Test Case Blueprint> (optional)	--
Get ExpB	ExpB ID	ExpB
Get ExpBs list	Filter (e.g., use case, testbed, public vs restricted, category, etc.)	List <ExpB ID>
Onboard ExpD	ExpB ID ExpD	ExpD ID
Remove ExpD	ExpD ID Forced (Boolean)	--
Update ExpD	ExpD ID New ExpD	--
Get ExpD	ExpD ID	ExpD
Get ExpDs list	Filter (e.g., use case, testbed, public vs restricted, category, etc.)	List <ExpD ID>

7.2 Network Application Validator

The Network Application validator is based on an evolution of the Java-based Blueprint validator tool¹⁷ available in 5G-EVE which will be used for static validation before Network Application runtime and with a dynamic KPI monitoring and validation tool at onboarding/runtime. The conceptual architecture of the Network Application validator is presented in Figure 54, while the validator itself will be introduced in a later release of the VITAL-5G platform and will be available as a software implementation in D2.3. The following section introduces a preliminary design of the Network Application validator, which will be refined during the Network Application development and implementation.

A short description of the components is as follows:

¹⁷ <https://github.com/5GEVE/blueprint-validator>

- **Blueprint validator tool:** validates the blueprint of the Network Application. If all requirements are met (valid JSON syntax, availability of data sources – sensors in the experiment facility etc.), then the Network Application is successfully validated and onboarding occurs.
- **Dynamic KPI monitoring and validation tool:** monitors dynamic KPIs at onboarding and during the testing runtime. If at any moment, the KPIs fall below the required values, the Network Application is invalidated, and the experimental test is terminated.
- **Metrics Bus:** built using the “Apache Kafka Bus”, it receives both monitoring and experiment data (KPIs) that it sends to the Dynamic KPI monitoring and validation tool.
- **Data from Network Application Deployment:** provides monitoring and experiment data (KPIs) from the experiment facilities during Network Application onboarding and/or runtime.

The design of the Testing Tool will be highly modular, allowing the easy extension of the base design with necessary functionalities from future Network Application developments. Integration of external tools as well as additional instrumentation can be added using custom exporters and common communication interfaces depending on the needs of each site.

Figure 54: Conceptual architecture of the Network Application validator

7.3 License Manager

The License Manager is a software component to store and validate the licenses for proprietary Network Applications issued by the Network Application developers to the various VITAL-5G users. The License Manager will be introduced in the next releases of the VITAL-5G platform, and its software will be delivered in D2.4. At this stage, only a preliminary design is provided, which will be further refined during the implementation activities.

As already introduced in D1.2, a Network Application developer may want to protect the intellectual property associated to a Network Application through the adoption of different types of software licenses, which regulate the usage and the deployment of the Network Application for the various users. In this case, the Network Application developer can use the VITAL-5G platform to issue the licenses for the users. This license, with the details about the permitted usage of the Network Application and the unique license key generated for the given user, is stored in the License Manager component (step 1 of Figure 55) and it will be used to validate the various steps of the Network Application lifecycle.

The license key is distributed to the user through a manual and offline procedure that is out of the VITAL-5G scope (step 2). The user will provide the key when requesting the instantiation of a vertical service including the Network Application protected by the license (step 3). The Service LCM (see Section 5.2), when processing the instantiation request, will interact with the License Manager using the key to validate the request of instantiation or any following scaling actions (step 4). Moreover, all the Network Application lifecycle management actions (instantiation, scaling, termination) will be notified to the License Manager. Here, the record of the Network Application usage for the given license will be updated accordingly and it will be used to validate the incoming requests.

Figure 55: Procedures for License Management

The types of licenses managed in VITAL-5G, i.e., flat, subscription, pay-as-you-grow, have been presented in D1.2, Section 8.2.3. Each type of license is associated to a different type of validation, e.g., based on the Network Application running time or the total number of concurrent instances. The related logic is encoded in the License Manager for each type of supported license and the type of information exchanged between Service LCM and License Manager varies accordingly.

The License Manager will be implemented from scratch as a Java Spring-boot application using PostgreSQL as backend SQL database. The initial high-level software architecture is represented in Figure 56.

Figure 56: License Manager high-level software architecture

The REST controller implements the NBI of the License Manager, which offers three main functionalities:

- Creation and management of licenses for VITAL-5G users. This service is invoked by the Network Application developer to issue or delete licenses for his/her own Network Applications.
- License validation. This service is invoked by the Service LCM component to request the validation of instantiation or scaling actions related to Network Applications protected by licenses, before proceeding with the actual execution of the command.
- Notification of Network Application lifecycle management actions, as instantiation, scaling and termination. This service is invoked by the Service LCM component after the execution of the related action, allowing the License Manager to keep the synchronization between its internal records and the current usage of the Network Applications.

License creation and management requests are processed by the License Storage Service component, which generates the unique keys for the new licenses and stores all the license information in the SQL database interacting with the related JPA repository. The License Validation Service implement the logic to evaluate the validation of the different types of licenses, on the basis of the information encoded in the license itself (as stored in the licenses database) and, where needed, the latest information on the usage of the Network Application for the given user. Such information is stored in the internal Network Application usage record (also part of the SQL database), which is maintained updated on the basis of the notifications received from the Service LCM.

The abstract messages of the NBI exposed by the License Manager are described in Table 43, including the input parameters and the returned output. The data model associated to the license information for the various types of licenses is still under definition.

Table 43: Abstract messages of License Manager NBI

Message	Input Parameters	Output
Create license	Network Application package ID User License Type (flat, subscription, pay-as-you-grow) License Information (depends on license type)	License Key
Remove license	License Key	--
Validate Network Application License	Network Application package ID License Key Network Application Lifecycle Action Type (instantiation, scale out) Network Application Lifecycle Action Details (depends on the action type, e.g., number of instances, target deployment flavour, etc.)	Validation Result
Notify Network Application Lifecycle Action	Network Application package ID Network Application Lifecycle Action Type (instantiation, scale in/out, termination) Network Application Lifecycle Action Details (depends on the action type, e.g., number of instances, target deployment flavour, etc.)	--

8 VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI

The VITAL-5G web-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) will be based on the Portal GUI of the 5G-EVE project, as it was described in the documentation of the 5G-EVE project [2]. Figure 57 shows the home page of the 5G-EVE project that has four main sections and accordingly their buttons: (i) Design Experiment, (ii) Request Experiments, (iii) Manage Experiment and (iv) Manage Site.

Figure 57: The home page of the 5G-EVE project [2]

8.1 Design Experiment in VITAL-5G

The VITAL-5G GUI will provide access to all the backend functionalities and tools of the VITAL-5G platform to design their experiments through the proper selection of experiments, Network Applications and services blueprints, and to offer intent-based service. Namely the blueprints of vertical services (Vertical Service Blueprint – VSB), contexts (Context Blueprint – CB), test cases (Test Case Blueprint – TCB) and experiments (Experiment Blueprint – ExpB) will be created in the Design Experiment stage. Additionally, access to the Network Application packages and their blueprints will be given. All these blueprints are a kind of “templates” that define the high-level features of Network Application services, execution environments and experiments, respectively. Besides the creation of the blueprints, the relevant KPIs to be recorded and visualized will be also offered.

The blueprints are enclosing several variable parameters that are defined by experimenters in order to tune the specific experiment instance and hardware through the Network Applications. An experiment blueprint with well-defined variable parameters is called Experiment Descriptor (ExpD) and it corresponds to a deployment model for the instantiation of an experiment, by describing the characteristics of intended experimental environment, as it is illustrated in Figure 58. The actors involved in the Design Experiment phase are Experimenters, Network Application Developers and Service Providers as they were listed in the Section 3.2 of the D1.2 [1] “5G System Specifications and Architecture”.

Figure 58: The instantiation of an experiment [2]

The 5G EVE GUI has a simple wizard to guide the users to create experiment blueprints that is called “Experiment Blueprint Builder”, see Figure 59. This wizard breaks down into steps where in the first step the user provides general information (e.g., name, version, and a short description). The second step is to select the test site of the experiment and the corresponding vertical/T&L service, and it is followed by the selection of the context blueprint to be used in the experiment. The fourth step is to upload the NSD of the service to be tested, which is a json file. The next step is the specification of translation rules, where the experiment developer specifies how the network service needs to be instantiated for different configurations of the experiments. In VITAL-5G translation rules are not mandatory; if not provided, the service is automatically instantiated with its default instantiation level. The final step is the specification of all the details related to the experiment execution and validation such as the specification of metrics and KPIs and the list of Testcase blueprints to be executed.

Figure 59: Experiment Blueprint Builder Wizard [2]

8.2 Data Visualization

The visualization mechanism will be based on the Collection and Storage component defined in Section 5.3.2 that is utilizing three open-source Elastic products:¹⁸ (i) Logstash for data collection, aggregation and pre-processing, (ii) Elasticsearch for data indexing and storage, (iii) Kibana for data visualization. Figure 60 shows the whole Collection and Storage component implemented in 5G-EVE, within the blue frame is the Elastic Stack toolchain that was integrated with the Apache Kafka broker¹⁹ as a data collection manager in order to deliver the monitored information to the Elastic Stack toolchain. Also, ELK Beats was integrated in order to collect different types of data and forward them into the Elastic Stack through the Kafka bus. Using Kibana, a new customizable and interactive dashboard will be created specifically for the VITAL-5G project to visualize the KPIs and the measurements from each experiment. The user will be able to filter the data based on customizable parameters and to select the type of the graph that want to apply on each series of measurements.

Figure 60: The Elastic Stack toolchain integrated with Beats and Kafka [2]

¹⁸ <https://www.elastic.co/what-is/elk-stack>

¹⁹ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

9 Conclusions

This deliverable presents a first detailed overview of the VITAL-5G Network Applications to be developed for the three VITAL-5G Use Cases. The list of Network Applications is grouped and mapped to the specific T&L Services and Use Cases they belong to, and for each Network Application, a first detailed description (including their component models and internal architecture) and a first blueprint design (in JSON file format) is given.

Additionally, following the VITAL-5G platform functionalities and requirements given the D1.2 [1], this deliverable provides with an initial implementation description of the VITAL-5G platform, and each software component within the VITAL-5G Portal Backend, the VITAL-5G Management Backend, the Open Online Repository and the VITAL-5G Web GUI.

The first release of the VITAL-5G platform software (early-drop) is planned in D2.2, scheduled for March 2022.

References

- [1]. VITAL-5G, Deliverable D1.2, “System Specifications and Architecture”, December 2021.
- [2]. H2020-ICT-17-2018 5G-EVE project, <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>. [Online]
- [3]. NFVSOL004. ETSI GS NFV-SOL 004 V3.3, Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) Release 3, https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-SOL/001_099/004/03.03.01_60/gs_NFV-SOL004v030301p.pdf.
- [4]. NFVSOL006. ETSI GS NFV-SOL 006 V3.3, Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) Release 3, https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_gs/NFV-SOL/001_099/006/03.03.01_60/gs_NFV-SOL006v030301p.pdf.
- [5]. OSM. Open Source MANO (OSM) <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/open-source-mano>. [Online]
- [6]. VITAL-5G, Deliverable D1.4, “Testing & Validation Methodology”, December 2021.
- [7]. 3GPPTS. 3GPP TS 28.541, Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Management and orchestration; 5G Network Resource Model (NRM); Stage 2 and stage 3 (Release 17), v17.4.0, September 2021.
- [8]. 5G-TRANSFORMER. H2020-ICT-2016-2 5G-TRANSFORMER project, <http://5g-transformer.eu/>.
- [9]. A Density-Based Algorithm for Discovering Clusters in Large Spatial Databases with Noise. Ester, M., et al. Portland, OR : AAAI Press, 1996. 2nd International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining. pp. 226–231.
- [10]. OPTICS: ordering points to identify the clustering structure. Ankerst, Mihael, et al. 2, 1999, ACM Sigmod Record, Vol. 28, pp. 49-60.
- [11]. LIBSVM : a library for support vector machines. Chih-Chung Chang , Lin and Chih, Jen. 2011, ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology, pp. 1-27.
- [12]. Cisco Solutions for Intent-Based Networking (IBN) Solution Overview. (2019, June 10). Retrieved from Cisco: <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/collateral/enterprise-networks/digital-network-architecture/nb-06-ibn-sol-overview-cte-en.html>. Cisco2019.
- [13]. 5G-EVE Deliverable D4.1 “Experimentation Tools and VNF Repository”, October 2019, <https://zenodo.org/record/3628201#.YYUq4mBBxPY>.
- [14]. 5G-EVE Deliverable D4.4 “Report on benchmarking of new features and on the experimental portal (2nd version)”, July 2020, <https://zenodo.org/record/3946283#.YYUYhGBBxPY>.
- [15]. 5G-EVE Deliverable 4.2, "First version of the experimental portal and service handbook" <https://www.5g-eve.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/5geve-deliverabled4.2-final.pdf>.
- [16]. 5G-EVE Deliverable D3.5 “Final implementation of the interworking reference model”, May 2021, <https://zenodo.org/record/4964933>.
- [17]. 5G-EVE Deliverable D4.6 Final version of the experimentation portal, <https://zenodo.org/record/4964994>.
- [18]. 5G-EVE Deliverable D5.2 "Model-based testing framework", <https://zenodo.org/record/3628341>.
- [19]. 5G-EVE Deliverable 5.5 "Performance diagnosis mechanism and reporting methodology document".
- [20]. 5G-EVE Deliverable D5.8 “Testing and validation methodologies final report with the final version of testing and validation suite”, May 2021, <https://zenodo.org/record/4965106#.YYVTX2BBxPY>.
- [21]. VITAL-5G, Deliverable D1.1, “Report on use case requirements”, June 2021, https://www.vital5g.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/VITAL5G-D1.1_Report-on-Use-case-requirements_v1_Final.pdf.

Annex I: Network Application Blueprints

9.1 VA1 blueprint: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "SensorIngestionAndAutomation",
  "name": "WINGS Distributed Sensor Ingestion and Automation",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "0.1",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "frontend_port",
    "mqtt_gateway_port",
    "http_gateway_port",
    "vpn_gateway_port"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application for ingestion of sensor data, actuator control and automation.",
  "atomicComponents": [{
    "componentId": "CoreIoTController",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "CoreIoTControllerInternal",
      "CoreIoTControllerFrontendExternal"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "VirtualNetworkGateway",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "VirtualGatewayRAN",
      "VirtualGatewayInternal"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "MqttGateway",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "mqttGatewayInternal"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "HTTPGateway",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "HTTPGatewayInternal"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "PersistenceService",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "persistenceServiceInternal"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {

```

```

        "componentId": "ReasoningEngine",
        "endPointsIds": [
            "ReasoningEngineInternal"
        ],
        "placement": "CORE"
    }
],
"applicationMetrics": [{
    "id": "state_change_rate",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "state changes per second",
    "name": "State change Rate",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}],
"infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "latency",
    "type": "LATENCY_RTT",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "RTT Latency",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}, {
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "bytes",
    "name": "Memory usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["CoreIoTController", "MqttGateway"]
}, {
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "bytes",
    "name": "Disk usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["CoreIoTController", "PersistenceService"]
}
],
"endPoints": [
    {
        "endPointId": "CoreIoTControllerInternal",
        "type": "INTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
        "endPointId": "CoreIoTControllerFrontendExternal",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
        "endPointId": "httpGatewayInternal",
        "type": "INTERNAL",
        "management": false,
        "mobileConnection": false
    }
]

```

```

    },
    {
      "endPointId": "persistenceServiceInternal",
      "type": "INTERNAL",
      "management": false,
      "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
      "endPointId": "ReasoningEngineInternal",
      "type": "INTERNAL",
      "management": false,
      "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
      "endPointId": "VirtualGatewayRAN",
      "type": "EXTERNAL",
      "management": true,
      "mobileConnection": true,
      "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
      "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",
      "sliceProfile": [{
        "type": "URLLC",
        "sliceServiceParams": {
          "reliability": "99,999"
        }
      }]
    },
    {
      "endPointId": "mqttGatewayInternal",
      "type": "INTERNAL",
      "management": false,
      "mobileConnection": false
    }
  ],
  "providedInterfaceSpec": [],
  "requiredEquipment": [{
    "id": "VPN_gateway",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "string",
    "interfaceProtocol": "Proprietary",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE",
    "mandatory": "true",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "type": "OTHER"
  }],
  "required5GCoreServices": [
  ],
  "licenseTemplates": [{
    "id": "wingsIoTLicense",
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "licenseFile": "licenses/wingsIoTLicense.txt"
  }]
}

```

9.2 VA2 blueprint: Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "DistributedSensorDataIngestionMLModule",
  "name": "BEIA and INCE Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion, post-
processing and predictions Module",
  "accessLevel": "RESTRICTED",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "listOfActiveSensors", "listOfStreams", "persistense_port",
"collection_port"
  ],
  "testbed": "DANUBE",
  "useCase": "UC2",
  "description": "Network Application with data ingestion, fusion and post-
processing functionality from distributed data sources. Issues warnings,
notifications, reporting, cloud based decisions from resulting analytics. Also,
included performing supervised and unsupervised algorithms on federated schema.",
  "atomicComponents": [{
    "componentId": "DataPersistence",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "accessData"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "DataCollection",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "testbedData"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "MLModule",
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "DataProxyServer",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "dataProxyServer_in",
      "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "placement": "EDGE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "DataProcessingServer",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "dataProcessingServer_in",
      "dataProcessingServer_out"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  }
],
  "applicationMetrics": [
    {
      "id": "aliveSensors_count",
      "interval": "1",

```

```

        "unit": "number of sensor datasets managed by the Network Application",
        "name": "Object count",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }
],
"infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "reliability",
    "type": "RELIABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "reliability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
},
{
    "id": "latency",
    "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "latency",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
},
{
    "id": "uplink_datarate",
    "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "uplink_datarate",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
},
{
    "id": "availability",
    "type": "AVAILABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "availability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["DataPersistence", "UnsupervisedModelling",
"SupervisedModelling", "MLRegistry", "DataCollection", "DataFusion"]
},
{
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": [
        "RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer",
        "QoSMonitoringServer",
        "MonitoringDashboard",
        "DataPersistence", "UnsupervisedModelling", "SupervisedModelling",
"MLRegistry", "DataCollection", "DataFusion"]
},
{
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",

```

```

        "name": "disk_usage",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE",
        "componentIds": [
            "RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer",
            "QoSMonitoringServer",
            "MonitoringDashboard",
            "DataPersistence", "UnsupervisedModelling", "SupervisedModelling",
"MLRegistry"]
    }
],
    "endPoints": [
        {
            "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_in",
            "type": "EXTERNAL",
            "management": true,
            "mobileConnection": true,
            "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
            "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",
            "sliceProfile": [
                {
                    "type": "URLLC",
                    "sliceServiceParams": {
                        "reliability": "99,998"
                    }
                }
            ]
        },
        {
            "type": "MMTC",
            "sliceServiceProfileParams": {
            }
        },
        {
            "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_out",
            "type": "EXTERNAL",
            "management": true,
            "mobileConnection": false
        },
        {
            "endPointId": "dataProcessingServer_in",
            "type": "INTERNAL",
            "management": false,
            "mobileConnection": false
        },
        {
            "endPointId": "dataProcessingServer_out",
            "type": "INTERNAL",
            "management": false,
            "mobileConnection": false
        },
        {
            "endPointId": "accessData",
            "type": "EXTERNAL",
            "management": true,
            "mobileConnection": false
        },
        {
            "endPointId": "testbedData",

```

```

        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [{
    "id": "DataPersistenceAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "accessData"
    ],
    "name": "Data persistence access interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP"
},
{
    "id": "DataCollectionAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "testbedData"
    ],
    "name": "External data inserted to data lake",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP"
},
{
    "id": "ProxyProvider_generic",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Output exported by the Data Proxy Server",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
        {
            "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
            "file": "softwaredoc/DataProxyServerDocs.json"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "id": "DataConsumer_generic",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "dataProcessingServer_in"
    ],
    "name": "Data consumed by Network Application Core",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "CONSUMER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [

```

```

        {
            "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
            "file": "softwaredoc/DataConsumerDocs.json"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "id": "FusedDataProvider_generic",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "dataProcessingServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Fused Data exported by Network Application Core",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
        {
            "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
            "file": "softwaredoc/fusedDataProviderDocs.json"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "id": "DashBoardMgmtAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Data Proxy Server management interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
        {
            "format": "OPEN_API",
            "file": "apis/dataProxyServerMgmtInterface.json"
        }
    ]
}
],
"required5GCoreServices": [],
"licenseTemplates": [
    {
        "id": "beiaLicense",
        "version": "1.0",
        "openLicense": true,
        "type": "INSTANCE_BASED", //to review
        "licenseFile": "licenses/beiaLicense.txt"
    }
]
}

```

9.3 VA3 blueprint: Predictive Maintenance

```
{
```

```

    "Network ApplicationPackageId": "DataMLModule",
    "name": "INCE Data Forecasting Clustering Module",
    "accessLevel": "RESTRICTED",
    "version": "1.0",
    "type": "service",
    "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
    "configurableParameters": [
      "persistense_port"
    ],
    "testbed": "DANUBE",
    "useCase": "UC2",
    "description": "Network Application for performing supervised and unsupervised
algorithms on federated schema.",
    "atomicComponents": [{
      "componentId": "DataPersistence",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "accessData"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE"
    },
    {
      "componentId": "UnsupervisedModelling",
      "placement": "CORE"
    },
    {
      "componentId": "SupervisedModelling",
      "placement": "CORE"
    },
    {
      "componentId": "AutotuneEngine",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "testbedData"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE"
    },
    {
      "componentId": "MLRegistry",
      "placement": "CORE"
    }
  ],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "availability",
    "type": "AVAILABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "availability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["DataPersistence", "UnsupervisedModelling",
"SupervisedModelling", "MLRegistry"]
  },
  {
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",

```

```

        "componentIds": ["DataPersistence", "UnsupervisedModelling",
"SupervisedModelling", "MLRegistry"]

    }, {
        "id": "disk_usage",
        "type": "DISK_USAGE",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "percentage",
        "name": "disk_usage",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE",
        "componentIds": ["DataPersistence", "UnsupervisedModelling",
"SupervisedModelling", "MLRegistry"]

    }
],
"endPoints": [
    {
        "endPointId": "accessData",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
        "endPointId": "testbedData",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [{
    "id": "DataPersistenceAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "accessData"
    ],
    "name": "Data persistence access interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP"
},
{
    "id": "DataCollectionAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "testbedData"
    ],
    "name": "External data inserted to data lake",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP"
}
]
}

```

9.4 VA4 blueprint: IoT Management Platform

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "IoTManagementPlatform",
  "name": "NXW IoT Alert and Event Manager",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "dashboard_port"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application for collection of IoT data and actuators control for heterogeneous and configurable devices, with mechanisms for unified data modelling, monitoring, and reporting. ",

  "atomicComponents": [{
    "componentId": "IoTAlertAndEventManager",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "alertEventManager"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "MessageBroker",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "messageBrokerRAN",
      "messageBrokerCore"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "DatastoreAndDashboard",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "datastoreDashboard"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  }
  ],
  "applicationMetrics": [{
    "id": "alarm_rate",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "alarms per second",
    "name": "Alarm Rate",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }
  ],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "reliability",
    "type": "RELIABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "reliability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }, {
    "id": "latency",
    "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
  }
  ]
}

```

```

        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "latency",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }, {
        "id": "uplink_datarate",
        "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "uplink_datarate",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }, {
        "id": "downlink_datarate",
        "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_DOWNLINK",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "uplink_datarate",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }, {
        "id": "memory_usage",
        "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "memory_usage",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE",
        "componentIds": ["IoTAlertAndEventManager", "MessageBroker"]
    }, {
        "id": "disk_usage",
        "type": "DISK_USAGE",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "memory_usage",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE",
        "componentIds": ["IoTAlertAndEventManager", "MessageBroker",
"DatastoreAndDashboard"]
    }
],
"endPoints": [
    {
        "endPointId": "alertEventManager",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
        "endPointId": "datastoreDashboard",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,

```

```

        "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
        "endPointId": "messageBrokerCore",
        "type": "INTERNAL",
        "management": false,
        "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
        "endPointId": "messageBrokerRAN",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": true,
        "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
        "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",

        "sliceProfile": [{
            "type": "URLLC",
            "sliceServiceParams": {
                "reliability": "99,999"
            }
        }]
    }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [{
    "id": "SymphonyAlertEventManagerAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "AlertEventManagerAdmin"
    ],
    "name": "Symphony Alert and Event management interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "softwaredoc/symphonyAlertEventManagerInterface.json"
    }]
}],
{
    "id": "IoTDeviceDataProvider",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "messageBrokerCore"
    ],
    "name": "IoT device input data bus",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",

```

```

        "file": "apis/symphonyAlertEventMessages.txt"
    }
  ], {
    "id": "SymphonyAlertEventManager",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "alertEventManager"
    ],
    "name": "string",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "OTHER",
    "protocol": "GUI",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
    ]
  }, {
    "id": "SymphonyDatastoreDashboard",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "dashboardDatastore"
    ],
    "name": "SymphonyDatastoreDashboard",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
      "format": "OPEN_API",
      "file": "softwaredoc/symphonDatastoreOpenAPI.json"
    }]
  }, {
    "id": "IoTDeviceDataConsumer",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "alertManager", "datastoreDashboard"
    ],
    "name": "MQTT_output",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "CONSUMER",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
      "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
      "file": "apis/symphonyAlertEventMessages.txt"
    }]
  }
],
"requiredEquipment": [{
  "id": "IoT_Supervisor",
  "location": "AREA_ID",
  "description": "string",
  "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
  "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE",
  "mandatory": "true",
  "accessLevel": "READ",
  "type": "OTHER"
}],
"required5GCoreServices": [

```

```

    ],
    "licenseTemplates": [{
      "id": "symphonyLicense",
      "version": "1.0",
      "openLicense": false,
      "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
      "licenseFile": "licenses/symphonyLicense.txt"
    }]
  }
}

```

9.5 VA5 blueprint: Real Time Digital twin

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "RealTimeDigitalTwin",
  "name": "IMEC Real Time Digital Twin",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "accuracy_level"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application for creating a real-time digital twin that constructs a local copy of a situational awareness model. It makes use of all available sensor data to build a real-time model of the environment. This model can afterwards be send to VS6 for assisted vessel navigation, and VS5 for remote monitoring purposes ",
  "atomicComponents": [
    {
      "componentId": "3DBoundingBoxEstimation",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "3DBoundingBoxEstimation_in",
        "3DBoundingBoxEstimation_out"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE"
    },
    {
      "componentId": "LateSensorFusion",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "lateSensorFusion",
      ],
      "placement": "CORE"
    },
    {
      "componentId": "OccupancyGridMap",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "occupancyGridMap"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE"
    }
  ],
  "applicationMetrics": [
    {
      "id": "dangerous_object_count",
      "interval": "1",
      "unit": "number of dangerous objects detected",
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    "name": "Object count",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "reliability",
    "type": "RELIABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "reliability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }, {
    "id": "latency",
    "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "latency",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }, {
    "id": "uplink_datarate",
    "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "uplink_datarate",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }, {
    "id": "cpu_usage",
    "type": "CPU_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "cpu_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["3DBoundingBoxEstimation", "LateSensorFusion",
"OccupancyGridMap"]
  }, {
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["3DBoundingBoxEstimation", "LateSensorFusion",
"OccupancyGridMap"]
  }, {
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["3DBoundingBoxEstimation", "LateSensorFusion",
"OccupancyGridMap"]
  }
}

```

```

],
"endPoints": [
  {
    "endPointId": "3DBoundingBoxEstimation_in",
    "type": "EXTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": true
    "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
    "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",

    "sliceProfile": [{
      "type": "URLLC",
      "sliceServiceParams": {
        "reliability": "99,998"
      },{
      "type": "eMBB",
      "sliceServiceParams": {
        "throughput": "50"
      }
    }]
  },
  {
    "endPointId": "3DBoundingBoxEstimation_out",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
  },
  {
    "endPointId": "lateSensorFusion",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
  },
  {
    "endPointId": "occupancyGridMap",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
  }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [{
  "id": "Overlapping3DBoundingBoxesProvider",
  "version": "1.0",
  "endpoint": [
    "3DBoundingBoxEstimation_out"
  ],
  "name": "Output generated from a 3D bounding box estimation",
  "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
  "role": "PROVIDER",
  "dataFormat": "json",

```

```

    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
      "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
      "file": "softwaredoc/3DBoundingBoxEstimationDocs.json"
    }]
  }, {
    "id": "Overlapping3DBoundingBoxesConsumer",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "lateSensorFusion"
    ],
    "name": "Input received from the set of 3D bounding boxes",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "CONSUMER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
      "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
      "file": "softwaredoc/3DBoundingBoxEstimationDocs.json"
    }]
  }, {
    "id": "Fused3DBoundingBoxesProvider",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "lateSensorFusion"
    ],
    "name": "Output generated from the Late Sensor Fusion",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [

    ]
  }, {
    "id": "Fused3DBoundingBoxesConsumer",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "occupancyGridMap"
    ],
    "name": "Input received from the Late Sensor Fusion",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "CONSUMER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [

    ]
  }, {
    "id": "OccupancyGridMapMgmtAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "occupancyGridMap"
    ],
    "name": "Occupancy Grid Map management interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",

```

```

    "attachedSpecifications": [{
      "format": "OPEN_API",
      "file": "apis/occupancyGridMapMgmtInterface.json"
    }]
  }, {
    "id": "OccupancyGridMapMgmtGUI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "occupancyGridMap"
    ],
    "name": "Occupancy Grid Map management GUI",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "HTML5",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [

    ]
  }, {
    "id": "OutputOccupancyExternal",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "occupancyGridMap"
    ],
    "name": "Ouput of the OccupancyGridMap i.e., Obstacles and Occupancy",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
      "format": "OPEN_API",
      "file": "apis/OutputOccupancyExternalAPI.txt"
    }]
  }
],
"requiredEquipment": [{
  "id": "IPCamera_type1",
  "location": "AREA_ID",
  "description": "Camera to provide video feed",
  "interfaceProtocol": "WebRTC",
  "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE",
  "accessLevel": "READ",
  "mandatory": "true",
  "type": "OTHER"
}],
"required5GCoreServices": [

],
"licenseTemplates": [{
  "id": "imecLicense",
  "version": "1.0",
  "openLicense": false,
  "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
  "licenseFile": "licenses/imecLicense.txt"
}]
}

```

9.6 VA6 blueprint: Data stream organization

```
{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "DataStreamOrganization",
  "name": "BEIA Data Stream Organization",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "listOfActiveSensors", "listOfStreams"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application that organizes data streams to be transmitted
to the navigation centre using 5G network parameters",
  "atomicComponents": [
    {
      "componentId": "DataProxyServer",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "dataProxyServer_in",
        "dataProxyServer_out"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE"
    }
  ],
  "applicationMetrics": [
    {
      "id": "aliveSensors_count",
      "interval": "1",
      "unit": "number of sensor datasets managed by the Network Application",
      "name": "Object count",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }
  ],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [
    {
      "id": "reliability",
      "type": "RELIABILITY",
      "interval": "10",
      "unit": "percentage",
      "name": "reliability",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    },
    {
      "id": "latency",
      "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
      "interval": "10",
      "unit": "seconds",
      "name": "latency",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    },
    {
      "id": "uplink_datarate",
      "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
      "interval": "10",
      "unit": "seconds",
      "name": "uplink_datarate",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    },
    {
      "id": "memory_usage",
      "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
      "interval": "10",
      "unit": "seconds",
      "name": "memory_usage",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE",
      "componentIds": [
        "RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer",
        "QoSMonitoringServer",
        "MonitoringDashboard"
      ]
    },
    {
      "id": "disk_usage",
      "type": "DISK_USAGE",
      "interval": "10",
      "unit": "seconds",
      "name": "memory_usage",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE",
      "componentIds": [
        "RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer",
        "QoSMonitoringServer",
        "MonitoringDashboard"
      ]
    }
  ],
  "endPoints": [
    {
      "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_in",
      "type": "EXTERNAL",
      "management": true,
      "mobileConnection": true,
      "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
      "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",
      "sliceProfile": [
        {
          "type": "URLLC",
          "sliceServiceParams": {
            "reliability": "99,998"
          }
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_out",
      "type": "INTERNAL",
      "management": true,
      "mobileConnection": false
    }
  ],
  "providedInterfaceSpec": [
    {
      "id": "ProxyProvider_generic",
      "version": "1.0",
      "endpoint": [
        "dataProxyServer_out"
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    ],
    "name": "Output exported by the Data Proxy Server",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "softwaredoc/DataProxyServerDocs.json"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "DashBoardMgmtAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Data Proxy Server management interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "apis/dataProxyServerMgmtInterface.json"
      }
    ]
  }
],
"required5GCoreServices": [],
"licenseTemplates": [
  {
    "id": "imecLicense",
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "licenseFile": "licenses/beiaLicense.txt"
  }
]
}

```

9.7 VS1 blueprint: Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "AutonomousNavigation",
  "name": "WINGS Autonomous Navigation",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "0.1",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "mqtt_gateway_port",
    "http_gateway_port"
  ],

```

```

"description": "Network Application for autonomous navigation and coordination
of AGVs",
"atomicComponents": [{
  "componentId": "LogisticsLCM",
  "endPointsIds": [
    "LogisticsLCMInternal"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
},
{
  "componentId": "PlanningComponent",
  "endPointsIds": [
    "PlanningComponentInternal"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
},
{
  "componentId": "ComputationalOffloadingComponent",
  "endPointsIds": [
    "ComputationalOffloadingInternal"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
}
],
"applicationMetrics": [{
  "id": "tasks_count",
  "interval": "3600",
  "unit": "tasks per hour",
  "name": "Number of Tasks",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}],
"infrastructureMetrics": [{
  "id": "cpu_usage",
  "type": "CPU_USAGE",
  "interval": "10",
  "unit": "percentage",
  "name": "CPU usage",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}, {
  "id": "memory_usage",
  "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
  "interval": "10",
  "unit": "bytes",
  "name": "Memory usage",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE",
  "componentIds": ["ComputationalOffloadingComponent",
"PlanningComponent"]
}, {
  "id": "disk_usage",
  "type": "DISK_USAGE",
  "interval": "60",
  "unit": "bytes",
  "name": "Disk usage",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE",
  "componentIds": ["ComputationalOffloadingComponent",
"PlanningComponent"]
}
],

```

```

"endPoints": [
  {
    "endPointId": "LogisticsLCMInternal",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
  },
  {
    "endPointId": "PlanningComponentInternal",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": false,
    "mobileConnection": false
  },
  {
    "endPointId": "ComputationalOffloadingInternal",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": false,
    "mobileConnection": false
  }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [],
"requiredEquipment": [{
  "id": "LocalVirtualNetworkGateway",
  "location": "AREA_ID",
  "description": "string",
  "interfaceProtocol": "Proprietary",
  "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE",
  "mandatory": "true",
  "accessLevel": "READ",
  "type": "OTHER"
}],
"required5GCoreServices": [
],
"licenseTemplates": [{
  "id": "wingsIoTLicense",
  "version": "1.0",
  "openLicense": false,
  "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
  "licenseFile": "licenses/wingsIoTLicense.txt"
}]
}

```

9.8 VS2 blueprint: Human-robot collaboration

```

{
  "NetworkApplicationPackageId": "HumanRobotCollaboration",
  "name": "WINGS Human Robot Collaboration",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "0.1",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_AGNOSTIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "mqtt_gateway_port",
    "http_gateway_port"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application for Human Robot Collaboration",

```

```

"atomicComponents": [{
  "componentId": "HMIassist",
  "endPointsIds": [
    "HMIassistInternal"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
},
{
  "componentId": "ComputationalOffloadingComponent",
  "endPointsIds": [
    "ComputationalOffloadingInternal"
  ],
  "placement": "CORE"
}
],
"applicationMetrics": [{
  "id": "mode_change_count",
  "interval": "3600",
  "unit": "mode changes per hour",
  "name": "Number of mode changes",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}],
"infrastructureMetrics": [{
  "id": "cpu_usage",
  "type": "CPU_USAGE",
  "interval": "10",
  "unit": "percentage",
  "name": "CPU usage",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE",
  "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
  "componentIds": ["ComputationalOffloadingComponent", "HMIassist"]
}, {
  "id": "memory_usage",
  "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
  "interval": "10",
  "unit": "bytes",
  "name": "Memory usage",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE",
  "componentIds": ["ComputationalOffloadingComponent"]
}, {
  "id": "disk_usage",
  "type": "DISK_USAGE",
  "interval": "60",
  "unit": "bytes",
  "name": "Disk usage",
  "metricGraphType": "LINE",
  "componentIds": ["ComputationalOffloadingComponent"]
}
],
"endPoints": [
  {
    "endPointId": "HMIassistInternal",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": false,
    "mobileConnection": false
  },
  {
    "endPointId": "ComputationalOffloadingInternal",

```

```

        "type": "INTERNAL",
        "management": false,
        "mobileConnection": false
    }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [],
"requiredEquipment": [{
    "id": "LocalVirtualNetworkGateway",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "string",
    "interfaceProtocol": "Proprietary",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE",
    "mandatory": "true",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "type": "OTHER"
}],
"required5GCoreServices": [
],
"licenseTemplates": [{
    "id": "wingsIoTLicense",
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "licenseFile": "licenses/wingsIoTLicense.txt"
}]
}

```

9.9 VS3 blueprint: AI/ML based automated fault detection

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "vs3",
  "version": "1.0",
  "name": "AI/ML based automated fault detection",
  "description": "Network Application supporting AI algorithms for automated fault
detection and predictive service management. It operates on the data collected by
the VA3 IoT Monitoring Platform to provide an enhanced elaboration logic of the
data. This Network Application is proprietary and it operates on a custom version
of the Symphony platform developed by NXW.",
  "testbed": "ATHENS",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_SPECIFIC",
  "vnfPackagePath": "path",
  "atomicComponents": [
    {
      "componentId": "aimlLogicEventGenerator",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "data"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE",
      "minInstances": 1,
      "maxInstances": 1
    }
  ],
  "endPoints": [
    {
      "endPointId": "data",
      "type": "EXTERNAL",

```

```
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
  }
],
"configurableParameters": {
  "configPort": "Port to access the configuration API",
  "queryPort": "Port to access the query API"
},
"applicationMetrics": [
  {
    "interval": 3600,
    "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "metricId": "anomalies",
    "name": "Number of detected anomalies",
    "topic": "vs3.anomalies",
    "unit": "items per hour"
  },
  {
    "interval": 3600,
    "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "metricId": "faults",
    "name": "Number of predicted faults",
    "topic": "vs3.faults",
    "unit": "items per hour"
  }
],
"infrastructureMetrics": [
  {
    "componentIds": [
      "aimlLogicEventGenerator"
    ],
    "iMetricType": "CPU_USAGE",
    "interval": "10s",
    "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "metricId": "cpuUsage",
    "name": "CPU usage",
    "unit": "percentage"
  },
  {
    "componentIds": [
      "aimlLogicEventGenerator"
    ],
    "iMetricType": "RAM_USAGE",
    "interval": "10s",
    "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "metricId": "ramUsage",
    "name": "RAM usage",
    "unit": "percentage"
  }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [
  {
    "id": "symphonyAimlConfigInterface",
    "version": "1.0",
```

```

    "endpoint": [
      "data"
    ],
    "name": "NXW Symphony AI/ML Config Interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "path"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "symphonyAimlQueryInterface",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "data"
    ],
    "name": "NXW Symphony AI/ML Query Interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "path"
      }
    ]
  }
],
"requiredInterfaceSpec": [
  {
    "id": "SymphonyDatastore",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "data"
    ],
    "name": "Datastore interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "role": "CONSUMER",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "path"
      }
    ]
  }
],
"softwareLicenses": [
  {
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,

```

```

        "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
        "licenseFile": "path",
        "softwareLicenseId": "symphonyLicense"
    }
],
"required5GCoreServices": [],
"requiredEquipments": []
}

```

9.10 VS4 blueprint: Technical Data Visualization

```

{
  "version": "1.0",
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "vs4",
  "name": "Technical data visualization",
  "description": "Provides real-time and customizable graphical interface for
visualization and management of specific IoT environments. It operates on top of
the VA3 IoT Management Platform. This Network Application is proprietary and it is
based on a custom version of the Symphony platform developed by NXW. ",
  "testbed": "ATHENS",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_SPECIFIC",
  "vnfPackagePath": "path",
  "atomicComponents": [
    {
      "componentId": "visualizationDashboard",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "data"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE",
      "minInstances": 1,
      "maxInstances": 1
    }
  ],
  "endPoints": [
    {
      "endPointId": "data",
      "type": "EXTERNAL",
      "management": true,
      "mobileConnection": false
    }
  ],
  "applicationMetrics": [
    {
      "interval": 3600,
      "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
      "metricGraphType": "LINE",
      "metricId": "queries",
      "name": "Number of queries processed per hour",
      "topic": "vs4.queries",
      "unit": "items per hour"
    }
  ],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [
    {
      "componentIds": [
        "visualizationDashboard"
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    ],
    "iMetricType": "CPU_USAGE",
    "interval": "10s",
    "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "metricId": "cpuUsage",
    "name": "CPU usage",
    "unit": "percentage"
  },
  {
    "componentIds": [
      "visualizationDashboard"
    ],
    "iMetricType": "RAM_USAGE",
    "interval": "10s",
    "metricCollectionType": "GAUGE",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "metricId": "ramUsage",
    "name": "RAM usage",
    "unit": "percentage"
  }
],
"configurableParameters": {
  "guiPort": "Port to access the GUI"
},
"providedInterfaceSpec": [
  {
    "id": "SymphonyVisualizationGuiInterface",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "data"
    ],
    "name": "Symphony technical visualization GUI",
    "commType": "OTHER",
    "dataFormat": "OTHER",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "path"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "SymphonyVisualizationMgmtInterface",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "data"
    ],
    "name": "Symphony technical visualization Management interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "path"
      }
    ]
  }
]

```

```

    }
  ]
}
],
"requiredInterfaceSpec": [
  {
    "id": "SymphonyDatastore",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "data"
    ],
    "name": "Datastore interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "role": "CONSUMER",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "path"
      }
    ]
  }
],
"softwareLicenses": [
  {
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "licenseFile": "path",
    "softwareLicenseId": "symphonyLicense"
  }
],
"required5GCoreServices": [],
"requiredEquipments": []
}

```

9.11 VS5 blueprint: Remote Vessel Monitoring

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "RemoteVesselMonitoring",
  "name": "Seafar Remote Vessel Monitoring",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "RESTRICTED",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_SPECIFIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "metricsToBeDisplayed"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application that serves as the interface with the vessel. It will monitor the vessel on-board sensors and will display the information to the user. It will provide also planning data and coordinates goals to VS7 and VS6 respectively.",
  "atomicComponents": [{

```

```

        "componentId": "VesselConnector",
        "endPointsIds": [
            "VesselConnector_in"
        ],
        "placement": "CORE"
    },
    {
        "componentId": "Network ApplicationConnector",
        "endPointsIds": [
            "Network ApplicationConnector_in"
            "Network ApplicationConnector_out"
        ],
        "placement": "CORE"
    }
],

"applicationMetrics": [{
    "id": "datasets_count",
    "interval": "1",
    "unit": "number of data models managed by the Network Application",
    "name": "Object count",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}],

"infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "reliability",
    "type": "RELIABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "reliability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}, {
    "id": "latency",
    "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "latency",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}, {
    "id": "uplink_datarate",
    "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "uplink_datarate",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
}, {
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["VesselConnector", "", "Network ApplicationConnector"]
}, {
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",

```

```

        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "memory_usage",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE",
        "componentIds": ["VesselConnector","", "Network ApplicationConnector"]
    }
],
"endPoints": [
    {
        "endPointId": "VesselConnector_in",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": true
        "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
        "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",

        "sliceProfile": [{
            "type": "URLLC",
            "sliceServiceParams": {
                "reliability": "99,998"
            },{
            "type": "eMBB",
            "sliceServiceParams": {
                "throughput": "50"
            }
        }
    ]
},
    {
        "endPointId": "Network ApplicationConnector_in",
        "type": "INTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    },
    {
        "endPointId": "Network ApplicationConnector_out",
        "type": "INTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [
    {
        "id": "DashboardGUI",
        "version": "1.0",
        "endpoint": [
            "dashboard"
        ],
        "name": "Interface for the Dashboard GUI",
        "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
        "dataFormat": "HTML5",
        "protocol": "HTTP",
        "attachedSpecifications": [

```

```

    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "VesselConnector",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "dashboard"
    ],
    "name": "Interface for the Dashboard GUI",
    "commType": "ASYNC_BIDIRECTIONAL",
    "dataFormat": "PROPRIETARY_FORMAT",
    "protocol": "Tcp Sockets",
    "attachedSpecifications": [

    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "VS8 Connector",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "dashboard"
    ],
    "name": "Connector to VS8",
    "commType": "PUB_SUB",
    "dataFormat": "PROPRIETARY_FORMAT",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [

    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "Network Application Connector",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "dashboard"
    ],
    "name": "Connector to different Network Applications",
    "commType": "ASYNC_BIDIRECTIONAL",
    "dataFormat": "PROPRIETARY_FORMAT",
    "protocol": "Tcp sockets",
    "attachedSpecifications": [

    ]
  }
],
"requiredEquipment": [{
  "id": "IPCamera_type1",
  "location": "AREA_ID",
  "description": "Camera to provide video feed",
  "interfaceProtocol": "WebRTC",
  "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE",
  "accessLevel": "READ",
  "mandatory": "true",
  "type": "OTHER"
}],
"required5GCoreServices": [

```

```

],
"licenseTemplates": [{
  "id": "seafarLicense",
  "version": "1.0",
  "openLicense": false,
  "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
  "licenseFile": "licenses/seafarLicense.txt"
}]
}

```

9.12 VS6 blueprint: Assisted vessel navigation

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "AssistedVesselNavigation",
  "name": "Assisted Vessel Navigation",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "RESTRICTED",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_SPECIFIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "optimizedMode"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application to enable an assisted navigation system of
a vessel. It assists a vessel to navigate thanks to the inputs from the Digital
Twin (VA5), the vessel location (VS8) and the global waypoints (VS5)",

  "atomicComponents": [{
    "componentId": "LocalPathPlanner",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "localPathPlanner_ran"
      "localPathPlanner_core"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  },
  {
    "componentId": "GlobalPathPlanner",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "globalPathPlanner",
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  }
  ],
  "applicationMetrics": [{
    "id": "estimatedErrorLocation",
    "interval": "1",
    "unit": "estimated error in meters on the vessel location",
    "name": "Object count",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  },
  {
    "id": "estimatedErrorSpeed",
    "interval": "1",
    "unit": "estimated deviation from the optimal in kph on the vessel speed",
    "name": "Object count",
  }
]

```

```

    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "reliability",
    "type": "RELIABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "reliability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }, {
    "id": "latency",
    "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "latency",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }, {
    "id": "uplink_datarate",
    "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "uplink_datarate",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }, {
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["LocalPathPlanner", "GlobalPathPlanner"]
  }, {
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["LocalPathPlanner", "GlobalPathPlanner"]
  }
  ],
  "endPoints": [
    {
      "endPointId": "localPathPlanner_ran",
      "type": "EXTERNAL",
      "management": true,
      "mobileConnection": true,
      "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
      "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",
      "sliceProfile": [{

```

```

        "type": "URLLC",
        "sliceServiceParams": {
            "reliability": "99,998"
        }
    }
}]]
},{
    "endPointId": "localPathPlanner_core",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
}, {
    "endPointId": "globalPathPlanner",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
}
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [{
    "id": "GlobalPathPlanner_inputs",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "globalPathPlanner"
    ],
    "name": "Inputs coming from external Network Applications",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "CONSUMER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "softwaredoc/GlobalPathPlannerDocs.json"
    }]
}, {
    "id": "GlobalPathPlanner_outputs",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "globalPathPlanner"
    ],
    "name": "Outputs generated in the GlobalPathPlanner to be converted to
local",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "softwaredoc/GlobalPathPlannerDocs .json"
    }]
}, {
    "id": "LocalPathPlanner_consumer",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "localPathPlanner_core"
    ],
    "name": "Input received in the Local Path Planner from the Global Path
Planner",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",

```

```

        "role": "CONSUMER",
        "dataFormat": "json",
        "protocol": "MQTT",
        "attachedSpecifications": [{
            "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
            "file": "softwaredoc/LocalPathPlannerDocs .json"
        }]
    }, {
        "id": "GlobalPathPlannerMgmtAPI",
        "version": "1.0",
        "endpoint": [
            "globalPathPlanner"
        ],
        "name": "Management interface for the GlobalPathPlanner",
        "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
        "dataFormat": "JSON",
        "protocol": "HTTP",
        "attachedSpecifications": [{
            "format": "OPEN_API",
            "file": "apis/globalPathPlannerMgmtInterface.json"
        }]
    }
],
"requiredEquipment": [{
    "id": "SeafarProxyControl_type1",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "End device to send the commands to the vessel",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PRIVATE",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "mandatory": "true",
    "type": "OTHER"
}],
"required5GCoreServices": [

],
"licenseTemplates": [{
    "id": "imecLicense",
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "licenseFile": "licenses/imecLicense.txt"
}]
}

```

9.13 VS7 blueprint: Navigation Speed Optimizer

```

{
    "Network ApplicationPackageId": "NavigationSpeedOptimizer",
    "name": "Digitrans Navigation Speed Optimizer",
    "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
    "accessLevel": "RESTRICTED",
    "version": "1.0",
    "type": "service",
    "specLevel": "VERTICAL_SPECIFIC",
    "configurableParameters": [
    ],
}

```

```

    "description": "Network Application developed to help vessel operators in their
daily navigation tasks by providing them with an optimal navigation speed so that
they arrive just in time.",

    "atomicComponents": [{
        "componentId": "NavigationSpeedOptimizer",
        "endPointsIds": [
            "navigationSpeedOptimizer"
        ],
        "placement": "CORE"
    }
],
"applicationMetrics": [{
    "id": "parallel_optimizations_count",
    "interval": "1",
    "unit": "number of current optimizations performed by the Network
Application",
    "name": "Object count",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"

}],
"infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["NavigationSpeedOptimizer"]

}, {
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["NavigationSpeedOptimizer"]
}, {
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": ["NavigationSpeedOptimizer"]

}

],
"endPoints": [
{
    "endPointId": "navigationSpeedOptimizer",
    "type": "EXTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
}
]

```

```

    ],
    "providedInterfaceSpec": [{
      "id": "TerminalPlanning",
      "version": "1.0",
      "endpoint": [
        "navigationSpeedOptimizer"
      ],
      "name": "API used to communicate with the Terminal Planner (NxtPort
PortCall+) ",
      "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
      "dataFormat": "json",
      "protocol": "HTTP",
      "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "softwaredoc/TerminalPlanningAPIServerDocs.json"
      }]
    }], {
      "id": "InlandNavigation",
      "version": "1.0",
      "endpoint": [
        "navigationSpeedOptimizer"
      ],
      "name": "Used to communicate with the Inland Navigation API (VisuRIS)",
      "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
      "dataFormat": "json",
      "protocol": "HTTP",
      "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "softwaredoc/InlandNavigationAPIServerDocs.json"
      }]
    }], {
      "id": "SpeedOptimizerClientGUI",
      "version": "1.0",
      "endpoint": [
        "navigationSpeedOptimizer"
      ],
      "name": "Client application to access the optimizer",
      "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
      "dataFormat": "HTML",
      "protocol": "HTTP",
      "attachedSpecifications": [
    ]
  }], {
    "id": "DashBoardMgmtAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "navigationSpeedOptimizer"
    ],
    "name": "Management interface for the Navigation Speed Optimizer",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
      "format": "OPEN_API",
      "file": "apis/speedOptimizerServerMgmtInterface.json"
    }]
  }
}

```

```

    }
  ],
  "requiredEquipment": [
  ],
  "required5GCoreServices": [
  ],
  "licenseTemplates": [{
    "id": "digitransLicense",
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "licenseFile": "licenses/digitransLicense.txt"
  }]
}

```

9.14 VS8 blueprint: Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "OnBoardDataCollection",
  "name": "Seafar/IMEC On Board Data Collection",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_SPECIFIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "listOfActiveSensors"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application that collects the the vessel on-board sensor data and will publicly export it to other Network Applications (VITAL5G and 3rd party).",
  "atomicComponents": [{
    "componentId": "DataProxyServer",
    "endPointsIds": [
      "dataProxyServer_in",
      "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "placement": "CORE"
  }
  ],
  "applicationMetrics": [{
    "id": "aliveSensors_count",
    "interval": "1",
    "unit": "number of sensor datasets managed by the Network Application",
    "name": "Object count",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }],
  "infrastructureMetrics": [{
    "id": "reliability",
    "type": "RELIABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "reliability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }], {

```

```

        "id": "latency",
        "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "latency",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }, {
        "id": "uplink_datarate",
        "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "uplink_datarate",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE"
    }, {
        "id": "memory_usage",
        "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "memory_usage",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE",
        "componentIds": ["RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer", "QoSMonitoringServer",
"MonitoringDashboard"]
    }, {
        "id": "disk_usage",
        "type": "DISK_USAGE",
        "interval": "10",
        "unit": "seconds",
        "name": "memory_usage",
        "metricGraphType": "LINE",
        "componentIds": ["RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer", "QoSMonitoringServer",
"MonitoringDashboard"]
    }
],
"endPoints": [
    {
        "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_in",
        "type": "EXTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": true
        "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
        "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",

        "sliceProfile": [{
            "type": "URLLC",
            "sliceServiceParams": {
                "reliability": "99,998"
            }
        }
    ]
    }, {
        "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_out",

```

```

        "type": "INTERNAL",
        "management": true,
        "mobileConnection": false
    }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [{
    "id": "ProxyProvider_generic",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Output exported by the Data Proxy Server",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "softwaredoc/DataProxyServerDocs.json"
    }]
}, {
    "id": "DashBoardMgmtAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
        "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Data Proxy Server management interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [{
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "apis/dataProxyServerMgmtInterface.json"
    }]
}
],
"requiredEquipment": [{
    "id": "SpeedSensor_type1",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "Sensor to provide vessel speed",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PUBLIC",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "mandatory": "true",
    "type": "OTHER"
}, {
    "id": "GPS_type1",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "GPS sensor to provide location of the vessel",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PUBLIC",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "mandatory": "true",
    "type": "OTHER"
}, {
    "id": "SensorHeading_type1",
    "location": "AREA_ID",

```

```

        "description": "Heading sensor to measure vessel orientation",
        "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
        "exposedAccessLevel": "PUBLIC",
        "accessLevel": "READ",
        "mandatory": "false",
        "type": "OTHER"
    }],
    "required5GCoreServices": [
    ],
    "licenseTemplates": [{
        "id": "imecLicense",
        "version": "1.0",
        "openLicense": false,
        "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
        "licenseFile": "licenses/imecLicense.txt"
    }]
}

```

9.15 VS9 blueprint: Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessels NAVROM

```

{
  "Network ApplicationPackageId": "OnBoardDataCollection",
  "name": "BEIA On Board Data Collection",
  "vnfPackagePath": "__Link__",
  "accessLevel": "PUBLIC",
  "version": "1.0",
  "type": "service",
  "specLevel": "VERTICAL_SPECIFIC",
  "configurableParameters": [
    "listOfActiveSensors"
  ],
  "description": "Network Application that collects the NAVROM vessel on-board sensor data and publicly exports it to other Network Applications (VITAL5G and 3rd party).",
  "atomicComponents": [
    {
      "componentId": "DataProxyServer",
      "endPointsIds": [
        "dataProxyServer_in",
        "dataProxyServer_out"
      ],
      "placement": "CORE"
    }
  ],
  "applicationMetrics": [
    {
      "id": "aliveSensors_count",
      "interval": "1",
      "unit": "number of sensor datasets managed by the Network Application",
      "name": "Object count",
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  }
],
"infrastructureMetrics": [
  {
    "id": "reliability",
    "type": "RELIABILITY",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "percentage",
    "name": "reliability",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  },
  {
    "id": "latency",
    "type": "LATENCY_USERPLANE_RTT",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "latency",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  },
  {
    "id": "uplink_datarate",
    "type": "USER_DATA_RATE_UPLINK",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "uplink_datarate",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE"
  },
  {
    "id": "memory_usage",
    "type": "MEMORY_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": [
      "RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer",
      "QoSMonitoringServer",
      "MonitoringDashboard"
    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "disk_usage",
    "type": "DISK_USAGE",
    "interval": "10",
    "unit": "seconds",
    "name": "memory_usage",
    "metricGraphType": "LINE",
    "componentIds": [
      "RemoteMonitoringBrokerServer",
      "QoSMonitoringServer",
      "MonitoringDashboard"
    ]
  }
],
"endPoints": [
  {
    "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_in",

```

```

    "type": "EXTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": true,
    "coverageArea": "AREA_ID",
    "radioAccessTechnology": "FIVE_G_NSA",
    "sliceProfile": [
      {
        "type": "URLLC",
        "sliceServiceParams": {
          "reliability": "99,998"
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "endPointId": "dataProxyServer_out",
    "type": "INTERNAL",
    "management": true,
    "mobileConnection": false
  }
],
"providedInterfaceSpec": [
  {
    "id": "ProxyProvider_generic",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Output exported by the Data Proxy Server",
    "commType": "SUBSCRIBE_NOTIFY",
    "role": "PROVIDER",
    "dataFormat": "json",
    "protocol": "MQTT",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "DOCUMENTATION",
        "file": "softwaredoc/DataProxyServerDocs.json"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "id": "DashBoardMgmtAPI",
    "version": "1.0",
    "endpoint": [
      "dataProxyServer_out"
    ],
    "name": "Data Proxy Server management interface",
    "commType": "REQUEST_RESPONSE",
    "dataFormat": "JSON",
    "protocol": "HTTP",
    "attachedSpecifications": [
      {
        "format": "OPEN_API",
        "file": "apis/dataProxyServerMgmtInterface.json"
      }
    ]
  }
]
],

```

```
"requiredEquipment": [
  {
    "id": "AIS_transponder",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "Transponder to provide vessel location",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PUBLIC",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "mandatory": "true",
    "type": "OTHER"
  },
  {
    "id": "2K_camera",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "Camera to provide video streaming from vessel",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PUBLIC",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "mandatory": "true",
    "type": "OTHER"
  },
  {
    "id": "Propulsion_engine",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "Propulsion engine readings to measure vessel speed",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PUBLIC",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "mandatory": "false",
    "type": "OTHER"
  },
  {
    "id": "Depth_probe",
    "location": "AREA_ID",
    "description": "Probe to measure water depth",
    "interfaceProtocol": "MQTT",
    "exposedAccessLevel": "PUBLIC",
    "accessLevel": "READ",
    "mandatory": "false",
    "type": "OTHER"
  }
],
"required5GCoreServices": [],
"licenseTemplates": [
  {
    "id": "imecLicense",
    "version": "1.0",
    "openLicense": false,
    "type": "APPLICATION_PROPRIETARY",
    "licenseFile": "licenses/beiaLicense.txt"
  }
]
}
```